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Mass drug administration for malaria burden reduction

Authors

Zachary D. Schneider, Monica P. Shah, Marisa C. Boily, Alexandra L. Busbee, Jimmie Hwang, Julie R. Gutman

Contact

gmpfeedback@who.int

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Mass drug administration for malaria burden reduction

Zachary D. Schneider¹, Monica P. Shah¹, Marisa C. Boily², Alexandra L. Busbee², Jimee Hwang³, Julie R. Gutman¹

1. Malaria Branch, Division of Parasitic Diseases and Malaria, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, GA USA
2. Rollins School of Public Health, Emory University, Atlanta, GA USA
3. U.S. President’s Malaria Initiative, Malaria Branch, Division of Parasitic Diseases and Malaria, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, GA USA

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List of Abbreviations

ACTs	Artemisinin-based combination therapies
AE	Adverse event
AQ	Amodiaquine
AS	Artesunate
CBA	Controlled before-and-after trial
CI	Confidence interval
CQ	Chloroquine
cRCT	Cluster-randomized controlled trial
DP	Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine
G6PD	Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase
ICC	Intracluster correlation coefficient
ITNs	Insecticide-treated bednets
IRS	Indoor residual spraying
ITS	Interrupted time series
MDA	Mass drug administration
NRCT	Non-randomized controlled trial
NRT	Non-randomized trial
OR	Odds ratio
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
Pf	Plasmodium falciparum
PQ	Primaquine
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
Pv	Plasmodium vivax
RCT	Randomized controlled trial
ROB2	Cochrane Risk of Bias 2
RR	Risk or rate ratio
SAE	Serious adverse event
SP	Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine
UCBA	Uncontrolled before-and-after trial
WHO	World Health Organization

Executive Summary

- ***P. falciparum*, moderate-high transmission settings:** A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area results in little to no effect on clinical malaria illness or parasite prevalence (low certainty evidence) due to *P. falciparum*. MDA reduces all-cause mortality within the first month post MDA, with a larger effect in children under 5 than in all ages, but there is little to no effect by 1–3 months post MDA. There may be some reduction in *P. falciparum* incidence in areas with moderate/high transmission 1–3 months post MDA (moderate certainty evidence). There may be little to no effect of MDA on *P. falciparum* prevalence from 4–12 and 12–24 months (low certainty evidence). We are uncertain whether MDA has any effect on *P. falciparum* incidence or *P. falciparum* clinical malaria incidence from 4–12 or 12–24 months as the certainty of evidence was very low or no studies were identified.
- ***P. falciparum*, low–very low transmission settings** A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area probably results in large reduction in *P. falciparum* prevalence and in a large reduction in *P. falciparum* incidence (moderate certainty evidence) but may have little to no effect on *P. falciparum* clinical malaria incidence (low certainty evidence) in areas with low/very low transmission 1–3 months post MDA. We are uncertain whether MDA reduces any *P. falciparum* outcome from 4–12 or 12–24 months post–MDA as the certainty of the evidence has been assessed as low or very low and no effect estimate was statistically significant for those time periods. There was no significant impact of MDA on anemia.
- ***P. vivax*:** The evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may result in a large reduction in *P. vivax* prevalence (low certainty evidence) at 1–3 months post–MDA, but we are uncertain whether MDA reduces *P. vivax* incidence or the incidence of clinical malaria due to *P. vivax* at 1–3 months post-MDA due to very low certainty evidence. We are uncertain whether MDA has any impact on *P. vivax* outcomes from 4–12 and 12–24 months as the certainty of evidence was assessed as very low or the evidence was assessed as low certainty and the effect estimate was not statistically significant.
- **Adverse events:** Adverse events (AEs) after MDA were rare. Among people who received MDA, MDA may have little to no effect on the frequency of serious AEs (SAEs)/ AEs, but the evidence is very uncertain.
- **Drug resistance:** Data on whether MDA increases drug resistance is limited, but based on one study in which drug resistance markers were collected, there does not appear to be an increase in drug resistance markers following MDA.
- **Contextual Factors:**
 - Values and preferences
 - Policymakers and scientists value effective interventions
 - Participants value reducing/eliminating malaria. Adult participants value low rates of adverse events. Children prefer tasteless/easy-to-swallow medications.

- Acceptability
 - Previous MDAs influenced acceptability both positively and negatively
 - Adverse events, economic impact (including time required to administer drugs or AE's during agricultural season), and mistrust of MDA staff lowered acceptability.
 - Sensitization, education, and inclusion of local staff were very important to improve acceptability
- Health Equity, Equality, and Non-Discrimination
 - No *direct* impacts, but acceptability drivers are unequally distributed; uptake and acceptability tend to be lower in high-risk communities. Ethnic minority communities may suffer from geographic isolation; specific efforts may be needed to reach them.
- Financial and Economic Considerations
 - Estimated costs per patient varied from USD ~3 to ~20, with better cost-effectiveness in high transmission settings.
- Feasibility and Challenges
 - Multiple studies noted participant distance or mobility as a major limitation. Mobility was primarily seasonal mobility related to agriculture. Religious mobility was also noted.

Summary of Findings Table

P. falciparum in moderate to high transmission settings

Patient or population: reducing burden of *P. falciparum* in high transmission settings

Setting: An area with ongoing moderate–high transmission of *P. falciparum* or malarigenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pf - Prevalence - Moderate/High Transmission - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	5 per 100	9 per 100 (3 to 27)	RR 1.76 (0.58 to 5.36)	786 (1 RCT) ¹	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) results in little to no difference in <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in moderate/high transmission areas - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA.
Pf - Prevalence - Moderate/High Transmission - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA - NRS	723 per 1,000	614 per 1,000 (564 to 672)	RR 0.85 (0.78 to 0.93)	1000 (1 observational study) ²	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^b	Mass drug administration (MDA) may reduce <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in moderate/high transmission areas - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA however the certainty of the evidence for this is very low.
Pf - Prevalence - Moderate/High Transmission - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	483 per 1,000	570 per 1,000 (430 to 754)	RR 1.18 (0.89 to 1.56)	1497 (1 RCT) ³	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in little to no difference in <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in moderate/high transmission areas - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA .
Pf - Prevalence - Moderate/High Transmission - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA - NRS	418 per 1,000	251 per 1,000 (230 to 280)	RR 0.60 (0.55 to 0.67)	3154 (1 observational study) ⁴	⊕⊕○○ LOW	The evidence suggests mass drug administration (MDA) may reduce <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence slightly in moderate/high transmission areas - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA
Pf - Prevalence - Moderate/High Transmission - 12–24 Mos. Post MDA - NRS	431 per 1,000	332 per 1,000 (302 to 362)	RR 0.77 (0.70 to 0.84)	3261 (1 observational study) ⁴	⊕⊕○○ LOW	Mass drug administration (MDA) may slightly reduce <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in moderate/high transmission areas - 12–24 Mos. Post MDA .
Pf - Incidence - Moderate/High Transmission - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	57 per 1,000	35 per 1,000 (23 to 52)	Rate ratio 0.61 (0.40 to 0.92)	820.25 (1 RCT) ⁵	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE	Mass drug administration (MDA) reduces the incidence of <i>P. falciparum</i> in moderate/high transmission areas - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA.

Patient or population: reducing burden of *P. falciparum* in high transmission settings

Setting: An area with ongoing moderate–high transmission of *P. falciparum* or malarigenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pf - Incidence - Moderate/High Transmission - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	108 per 1,000	98 per 1,000 (59 to 162)	Rate ratio 0.91 (0.55 to 1.50)	517.75 (1 RCT) ³	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^{a,b}	Mass drug administration (MDA) may have little to no effect on the incidence of <i>P. falciparum</i> in moderate/high transmission - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA as the evidence is very low.
Pf - Clinical Malaria Incidence - Moderate/High Transmission - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	2 per 1,000	1 per 1,000 (0 to 10)	Rate ratio 0.41 (0.04 to 4.42)	144422 (1 RCT) ⁵	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) makes little to no difference to the incidence of <i>P. falciparum</i> clinical malaria in moderate/high transmission areas - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA.
Pf -self-reported AEs - Moderate/High Transmission - cRCTs follow up: 2 days	133 per 1,000	333 per 1,000 (95 to 705)	OR 3.25 (0.68 to 15.53)	90 (1 RCT) ³	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^{a,c}	MDA may increase any Adverse Events among people who received MDA vs Control, but the certainty of the evidence is very low.
Pf - AEs among people who received MDA - Moderate/High Transmission - cRCTs	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	336821 (1 RCT) ⁵	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^{d,e}	MDA may have little to no effect on adverse events among people who received MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.
Pf - SAEs among people who received MDA - Moderate/High Transmission - cRCTs	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	336821 (1 RCT) ⁵	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^{d,e}	MDA may have little to no effect on SAEs among people who received MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval; RR: Risk ratio; OR: Odds ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: We are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect

Moderate certainty: We are moderately confident in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different

Low certainty: Our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect

Very low certainty: We have very little confidence in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect

Explanations

- Wide confidence intervals including both no effect and appreciable benefit/ risk
- High risk of bias in all included studies
- Rates of events in both arms are much higher than in other studies; unclear how questions were asked.
- Although an RCT, outcome was collected in MDA arm only, not in control group
- Unable to calculate effect measure in absence of control

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Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine compared to no medicine for reducing disease burden in delimited geographic areas with malaria transmission

Patient or population: reducing disease burden in delimited geographic areas with malaria transmission

Setting: An area with ongoing moderate-high transmission of P. falciparum or malariogenic potential

Intervention: therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine

Comparison: no medicine

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with no medicine	Risk with therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine				
Mean difference in Hb between day 1 and 7	The mean mean difference in Hb between day 1 and 7 was 0	MD 0.53 higher (0.27 higher to 0.79 higher)	-	680 (1 RCT)	⊕⊕⊕⊕ HIGH	
All-cause mortality <1 months post MDA among people of all ages	1 per 10,000	1 per 10,000 (0 to 1)	RR 0.68 (0.57 to 0.81)	7540998 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW _b	MDA may reduce all-cause mortality <1 months post MDA among all ages. However, it is possible that it makes little or no difference as the certainty of the evidence is very low
All-cause mortality <1 months post MDA among children under 5	3 per 10,000	1 per 10,000 (1 to 1)	RR 0.34 (0.25 to 0.47)	1353074 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW _b	MDA may reduce all-cause mortality <1 months post MDA among children under 5. However, it is possible that it makes little or no difference as the certainty of the evidence is very low.

Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine compared to no medicine for reducing disease burden in delimited geographic areas with malaria transmission

Patient or population: reducing disease burden in delimited geographic areas with malaria transmission

Setting: An area with ongoing moderate-high transmission of *P. falciparum* or malariogenic potential

Intervention: therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine

Comparison: no medicine

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with no medicine	Risk with therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine				
All-cause mortality 1–3 months post MDA among people of all ages	1 per 10,000	1 per 10,000 (1 to 1)	OR 1.77 (1.54 to 2.04)	11419195 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW b	MDA may increase all-cause mortality 1–3 months post MDA. However, it is possible that it makes little or no difference as the certainty of the evidence is very low.
All-cause mortality 1–3 months post MDA among children under 5	1 per 10,000	1 per 10,000 (1 to 2)	OR 1.13 (0.87 to 1.46)	2008720 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ VERY LOW a,b	MDA may have little to no effect on all-cause mortality 1–3 months post MDA among children under 5 as the certainty of the evidence is very low.

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval; OR: Odds ratio; MD: Mean difference; RR: Risk ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: We are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect

Moderate certainty: We are moderately confident in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different

Low certainty: Our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect

Very low certainty: We have very little confidence in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect

Explanations

a. Wide confidence interval which includes both no effect and substantial effect

b. Some bias in most/ all included studies

Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Setting: An area with ongoing low/ very low transmission of *P. falciparum* or malariogenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pf - Prevalence - Low/Very Low Transmission - 0–1 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	35 per 1,000	4 per 1,000 (1 to 18)	RR 0.12 (0.03 to 0.52)	718 (2 RCTs) ^{1,2}	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^a	MDA may result in large reduction in <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in areas with low/very low transmission – 0–1 Mos. Post MDA.
Pf - Prevalence - Low/Very Low Transmission - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	24 per 1,000	6 per 1,000 (4 to 10)	RR 0.25 (0.15 to 0.41)	6511 (5 RCTs) ^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8}	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE ^b	MDA probably results in large reduction in <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in areas with low/very low transmission - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA.
Pf - Prevalence - Low/Very Low Transmission - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	19 per 1,000	16 per 1,000 (11 to 23)	RR 0.82 (0.56 to 1.22)	5102 (3 RCTs) ^{1,2,3,4,5,6}	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^b	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in little to no difference in <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in low/very low transmission areas- 4–12 Mos. Post MDA.
Pf - Prevalence - Low/Very Low Transmission - 12–24 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	32 per 1,000	11 per 1,000 (2 to 63)	RR 0.34 (0.06 to 1.97)	1390 (1 RCT) ¹	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^{a,c,d}	Mass drug administration (MDA) may reduce <i>P. falciparum</i> prevalence in low/very Low transmission areas - 12–24 Mos. Post MDA - but the certainty of the evidence is very low.
Pf - Incidence- Low/Very Low Transmission - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	12 per 1,000	5 per 1,000 (3 to 8)	Rate ratio 0.37 (0.21 to 0.66)	811.55 (1 RCT) ⁸	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE ^b	Mass drug administration (MDA) probably reduces <i>P. falciparum</i> incidence slightly in low/very low transmission areas - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA.
Pf - Clinical Malaria Incidence - Low/Very Low Transmission - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	6 per 1,000	4 per 1,000 (1 to 17)	Rate ratio 0.58 (0.12 to 2.73)	130651 (2 RCTs) ^{7,8}	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^e	MDA makes little to no difference on the incidence of <i>P. falciparum</i> clinical malaria in low/very low transmission areas - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA.

Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Setting: An area with ongoing low/ very low transmission of *P. falciparum* or malariogenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pf - Clinical Malaria Incidence - Low/Very Low Transmission 4–12 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	11 per 1,000	5 per 1,000 (2 to 12)	Rate ratio 0.47 (0.21 to 1.03)	26576 (2 RCTs) ^{3,4,6,7}	⊕○○○ VERY LOW _{b,d,f}	MDA makes little or no difference on incidence of <i>P. falciparum</i> clinical malaria in low/very low transmission areas 4–12 Mos. Post MDA .
Pf - Clinical Malaria Incidence - Low/Very Low Transmission - 12–24 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	17 per 1,000	13 per 1,000 (3 to 51)	Rate ratio 0.77 (0.20 to 3.03)	23251 (1 RCT) ⁷	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^d	MDA may reduce the incidence of <i>P. falciparum</i> clinical malaria slightly in low/very low transmission areas - 12–24 Mos. Post MDA. However, the effects vary and it is possible that MDA makes no difference on the incidence of clinical malaria

Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Setting: An area with ongoing low/ very low transmission of *P. falciparum* or malarigenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pf - AEs - Low/Very Low - cRCTs	<p>SAE: Morris_2018 reported no SAEs, Shekalaghe_2011 reported two SAEs- a serious skin reaction and severe anemia, Eisele_2020 reported four SAEs, of which 3 were deemed unrelated to drug ingestion, and McLean_2021 reported 6 SAEs (3 deaths (all deemed unrelated to drug), one stillbirth, one miscarriage, and one episode of severe dehydration secondary to vomiting and diarrhea).</p> <p>AE: Morris_2018 used both active and passive detection of AEs; 298 individuals reported a total of 414 events out of 2411 doses of DP + single low dose primaquine; the most commonly reported AEs were nausea and vomiting (33.1% of all reports), dizziness, headache, and fatigue (23.5%), and stomach pain and diarrhea (18.9%). von Seidlein_2019 reported that "1,535 of 8,112 (19%) MDA participants recalled 2,577 AEs, of which 911 (35%) were considered related to the antimalarials; 592 (23%) of the 2,577 AEs were dizziness, 199 (8%) nausea, 96 (4%) vomiting, and 39 (2%) itching, and 1,653 (64%) participants reported a range of other minor complaints. There were no cases of severe haemolysis." Among 336,821 courses of DP, Eisele_2020 reported 687 AEs. The most common AE reported was gastrointestinal disturbances (diarrhea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and nausea) at 48.6%; dizziness 19.8%; headache 16.0%, and general body weakness at 11.4%. McLean_2021 reported 151 AEs out of a total of 10677 doses. The majority of these (120) were mild and dizziness and rash or itching were most commonly reported. Only 18 AEs were assessed as probably related to the medication.</p>			(4 studies) ^{1,2,3,7,8}	-	

Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Setting: An area with ongoing low/ very low transmission of *P. falciparum* or malariogenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pf - Serious Adverse Events - Low/Very Low - 0– 3 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	0 per 1,000	1 per 1,000 (0 to 11)	OR 3.61 (0.43 to 30.03)	6911 (1 RCT) ³	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE ^d	MDA probably results in little to no difference in serious Adverse Events - Within 3 Months, MDA vs Control.
Pf - Serious Adverse Events - Low/Very Low - 4–12 Mos. Post-MDA - cRCTs	3 per 1,000	5 per 1,000 (2 to 11)	OR 1.47 (0.68 to 3.20)	6911 (1 RCT) ^{3,g}	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE ^d	MDA probably results in a slight increase in serious Adverse Events - Within 12 Months, MDA vs Control.
Pf - Vomiting among people receiving SP+AS with or without PQ vs Placebo - Low/Very Low - cRCTs	43 per 1,000	24 per 1,000 (8 to 65)	OR 0.54 (0.19 to 1.54)	703 (1 RCT) ²	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE ^d	Mass drug administration (MDA) probably does not increase vomiting among people receiving SP+AS with or without PQ vs Placebo.
Pf - SAEs among people who received MDA - Low/Very Low - cRCTs	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	353143 (4 RCTs) ^{1,2,7,8}	- ^{h,i}	
Pf - AEs among people who received MDA - Low/Very Low - cRCTs	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	376807 (4 RCTs) ^{1,3,7,8}	- ^{h,i,j}	
Pf - Drug resistance markers among those who received the intervention - Low/Very Low - cRCTs assessed with: sequencing of PfKelch13 gene	269 patients with <i>P. falciparum</i> were identified at baseline., of which 221 completed at least one round of MDA and had parasites sequenced for PfKelch13. at baseline and 1 month post-MDA. At baseline, 10/221 were positive for PfKelch13 (4.5%) and one-month post MDA, there was 1 infection out of 14 (7%) remaining Pf infections that showed the PfKelch13 genotype.			269 (1 RCT) ³	- ^{h,i}	

Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of *P. falciparum* in low transmission settings

Setting: An area with ongoing low/ very low transmission of *P. falciparum* or malarigenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	No of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the relative effect of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval; RR: Risk ratio; OR: Odds ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: We are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect

Moderate certainty: We are moderately confident in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different

Low certainty: Our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect

Very low certainty: We have very little confidence in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect

Explanations

- High risk of bias in all included studies
- Some risk of bias in most/all included studies
- McLean had contact tracing for neighbors in 50 km surrounding positive cases in the intervention but not control arm; this effect measures the combined intervention.
- Wide confidence intervals including both no effect and appreciable benefit/ risk
- Substantial variability in point estimates including both appreciable risk and appreciable benefit.
- I-squared 72%
- None of the SAEs were considered related to study drugs
- Although an RCT, data on AEs, SAEs and drug resistance markers was only collected in the MDA arm, thus there is no control
- Unable to calculate effect measure as there is no comparison group
- Substantial variability in proportion of AEs across studies including minimal risk (<1%) to relatively large risk (12%)
- Small event numbers, does not meet Optimal Information Size

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Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of P. vivax

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of P. vivax

Setting: An area with ongoing transmission of P. vivax or malariogenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pv - Prevalence - 0–1 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	272 per 1,000	49 per 1,000 (22 to 109)	RR 0.18 (0.08 to 0.40)	234 (1 RCT) ¹	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE ^a	
Pv - Prevalence - 1–3 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	133 per 1,000	20 per 1,000 (13 to 32)	RR 0.15 (0.10 to 0.24)	2672 (2 RCTs) ^{1,3,4,5,6}	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^{c,d,e}	MDA results in a large reduction in P. vivax prevalence - 1–3 mos. Post MDA .
Pv - Prevalence - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	96 per 1,000	97 per 1,000 (84 to 113)	RR 1.01 (0.87 to 1.18)	6255 (2 RCTs) ^{1,3,4,5,6}	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^{c,f}	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in little to no difference in P. vivax prevalence - 4–12 Mos. Post MDA.
Pv - Prevalence - 12–24 Mos. Post MDA - cRCTs	175 per 1,000	142 per 1,000 (77 to 259)	RR 0.81 (0.44 to 1.48)	243 (1 RCT) ¹	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^{a,g}	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in a large reduction in P. vivax prevalence - 12–24 Mos. Post MDA. However, the effects vary and it is possible that MDA makes no difference on P. vivax prevalence.
Pv - Incidence - <1 Mos. Post MDA - NRS	Low		Rate ratio 0.15 (0.12 to 0.19)	226390 (2 observational studies) ^{2,8}	⊕⊕○○ LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in a large reduction in P. vivax incidence <1 mo. Post MDA.
	5 per 1,000 ⁸	1 per 1,000 (1 to 1)				
	High					
	180 per 1,000 ²	27 per 1,000 (22 to 34)				

Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of P. vivax

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of P. vivax

Setting: An area with ongoing transmission of P. vivax or malariogenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pv - Incidence - 1–3 Mos. post MDA - NRS	Low		Rate ratio 0.37 (0.32 to 0.43)	226390 (2 observational studies) _{2,8}	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) may reduce the incidence of P. vivax 1–3 mos. post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.
	5 per 1,000 ⁸	2 per 1,000 (2 to 2)				
	High					
	180 per 1,000 ²	67 per 1,000 (58 to 77)				
Pv - Incidence - 4–12 Mos. post MDA - NRS	Low		Rate ratio 0.15 (0.07 to 0.34)	223990 (1 observational study) ⁸	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) may reduce the incidence of P. vivax 4–12 Mos. post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.
	5 per 1,000 ⁸	1 per 1,000 (0 to 2)				
Pv - Clinical Malaria Incidence - 0–1 Mos. Post MDA - NRS	Low		Rate ratio 0.23 (0.21 to 0.25)	62744 (2 observational studies) _{9,10}	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in a large reduction in the incidence of P. vivax clinical malaria <1 mo. Post MDA, but the evidence is very uncertain.
	264 per 1,000	61 per 1,000 (55 to 66)				
	High					
	1,872 per 1,000	431 per 1,000 (393 to 468)				

Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of P. vivax

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of P. vivax

Setting: An area with ongoing transmission of P. vivax or malariogenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pv - Clinical Malaria Incidence - 1–3 Mos. post MDA - NRS	High		Rate ratio 0.29 (0.26 to 0.31)	62744 (2 observational studies) ^{9,10,11}	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^{a,d}	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in a large reduction in the incidence of P. vivax clinical malaria 1–3 mo. Post MDA, but the evidence is very uncertain.
	156 per 1,000	45 per 1,000 (41 to 48)				
Pv - Clinical Malaria Incidence - 4–12 Mos. post MDA - cRCTs	41 per 1,000	57 per 1,000 (40 to 80)	Rate ratio 1.38 (0.97 to 1.95)	3325 (1 RCT) ^{3,4,6}	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^{c,g,h}	Mass drug administration (MDA) may increase the incidence of P. vivax clinical malaria slightly 4–12 Mos. post MDA, but the evidence is very uncertain.
Pv - Clinical Malaria Incidence - 4–12 Mos. post MDA - NRS	156 per 1,000 ⁱ	112 per 1,000 (106 to 119)	Rate ratio 0.72 (0.68 to 0.76)	11300 (1 observational study) ^{9,11}	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in a large decrease in the incidence of P. vivax clinical malaria 4–12 mos. post MDA, but the evidence is very uncertain.
Pv - Clinical Malaria Incidence - 12–24 Mos. post MDA - NRS	156 per 1,000	6 per 1,000 (3 to 11)	Rate ratio 0.04 (0.02 to 0.07)	11300 (1 observational study) ⁹	⊕○○○ VERY LOW ^a	Mass drug administration (MDA) may result in a large decrease in the incidence of P. vivax clinical malaria 12–24 mos. post MDA, but the evidence is very uncertain.
Pv - SAEs - 0-3 Months post MDA - cRCTs	0 per 1,000	1 per 1,000 (0 to 11)	OR 3.61 (0.43 to 30.03)	6911 (1 RCT) ³	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE ^g	MDA probably does not increase serious Adverse Events - 0-3 Months post MDA.
Pv - SAEs- 4–12 Months post MDA - cRCTs	3 per 1,000	5 per 1,000 (2 to 11)	OR 1.47 (0.68 to 3.20)	6911 (1 RCT) ³	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE ^g	MDA probably does not increase serious Adverse Events - 4–12 Months post MDA.
Pv - SAEs among people who received MDA - cRCTs	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	37575 (2 RCTs) ^{1,3}	- ^{c,j}	

Mass drug administration (MDA) compared to standard of care for reducing disease burden of P. vivax

Patient or population: reducing disease burden of P. vivax

Setting: An area with ongoing transmission of P. vivax or malariogenic potential

Intervention: mass drug administration (MDA)

Comparison: standard of care

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with standard of care	Risk with mass drug administration (MDA)				
Pv - AEs among people who received MDA - cRCTs	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	37575 (2 RCTs) ^{1,3}	- ,j,k	MDA may have little to no effect on adverse events among people who received MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: Confidence interval; RR: Risk ratio; OR: Odds ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: We are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect

Moderate certainty: We are moderately confident in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different

Low certainty: Our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect

Very low certainty: We have very little confidence in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect

Explanations

- High risk of bias in all included studies
- Optimal information size not met
- High or unclear risk of bias in some/ all studies
- Completely non-overlapping confidence intervals
- I-squared 84%
- I-squared 74%
- Wide confidence interval; include both null effect and appreciable risk/ benefit
- I-squared 52%
- Calculated by applying the reported baseline incidence (156 per 1000) by the population (5650).
- Unable to calculate an effect estimate in absence of control
- Although data derive from an RCT, AEs were only reported in the intervention arm

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Explanations

- a. Wide confidence interval which includes both no effect and substantial effect
- b. Some bias in most/ all included studies

Background

Mass drug administration (MDA) for malaria

Malaria is a parasitic disease transmitted to humans through the bite of an infected female *Anopheles* mosquito and is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Of the four human *Plasmodium* species, *P. falciparum* accounted for 97% of the 229 million cases (95% confidence interval [CI] 211–252) in 2019.¹ Malaria is both preventable through use of vector control tools such as insecticide-treated bednets (ITNs) and chemoprevention such as seasonal malaria chemoprevention, and curable by effective treatment such as artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs).

Mass drug administration (MDA) consists of administering antimalarial treatment (irrespective of the presence of symptoms or infection) to all age groups of a defined population or every person living in a defined geographical area (except to those for whom the medicine is contraindicated) at approximately the same time and often at repeated intervals.² MDA targets the human parasite reservoir by both clearing existing parasites from the population and providing a prophylactic window (duration determined by the half-life of the antimalarial drug) in which new infections are prevented. The effectiveness of MDA may depend on the duration and mechanism of antimalarial action, coverage of vector control, the timing of rounds in relation to seasonal malaria peaks, and, most importantly, the coverage of the intervention, which can be improved by multiple rounds to target a greater proportion of the population and increased participation within a given round.³⁻⁵

Two species of malaria parasites, *P. vivax* and *P. ovale*, may cause acute infection while also developing a latent stage that remains dormant in the liver, called the hypnozoite. The hypnozoites can cause relapses many months, or even years, after the initial infection. An MDA strategy for these parasites may include the addition of a drug that targets hypnozoites to reduce the risk and rate of future relapses. Currently the only drugs that are effective against the liver stage parasites are among the 8-aminoquinolines. Because 8-aminoquinolines can cause severe hemolysis among persons with a deficiency of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD), an enzyme that helps red blood cells function, additional testing and pharmacovigilance are required when treating people with a drug in that class. Additionally, the drug currently recommended by WHO to treat hypnozoites (primaquine) requires a multi-day regimen. These considerations mean that recommendations related to MDA for *P. vivax* (or *P. ovale*, a parasite found much less frequently) are likely to be quite different than for *P. falciparum* and separate questions for MDA for *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* have been developed. MDA was explored both prior to and as part of the World Health Organization's (WHO) Global Malaria Eradication Program in the 1950s with limited success. Due to the availability of safe and long-acting ACTs, there has been renewed interest in MDA to reduce the burden of malaria morbidity and mortality and to accelerate transmission reduction for malaria elimination.⁶

MDA for burden reduction

MDA may be an effective strategy for reducing the burden of clinical disease by clearing existing and preventing new infections. Older studies have found reductions in epidemics of severe malaria⁷ and anemia⁸ following MDA. Recently, a multi-country trial in Southeast Asia found that three rounds of MDA with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DHAp) significantly reduced clinical malaria incidence by 59% over a 9 month period following the intervention (incidence rate ratio: 0.41, 95% confidence interval [CI]: 0.20-0.84).⁹ However, the effect on disease burden may vary by malaria transmission intensity; following four rounds of MDA in Zambia, there was a nearly 40% reduction in confirmed malaria illness incidence in intervention compared to control clusters in low transmission areas, but no difference in high transmission clusters.

The development of WHO guidelines on the use of MDA to reduce the clinical burden of malaria could be informed by a systematic synthesis of available evidence and contextual considerations.

Objectives

Main objective

To synthesize evidence about the efficacy and safety of giving a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial at approximately the same time to people residing in delimited geographic areas with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential (i.e., MDA) to reduce the clinical disease burden of malaria. Separate reviews for *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* were conducted.

Secondary objectives

1. To summarize evidence on contextual factors, including the valuation of the outcomes of interest, impact on equity, resource use, cost-effectiveness, acceptability, and feasibility of MDA.
2. To summarize findings from mathematical modeling studies with respect to the impact of different operational factors on the modeled efficacy of MDA, including optimal timing with respect to malaria transmission seasons, number of rounds, time between rounds, minimum coverage, and number of years.

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for these reviews

Types of study to be included

For the main objectives, the following study designs were **included**:

- Randomized designs (*P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* reviews)
 - Cluster-randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) with at least two clusters per arm
 - Cluster-randomized cross over trials with: (a) at least two clusters per arm and (b) a suitable washout period during which the intervention is no longer applied
 - Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs with at least four clusters
 - Cluster-randomized factorial designs with at least two clusters per level
- Non-randomized designs (*P. falciparum* reviews)
 - Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials with at least two clusters per arm
 - Controlled before-and-after studies (CBAs) with (a) a contemporaneous control group and (b) at least two sites per arm
 - Interrupted time series (ITS) studies with: (a) a clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred, and (b) at least three data points collected both before the first round of MDA and after the last round of MDA, measured at evenly spaced intervals (i.e. monthly)
 - Due to the seasonality of malaria transmission, if pre- and post-intervention data points are measured at different calendar months (i.e. different periods of the transmission season), a sensitivity analysis was performed to explore the potential bias introduced by including these studies if applicable.
- Non-randomized designs (*P. vivax* reviews)
 - Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials
 - Controlled before-and-after studies with a contemporaneous control group

- Interrupted time series (ITS) studies with: (a) a clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred, and (b) at least three data points collected both before the first round of MDA and after the last round of MDA, measured at evenly spaced intervals (i.e. monthly)
 - Due to the seasonality of malaria transmission, if pre- and post-intervention data points are measured at different calendar months (i.e. different periods of the transmission season), a sensitivity analysis was performed to explore the potential bias introduced by including these studies if applicable.
- Uncontrolled before-and-after studies (UCBA) or before-and-after studies with historical controls (if included in sufficient numbers, a sensitivity analysis was performed)

We **excluded** studies under the following conditions:

- For studies with a control group or control period (i.e., ITS and before-and-after studies):
 - The follow-up periods for the intervention and control groups were not identical
 - The timing of baseline and/or endline surveys differed in intervention and control groups
 - For ITS studies, the length of pre- and post-intervention periods differed
 - Background interventions were not equally implemented between intervention and control arms or control periods (i.e., the same set of co-interventions were not available in both arms) or were implemented at different times
- The intervention was administered to a subset of the population (i.e., targeted MDA by occupation or age)
- A sub-therapeutic antimalarial dose was administered for MDA

For the secondary objectives, all study designs including qualitative and economic evaluations were considered to synthesize contextual information. Mathematical modeling studies were included to inform operational parameters (reported separately).

Types of participants

Studies including adults and children living in a delimited geographic area with ongoing malaria transmission or malariogenic potential were included. We included studies in special groups (i.e., refugees and soldiers) if they met eligibility criteria and constituted the entire population of a delimited geographic area.

Types of interventions

Intervention arm

For the purpose of this review, MDA was defined as the direct administration of a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine (irrespective of the presence of symptoms or infection) to every person living in a defined geographical area (except for those for whom the medicine is contraindicated) at approximately the same time (synchronous) and often at repeated intervals. Due to the nature of the intervention, only studies that were carried out on entire populations at the same time were included. We excluded studies of chemoprevention in the form of individually timed (asynchronous) intermittent preventive treatment in sub-populations (i.e., pregnant women, children, or infants), specific settings (e.g., post-discharge chemoprevention), or MDA targeted to a subset of the population based on age, occupation, or another demographic characteristic.

For the effect on *P. falciparum*, antimalarials for MDA included drugs that act on blood-stage parasites alone or in combination with a gametocidal drug, but there were no restrictions on the specific antimalarials considered.

We included only studies that provided doses of antimalarials intended for curative purposes. A dose greater than the current standard prophylactic dose was considered as a therapeutic dose (e.g., chloroquine or amodiaquine at 300 mg of base weekly; pyrimethamine at 25 mg weekly; proguanil at 100 mg daily; mepacrine at 300 mg weekly in one dose or 700 mg; weekly in daily doses of 100 mg; and quinine at 325 mg twice a day).^{10,11} The minimum dosage of primaquine to be considered effective as a gametocide was a single dose of 0.25 mg/kg.

For the effect of MDA on *P. vivax*, the drug regimen included drugs for blood stages alone or both blood and liver stages (mass relapse prevention, or the mass administration of drugs for liver stages alone, is the subject of another review). To be considered a hypnozoitocidal therapeutic dose, primaquine must have been a minimum of 3.5 mg/kg total dose, administered for up to 8 weeks.

Control arm (for designs with a control group or control period)

The control group for cluster-randomized trials or CBAs included populations that did not receive any intervention or were administered a placebo; the control group for an ITS or UCBA was the pre-intervention period.

Background interventions

Studies where additional malaria interventions considered standard of care were implemented were included as long as interventions (both malaria and non-malaria) were balanced between intervention and control arms or control periods. Ideally, the population coverage levels of all other malaria and non-malaria co-interventions should be similar in both arms at baseline and were noted during data extraction.

Types of outcome measures

Studies reported at least one of the following to be included: one or more outcomes, data on contextual factors, or mathematical modeling results for variation in operational parameters. For outcomes that specified parasitological confirmation, possible diagnostic approaches included malaria rapid diagnostic test (RDT), microscopy, or molecular method such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

Critical outcomes were measured at the population-level as the intent of the intervention is to reduce transmission community wide. However, certain outcomes could also be measured among those receiving the intervention. If outcomes were reported for unspecified *Plasmodium* species, the local epidemiology of the study area was used to infer the predominant species. The following outcomes were assessed:

- **Incidence of confirmed malaria illness:** parasitologically-confirmed clinical (with symptoms such as fever) malaria infection as measured by passive surveillance or in a cohort
- **Incidence of malaria infection:** parasitologically-confirmed malaria infection, irrespective of symptoms, from active and/or passive surveillance in a cohort
- **Prevalence of malaria parasitemia:** measured in a cross-sectional survey with parasitologic confirmation
- **Prevalence of anemia:** defined by hematocrit < 33% or hemoglobin < 11 g/dL
- **Number of hospital admissions (all-cause and malaria specific)**
- **Number of cases or incidence of severe malaria**
- **Number of blood transfusions**
- **Mortality (all-cause)**
- **Adverse events**
- **Drug resistance:** the prevalence or frequency of molecular markers associated with antimalarial drug resistance

Contextual factors

Evidence for the following contextual factors were summarized if available:

- **Values and preferences:** the relative importance assigned to health outcomes by those affected by them; how such importance varies within and across populations; and whether this importance or variability is surrounded by uncertainty.
- **Acceptability:** the extent to which those benefiting from an intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the *intervention* to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention.
- **Health equity, equality, and non-discrimination:** the extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all.
- **Financial and economic considerations:** the cost, overall economic impact, cost-benefit, and/or cost-effectiveness
- **Feasibility and health system considerations:** barriers to implementation (i.e. resources available, programmatic considerations, existing and necessary infrastructure), interaction with existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce (including training)

Operational parameters

Insights from mathematical modeling on how variation in operational parameters alter the effectiveness of mass relapse prevention were summarized for at least the following parameters if available:

- Timing of rounds with respect to the transmission season
- Number of rounds
- Spacing of rounds
- Number of years for the intervention
- Coverage
- Adherence
- Dosage and dosage schedule

Timing of outcome measurement

The pre-intervention or baseline period was defined as 1-12 months prior to, or time period concurrent with, the first round of MDA (except for ITS, which is defined above).

The post-intervention period refers to the time period following the *last round* of MDA. For studies with a single round of MDA, the *last round* refers to the time period following the single round. For studies with multiple rounds, the *last round* refers to the last round that occurred during a given transmission season (last round of the first year). Although the protocol envisaged assessing subsequent years independently, this was ultimately not done.

For analysis, data were pooled into the following post-intervention time period categories: <1 month, 1–3 months, 4 to <12 months and 12–24 months following the last round of MDA. If multiple data points were available within the same time period category, then the latest measure was used, except when prevalence was reported at regularly recurring time intervals, in which case the data were averaged.

Search methods for identification of studies

Literature searches were not restricted to specific study designs or restricted by date. Systematic review teams included studies that met the eligibility criteria, regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, and in progress). In addition to studies evaluating the efficacy or effectiveness of MDA, we screened all papers (qualitative and quantitative) from the search for studies which could contribute additional information on acceptability, feasibility, operational considerations, costing, antimalarial drug resistance, adherence to treatment and other factors. Both studies using empirical data and mathematical modeling were included.

Electronic database searches

We searched the following databases using the search terms and strategy described in Appendix 2 from 2012 onwards: Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library; MEDLINE (Pubmed); EMBASE (OVID); and LILACS. We also searched the WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP; <http://www.who.int/ictrp/en/>) and ClinicalTrials.gov (<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/home>) for trials in progress, using “malaria” and “mass drug administration” as search terms.

For articles prior to 2012, we screened both included and excluded articles identified from a Cochrane Review on MDA published in 2013¹². The Cochrane MDA Review used a similar database search strategy as described in Appendix 2 and the search was updated in February 2013 prior to publication.

Searching other resources

Reference lists

Additionally, we reviewed the reference lists of all studies and articles identified by the above methods and those listed in review articles¹²⁻¹⁶ for additional relevant studies.

Conference proceedings

We searched the following recent proceedings for relevant abstracts: Sixth Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Durban, South Africa; October 2013), Seventh Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Dakar, Senegal; April 2018), American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) 62nd Annual Meeting (Washington, DC, USA; November 2013), ASTMH 63rd Annual Meeting (New Orleans, LA, USA; November 2014), ASTMH 64th Annual Meeting (Philadelphia, PA, USA; October 2015), ASTMH 65th Annual Meeting (Atlanta, GA, USA; November 2016), ASTMH 66th Annual Meeting (Baltimore, MD, USA; November 2017), ASTMH 67th Annual Meeting (New Orleans, LA, USA; October 2018), and ASTMH 68th Annual Meeting (National Harbor, MD, USA; November 2019).

Researchers and organizations

In addition to the electronic searches described above, we consulted with the Malaria Elimination Initiative at the University of California at San Francisco and other relevant groups to identify both published and unpublished studies that might be available from other sources. We also contacted the Malaria Eradication Research Agenda Consortium, the Malaria Eradication Scientific Alliance, and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts identified from literature searches based on the pre-determined inclusion criteria. Any potentially relevant articles identified by at least one reviewer was evaluated by the same two reviewers for full-text eligibility based on the pre-determined inclusion criteria. A third reviewer was consulted to resolve any disagreements by discussion or consensus. At the beginning of the full-text screening, we conducted a calibration exercise with all reviewers in which the same set of articles was screened and discussed in order to ensure that the review process was standardized. Additionally, a full-text screening form with a step-by-step inclusion and exclusion checklist was provided to reviewers. At the full-text stage, we collated and linked different publications reporting on the same study. Full-text studies that did not meet eligibility criteria were listed with their reasons for exclusion in **Appendix 1**. The result of the study selection process is provided in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow diagram (Figure 1).

Data extraction and management

Two reviewers independently extracted information from studies on a pre-piloted electronic data extraction form after an initial calibration exercise. Any discrepancies in information were resolved by discussion to reach consensus or by consultation with a third reviewer. We contacted the original study author(s) to retrieve any missing data or for clarifications.

The following information were extracted:

- **Study design and setting:** dates of study, location of study, baseline malaria endemicity (prevalence or incidence), description of malaria seasonality, malaria species, vector species, antimalarial drug resistance context, study design type; method of randomization (if applicable), and statistical power.
 - For cRCTs: unit of randomization, adjustment for clustering and method used, intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC), number of clusters randomized and analyzed, number of participants, average cluster size, and features of the clusters (i.e., matching or buffer areas)
- **Participants:** Age groups and other demographic features of population included (i.e pregnancy, nutritional status) and population targeted by arm; degree of geographical isolation of the treated communities from the untreated communities.
- **Intervention:** MDA drug and dose, coverage, timing (number of rounds/campaigns, dates of rounds, duration implemented, and timing relative to malaria transmission season); availability of G6PD screening. Also, baseline coverage of malaria co-interventions in both intervention and control arms were recorded as well as adherence to the course of treatment if available.
- **Outcomes:** definition and measurement (including malaria diagnostic or surveillance method, population in which outcome was measured, and length of follow-up if relevant), time point(s) at which outcome was assessed relative to MDA rounds, sample size, incomplete outcomes or missing data.
- **Contextual factors:** information on contextual factors (as defined under “Types of outcome measures”) was extracted from studies and summarized, but these data were included in meta-analyses.
- **Sponsorship of the study:** the organizations funding and sponsoring the studies were extracted.

For dichotomous outcomes measured as prevalent cases, we extracted the number of cases and number of participants in each study arm. For dichotomous outcomes measured as rates or risks (incidence and mortality), we extracted the number of events, the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm, and a measure of variance (standard error).

For cRCTs we recorded the measure of effect (such as risk ratio [RR], odds ratio [OR], rate ratio [RR]) with confidence intervals (CI) or standard deviations. If the measure of effect was adjusted for baseline differences between study arms as pre-specified in a study protocol, then the adjusted measure of effect was extracted and the crude measure of effect was noted in a footnote.

For non-randomized studies, we extracted adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempted to control for confounding.

We included pre-intervention data up to one year prior to the intervention. Post-MDA data were extracted at the time points specified under each objective.

Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

Two members of the review team independently assessed the risk of bias for each study that met eligibility criteria using a tool designed to assess such risk and generated an overall assessment reported as low, some concerns and high, and summary graphs to display results. As the risk of bias in the effect of an intervention may be different for different outcomes, a 'Risk of bias' assessment for each outcome was made. We resolved any discrepancies through discussion or by consulting a third member of the review team.

For each included cRCT, the revised Cochrane 'Risk of bias' (ROB2) tool was used¹⁷. We assessed non-randomized studies for risk of bias using key criteria summarized from a variety of risk of bias assessments for observational studies¹⁸. Uncontrolled before-and-after studies were assigned a high overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

Strategy for data synthesis

Measures of treatment effect

To calculate incidence of parasitemia or clinical malaria, the denominator was the person-time of observation, calculated as the size of the study or observed population multiplied by the number of months of observation and divided by 12 to calculate person-years. For prevalence of parasitemia or adverse effects, the denominator was the population sampled, and prevalence was expressed as a percentage.

For study designs with a contemporaneous control group, the effect of the intervention was compared using RRs for dichotomous outcomes. For before and after comparisons, the pre-intervention measurement was calculated during the same calendar months as the post-intervention comparison to minimize seasonal differences.

Unit of analysis issues

For cRCTs, measures of effect adjusted for clustering were used if available and when possible, otherwise, we adjusted the raw data using ICC values. The ICC value was obtained from the study or authors or obtained from similar studies to estimate the ICC. If we estimated the ICC, we performed sensitivity analyses to investigate the robustness of our analyses.

If studies had multiple intervention arms, treatment arms were combined if appropriate, or participants in the control group split so that they were only included once in the meta-analysis¹⁹.

Dealing with missing data

We attempted to contact study authors to obtain any missing data. No data imputation was applied.²⁰⁻²²

Assessment of heterogeneity

We assessed heterogeneity by examining forest plots for overlapping CIs. Statistical heterogeneity was examined using the I^2 statistic.

In cases of substantial heterogeneity (I^2 statistic value above 50%) or inconsistency in the direction of the effect with non-overlapping CIs, or both, then a meta-analysis was not performed. Clinical and methodologic explanations for heterogeneity were considered through subgroup analyses.

Assessment of reporting biases

Reporting bias was not examined due to the small number (<10) of included studies in each meta-analysis group.

Data synthesis

Data from randomized and non-randomized studies were pooled separately. RevMan 5.3 was used for meta-analysis of outcomes [Review Manager (RevMan) [Computer program]. Version 5.3. Copenhagen: The Nordic Cochrane Centre, The Cochrane Collaboration, 2014]. We used fixed-effects meta-analysis to report pooled effect estimates for outcomes with fewer than eight studies and random effects for outcomes with eight or more.^{23,24} When effect measures were adjusted for baseline differences or to control for potential confounding, estimates and their standard errors were entered as natural logarithms directly into RevMan using the generic inverse variance outcome.

Certainty of the evidence

Randomized trials (e.g., cRCTs, randomized cross-over trials, stepped wedge cluster randomized trials) started at a high certainty of evidence but could be downgraded for valid reasons within the following five categories: risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias. Non-randomized studies (e.g. CBAs) started at a low certainty of evidence but could be upgraded if there was a large or a dose response effect, and if all plausible residual confounding would have reduced a demonstrated effect or would have suggested a spurious effect if no effect was observed.²⁵ The certainty of evidence and results are summarized in the summary of findings tables.²⁶⁻²⁸

The certainty of evidence was evaluated using the GRADE approach²⁶ and each outcome was rated as described by Balshem et. al.²⁵

- High: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.
- Moderate: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect.
- Low: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
- Very low: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Subgroup analysis

Potential effect modification by transmission level (very low-to-low defined as prevalence <10%, moderate-to-high ($\geq 10\%$))²⁹ was examined for studies of *Plasmodium falciparum*. Other potential subgroup analyses prespecified in the protocol, but not examined were level of vector control coverage at baseline ($\geq 80\%$ vs

<80%). Subgroup analyses were conducted when meta-analysis results indicated a high degree of heterogeneity (i.e., $I^2 > 50\%$).

Sensitivity analysis

We had planned to perform sensitivity analysis to explore the effect of exclusion of studies at high risk of bias (for allocation concealment, incomplete outcome data or critical risk of bias due to study design) on the overall results if appropriate, however sensitivity analyses were not conducted as we stratified analyses by randomized (none of which were at high risk of bias) and non-randomized trials (all of which were at high risk of bias).

Results

Description of studies

Included and excluded studies are described in detail in the Characteristics of studies tables (Appendix 1).

Results of the search

A total of 1,625 articles were identified from searching electronic databases, registers, and other sources: 740 records from database search from 2012 onwards (11 November 2020), 143 from previous Cochrane Reviews on MDA¹², and an additional 3 from other sources. After de-duplication, 859 articles were screened against title and abstract eligibility and, of these, 262 were assessed for full-text eligibility criteria (**Figure 1**).

Excluded studies

A total of 845 articles were excluded; 597 articles were excluded during title and abstract screening, and 248 were excluded during full text screening due to the following reasons: 44 No outcomes reported; 41 Cross reference with outcomes or additional details; 40 Contextual Factors; 30 Duplicate; 26 Intervention: not MDA; 18 Modelling data; 16 Design: control group criteria not met; 10 Intervention: not a treatment dose or insufficient info to determine; 7 Setting: emergencies/epidemics; 6 Design: <2 areas/clusters per group; 3 Design: No pre-intervention data or control; 3 Imbalance of background interventions; 3 Design: insufficient data points for ITS; 2 awaiting classification. Detailed reasons are provided in **Appendix 1**. Characteristics of included studies.

Included studies

A total of 15 studies were included (**Figure 2**): seven studies provided data on *P. falciparum* alone (4 cluster-randomized controlled studies (cRCTs; Eisele 2020, Morris 2018, Shekalaghe 2011, vonSeidlein 2003) and 3 non-randomized studies (Sterk 2020, Molineaux 1980, Schneider 1961)); two cRCTs provided data on both *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* (McLean 2021, vonSeidlein 2019), and an additional six provided data on *P. vivax* only (all non-randomized, before-after studies; Caceres 2008, Comer 1971, Gabaldon 1959, Jones 1958 (Pf data was not included as it did not meet inclusion criteria), Paik 1974, Simeons 1936).^{8,30-43} Studies reporting data on *P. falciparum* were stratified into areas of moderate to high (>10%) vs. low to very low (<10%) due to heterogeneity in outcomes. Since clusters in the Eisele trial were randomized by areas of low and high malaria transmission and the outcomes were stratified by endemicity (specified *a priori* by design), the two strata are presented separately as two studies (Eisele 2020a (low transmission); Eisele 2020b (moderate high transmission)). von Seidlein 2019 was a multi-country study which included four sites (Viet Nam, Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar). Due to the fact that there were some differences in the timing, bias, and outcomes available, the results stratified by site, with each site considered as a unique study, are presented here. Descriptive characteristics for the studies reporting empirical data are summarized in Table 1 and described in detail in **Appendix 1**. Characteristics of included studies.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Table 1. Summary characteristics of included studies

Study (location, years of study)	Study design	Mass drug administration		Outcomes reported (months of follow-up post-MDA)
		Rounds, interval, duration	Population targeted (coverage)	
Cluster randomized trials				
von Seidlein 2003 ⁸ (Gambia, 1999)	Cluster-randomized trial	All persons ≥ 6 months old; pregnant women excluded. 1 round SP+AS in June 1999	3,655 (89%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pf Parasitaemia prevalence (high transmission): 4–12 months
Shekalaghe 2011 ³⁹ (Zanzibar, 2008)	Cluster-randomized trial	Ages > 1 year, SPAS with PQ (0.75 mg/kg); 1 round; 16 days from January 2008-July 2008	1,110 (94.6%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pf Parasitaemia prevalence (low transmission): 0–1, 4–12 months
Morris 2018 ³⁶ (Tanzania, 2016-2017)	Cluster-randomized trial	All ages > 6 months. DP plus single low dose PQ; 2 rounds, every 4 weeks, April 2016-June 2016	10,944 (91%-80%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pf Parasitaemia prevalence (Low transmission): 1–3 months • Pf Clinical Malaria Incidence (Low transmission): 4–12, 12–24 months
von Seidlein 2019 ⁴¹ (Viet Nam, 2013-2014)	Cluster-randomized trial	All ages ≥ 6 months. 3 monthly rounds of DP + single low dose PQ (0.25 mg/kg); November 2013, January and February 2014 Transmission season: May to November	1,439 (83% R1; 98% R2; 99% R3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parasitaemia prevalence (Pv and Pf low transmission): 1–3, 4–12 months • Clinical malaria illness incidence (Pv and Pf low transmission): 4–12 months
Myanmar (2013-2014)		All ages ≥ 6 months. 3 monthly rounds of DP + single low dose PQ (0.25 mg/kg); May, June, July 2013 or June, July, August 2013 Transmission season: June to October	1,434 (66% R1; 56% R2; 65% R3)	
Laos (2016-2017)		All ages ≥ 6 months. 3 monthly rounds of DP + single low dose PQ (0.25 mg/kg); April, June, and July 2016 Transmission season: May to October	1006 (81% R1; 80% R2; 82% R3)	
Cambodia (2014-2016)		All ages ≥ 6 months. 3 monthly rounds of DP; July, August, September 2015 Transmission season: May to October	858 (74% R1; 60% R2; 71% R3)	

Eisele 2020A ³² (Zambia, 2014-2017) (Low transmission)	Cluster- randomized trial	MDA to all non-pregnant persons aged >3 months with DP; 4 rounds over 15 months from December 2014-March 2016; Low transmission area	37,694 (79% R1, 63% R2, 76% R3, 66% R4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pf Parasitaemia prevalence: 1–3 months • Pf Parasitemia Incidence: 1–3 months • Pf Clinical Malaria Incidence: 1–3 months
Eisele 2020B ³² (Zambia, 2014-2017) (High transmission)	Cluster- randomized trial	MDA to all non-pregnant persons aged >3 months; DP; 4 rounds over 15 months from January 2013 to May 2015; High transmission area	45,442 (79% in R1, 63% in R2, 76% in R3, and 66% in R4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pf Parasitaemia prevalence: 1–3 months • Pf Parasitemia Incidence: 1–3 months • Pf Clinical Malaria Incidence: 1–3 months
McLean 2021 ⁴² (Myanmar, 2014 to 2017)	Cluster- randomized trial	DP plus single low dose PQ (0.25 mg/kg). March-May 2015	8721 (90%-86%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parasitaemia prevalence- Pv & Pf low transmission: 0–1, 1–3, 4–12, 12–24 months
Non-randomized studies				
Simeons 1938 ⁴⁰ (India, 1935)	Uncontrolled before-and- after study	MDA administered to all persons; 1 round atebirin IM 300 mg daily for 2 days and plasmochin simplex (8- aminoquinoline) 60 mg daily for three days; May to June 1935	5650 (100%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pv Clinical malaria incidence 0–1, 1–3, 4–12 months
Jones 1958 ³⁴ (Kenya, 1952- 1953)	Uncontrolled before-and- after study	MDA administered to all persons with pyrimethamine 100 mg once; three rounds in September 1952, March 1953 and September 1953.	3721 (Coverage not specified)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pv Parasitaemia prevalence: 1–3 months (NOTE: Did not meet inclusion criteria for Pf, thus only Pv data included)
Gabalton 1959 ³³ (Venezuela, 1956-1957)	Uncontrolled before-and- after study	MDA to all persons aged > 1 month with pyrimethamine 50 mg per week for 24 weeks from July 1957 to December 1957	111,995 (Coverage not specified)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pv Parasitaemia prevalence: 4–12 months • Pv Parasitemia incidence 0–1, 1–3, 4–12 months
Schneider 1961 ³⁸ (Burkina Faso, 1960–1961)	Non- randomized controlled study	Intervention group 1: MDA administered to all persons with a combination of 600 mg base CQ or AQ and 15 mg base PQ every 14 days in June to December 1960 for 15 rounds.	6035 (90% in intervention 1, 2500 people; coverage not	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pf Parasitaemia prevalence (high transmission): 1–3 months

		Intervention group 2: MDA administered to all persons with 600 mg base AQ and 15 mg base PQ every 14 days in June to December 1960 for 8 rounds.	specified in intervention arm 2, 3535 people)	
Comer 1971 ³¹ (Panama, 1965-1968)	Uncontrolled before-and-after study	MDA to all persons aged > 6 months. Pyrimethamine 50 mg (cycles 1-25)/ 75 mg (cycles 26-49) and PQ 40 mg given every 2 weeks for 2 years from August 1966 to April 1968.	1548 - 1908 (61-87%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adverse events
Paik 1974A ³⁷ (Solomon Islands, 1972)	Uncontrolled before-and-after study	MDA administered to all persons with CQ 600 mg + pyrimethamine 50 mg monthly for four months from July to October 1972.	Not specified (90%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pv Parasitaemia prevalence: 0–1, 1–3, 4–12 months
Paik 1974B ³⁷ (Solomon Islands, 1972-73)	Uncontrolled before-and-after study	MDA administered to all persons; 3 rounds CQ mg and PQ 75 mg every three months from October 1972 to March 1973.	1200 (90%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pv Parasitemia incidence 0–1, 1–3 months
Molineaux 1980 ³⁵ (Nigeria, 1970–1976)	Controlled before-and-after study	MDA to all persons: <i>Low frequency:</i> Sulfalene-pyrimethamine as a single dose; 9 rounds, every 10 weeks, 18 months April 1972-October 1973 <i>High frequency:</i> Sulfalene-pyrimethamine as a single dose; 23 rounds, every 2 weeks May-Oct 1972 and 1973 and every 10 weeks Dec 1972, March 1973, October-November 1973	14,129 (73%-92%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pf Parasitaemia prevalence- high transmission, 4–12, 12–24 months
Cáceres Garcia 2008 ³⁰ (Venezuela, 2002-2007)	Uncontrolled before-and-after study	MDA to all non-pregnant persons aged >6 months with CQ 25 mg/kg administered over 3 days and PQ 3.5 mg/kg (radical cure) in November 2002.	25,722 (77% (of census)/ 86% (of included)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pv clinical malaria incidence 0–1, 1–3 months
Sterk 2021 ⁴³ (Democratic Republic of Congo, 2020-2021)	Non-randomized controlled before and after study	All people ages > 2 months. 3 rounds (2 rounds ASAQ and 1 round pyronaridine-artesunate; ASAQ1 from 24 September to 13 October 2020, ASAQ2 from 9 to 27 November 2020, pyronaridine-artesunate from 17 December 2020 to 8 January 2021).	13,645 (90.5%)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mortality Adverse events

Figure 2. Classification of included studies

Interventions

P. falciparum

Cluster-randomized controlled trials

One study used dihydroartemisinin piperazine (DP) alone (Eisele_2020), while three used DP plus single low dose primaquine (PQ; 0.25mg/kg; McLean_2021, von Seidlein_2019), and two used sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine + artesunate (SP+AS), either alone (von Seidlein_2003) or in combination with single low dose of PQ (0.75mg/kg; Shekalaghe_2011).

Non-randomized trials

One study provided 9 rounds of sulfalene-pyrimethamine every 10 weeks for a period of 18 months (Molineaux_1980) and one study provided either CQ or AQ in combination with PQ (15mg base; low dose) every 14 days for either 8 or 15 rounds (Schneider_1961). One study (Sterk 2020) provided 3 monthly rounds of MDA-2 rounds of ASAQ followed by one round of Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and artesunate (Pyramax).

P. vivax

Randomized controlled trials

Both used DP plus single low dose PQ (0.25mg/kg) (McLean_2021, von Seidlein_2019); McLean_2021 provided a single round while von Seidlein_2019 provided 3 monthly rounds.

Non-randomized trials

Two trials used CQ+PQ: 1 round (Caceres-Garcia_2008; CQ 25 mg/kg and PQ 3.5 mg/kg) and four monthly rounds (Paik_1974B: CQ 1500 mg and PQ 75 mg), one used pyrimethamine plus PQ every 2 weeks for 2 years (Comer_1971), two used pyrimethamine alone: weekly for 24 weeks (Gabaldon_1959) and every 6 months for 3

rounds (Jones_1958)), one used CQ 600 mg and pyrimethamine 50 mg monthly for four months (Paik 1974A), and one used a single round of atebine plus plasmochin (Simeons_1938).

For this review, we defined a primaquine dose of 210 mg within 8 weeks as radical cure, equivalent to 3.5 mg/kg within 8 weeks. Based on this definition, only the trial by Caceres-Garcia_2008 provided sufficient primaquine for radical cure. The minimum effective daily dose of plasmochin against *P. vivax* is 90mg daily for 14 days;⁴⁴ Simeons_1938 provided a total dose of only 60 mg. It should be noted that although the regimen used by Comer_1971 did not meet the strict definition of radical cure dosing, because they did not give 210mg over 8 weeks, the total dose exceeded 210 mg. Furthermore, the investigators intended to give primaquine for radical cure and it was effective in preventing new *P. vivax* cases.

Outcomes

We assessed the effects of MDA on incidence of confirmed malaria illness (clinical malaria), parasitemia prevalence, and parasitemia incidence at 0–1 months, 1–3 months, 4–12 months, and 12–24 months post MDA. Specific time points for each study are noted in Table 1. In addition, where available, we recorded data on anemia, hospital admissions (all-cause and malaria specific), cases or incidence of severe malaria, blood transfusions, all-cause mortality, and adverse events.

Contextual factors

Of 47 studies considered, 31 included contextual factors relevant to participants' values and preferences, drivers of MDA acceptability, health equity concerns, financial and economic aspects of the intervention, and barriers related to feasibility.

Modelling studies

Of 18 studies considered, 13 included relevant operational outcomes.

Resistance marker data

Two studies included data on resistance markers pre and post MDA.

Risk of bias in included studies

Assessments for risk of bias for each study are summarized by outcome in Figure 2 and Figure 3 with support for judgements provided in the Characteristics of included studies tables (Appendix 1).

Randomized studies

Randomized studies were assessed with the ROB2 tool from Cochrane using the following domains:

- **Domain 1a. Risk of bias arising from randomization:** All cRCTs except Morris 2018, and von Seidlein 2019 were low risk of bias. Morris 2018 was rated unclear as baseline malaria prevalence was higher in control (2.5%) compared to intervention (0.8%) sites; the von Seidlein 2019 sites in Cambodia, Laos, and Myanmar each only included 4 total clusters, and had different baseline malaria risk, and were also rated some concerns.
- **Domain 1b. Risk of bias from timing of identification/ recruitment:** all cRCTs were rated low risk of bias.
- **Domain 2. Risk of bias due to deviations from intended intervention:** all cRCTs were rated low risk of bias except for McLean 2021, which was rated as some concern for risk of bias as there was contact tracing of all identified cases in the 50km around the case in the MDA arm only, and von Seidlein 2019 Viet Nam, which was rated as some concern due to the fact that intervention and control clusters were

pair-matched by geographical proximity, which likely led to a high risk of contamination due to population movement.

- **Domain 3. Missing outcome data: Parasitemia prevalence:** McLean 2021 was rated as high risk of bias due to the fact that the population evaluated at different time points should have remained consistent, and did not. Parasitemia incidence: von Seidlein 2003 was rated as high risk of bias for parasitemia incidence as malaria cases were defined as a temperature $\geq 37.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and parasitaemia $> 5000/\mu\text{L}$, which may have precluded non-febrile or lower density infections and resulted in an underestimate of parasitaemia incidence.
- **Domain 4. Risk of bias in measurement of the outcome:** All cRCTs were rated low risk of bias.
- **Domain 5. Risk of bias in selection of reported result:** All cRCTs were rated low risk of bias.

Non-randomized studies

Non-randomized studies were assessed with the following domains:

- **Domain 1. Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria** (inclusion of control population): Comer 1971 was rated high risk of bias due to low coverage (66%) while Gabaldon 1959, Jones 1958, and Schneider 1961 were rated unclear risk of bias.
- **Domain 1b. Not applicable.**
- **Domain 2. Flawed measurement of exposure:** Gabaldon 1959 was rated unclear risk of bias because they did not record actual numbers of treatments.
- **Domain 3. Incomplete follow-up:** *Parasitemia incidence:* Paik was rated unclear risk of bias due to insufficient information to permit judgement. *Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness:* Caceres-Garcia and Simeons were rated high risk of bias due to the fact that they used passive surveillance to identify cases, and participants were aware of the intervention which may have affected care seeking.
- **Domain 4. Flawed measurement of outcome:** *Parasitemia incidence:* Paik B was rated high risk of bias because they used passive surveillance and it was unclear how care-seeking or testing was affected by knowledge of having received MDA. *Incidence of clinical malaria:* Caceres-Garcia and Simeons were high risk of bias because they used passive surveillance and it was unclear how care-seeking or testing was affected by knowledge of having received MDA.
- **Domain 5. Failure to adequately control for confounding:** Non-randomized controlled trials were rated as unclear while uncontrolled trials were rated as high risk of bias.

Figure 3. Risk of bias summary: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for each included study by malaria outcomes

	Domain 1 a.	Domain 1 b.	Domain 2.	Domain 3: Parasitemia Prevalence	Domain 3: Parasitemia Incidence	Domain 3: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Domain 4: Parasitemia Incidence	Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Domain 5.	OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	OVERALL: Parasitemia Incidence	OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness
Cáceres Garcia 2008 Venezuela	+		+			-			-	-			-
Comer 1971 Panama	-		+	+			+			-	-		
Eisele 2020 Zambia A	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	?	+	+	+	?
Eisele 2020 Zambia B	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	?	+	+	+	?
Gabalton 1959 Venezuela	?		?		+			+		-		-	
Jones 1954 Kenya	?		+	+			+			-	-		
McLean 2021 Myanmar	+	+	?	-			+			+	-		
Molineaux 1980 Nigeria	+		+	+			+			?	?		
Morris 2018 Zanzibar	?	+	+	+		+	+		?	+	?		?
Paik 1974 Solomon Islands A	+		+	?	?		+	+		-	-	-	
Paik 1974 Solomon Islands B	+		+		?			-		-		-	
Schneider 1961 Burkina Faso	?		+	+			+			?	?		
Shekalaghe 2011 Tanzania	+	+	+	+		+	+		+	+	+		+
Simeons 1938 India	+		+			-			-	-			-
von Seidlein 2003 Gambia	+	+	+	+	-		+	+		+	+	-	
von Seidlein 2019 Cambodia	?	+	+	+		+	+		?	+	?		?
von Seidlein 2019 Laos	?	+	+	+			+			+	?		
von Seidlein 2019 Myanmar	?	+	+	+		+	+		?	+	?		?
von Seidlein 2019 Viet Nam	+	+	?	+			+			+	?		

Randomized studies: ROB2 tool: Domain 1a. Risk of bias arising from randomization; Domain 1b. Risk of bias from timing of identification/ recruitment; Domain 2. Risk of bias due to deviations from intended intervention; Domain 3. Missing outcome data; Domain 4. Risk of bias in measurement of the outcome; Domain 5. Risk of bias in selection of reported result. **Non-randomized studies:** Domain 1. Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria (inclusion of control population); Domain 1b. Not applicable; Domain 2. Flawed measurement of exposure; Domain 3. Incomplete follow-up; Domain 4. Flawed measurement of outcome (outcome-level); Domain 5. Failure to adequately control for confounding (**NOTE:** Comer provided data on parasitemia during MDA, and thus contributed to AE outcomes only)

Figure 4. Risk of bias summary: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for mortality, anemia, adverse events/ serious adverse events, and resistance marker detection

Study	Risk of bias domains							Overall
	D1	D1b	D2	D3	D4	D5		
Eisele 2020 ZambiaA (AE)	+	+	+	⊗	-	+	⊗	
Eisele 2020 ZambiaB (AE)	+	+	+	⊗	-	+	⊗	
Morris 2018 Zanzibar (AE)	+	+	+	⊗	-	+	⊗	
McLean 2021 Myanmar (AE)	+	+	+	⊗	+	+	⊗	
McLean 2021 Myanmar (Resistance)	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	
Shekalaghe 2011 TZA (AE)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
Shekalaghe 2011 TZA (Anemia)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
von Seidlein 2003 Gambia (AE)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
von Seidlein 2019 SE Asia (AE)	+	+	+	⊗	+	+	⊗	
von Seidlein 2019 SE Asia (Resistance)	+	+	+	⊗	+	+	⊗	
MSF 2021 DRC (AE)*	+	○	-	+	-	+	-	
MSF 2021 DRC (mortality)*	+	○	-	+	-	+	-	

Domains:
D1 : Bias arising from the randomization process.
D1b: Bias arising from the timing of identification and recruitment of individual participants in relation to timing of randomization.
D2 : Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.
D3 : Bias due to missing outcome data.
D4 : Bias in measurement of the outcome.
D5 : Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement
⊗ High
- Some concerns
+ Low
○ Not applicable

D3 was rated as high risk of bias when the outcome was measured only in those who received MDA

Figure 5. Risk of bias graph: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies (malaria outcomes)

Randomized studies: ROB2 tool: Domain 1a. Risk of bias arising from randomization; Domain 1b. Risk of bias from timing of identification/ recruitment; Domain 2. Risk of bias due to deviations from intended intervention; Domain 3. Missing outcome data; Domain 4. Risk of bias in measurement of the outcome; Domain 5. Risk of bias in selection of reported result. **Non-randomized studies:** Domain 1. Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria (inclusion of control population); Domain 1b. Not applicable; Domain 2. Flawed measurement of exposure; Domain 3. Incomplete follow-up; Domain 4. Flawed measurement of outcome (outcome-level); Domain 5. Failure to adequately control for confounding.

Effects of interventions

P. falciparum

Due to substantial heterogeneity by transmission strata in parasitemia prevalence at the critical 1–3 month timepoint, all analyses assessing the effects of MDA on *P. falciparum* were stratified by low-very low vs. moderate high transmission.

P. falciparum: Incidence of clinical malaria post MDA

P. falciparum: Incidence of clinical malaria post MDA, moderate high transmission areas

One cRCT (Eisele 2020) provided data on incidence of clinical malaria 1–3 months post-MDA in moderate high settings. Low certainty evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may not reduce clinical malaria incidence in areas with moderate/high transmission 1–3 months post MDA. There are no data on incidence of clinical malaria 0–1 months, 4–12 months, or 12–24 months post-MDA.

Figure 6. Incidence of Clinical Pf Malaria, cRCTs, moderate to high transmission

Footnotes

(1) All ages; January-May 2015 and 2016; denominator assumed to be average of 2015 and 2016 mid-year HFCA population

P. falciparum: Incidence of clinical malaria post MDA, low/ very low transmission areas

There are no data on incidence of clinical malaria 0–1 months post-MDA. Two cRCTs (Eisele 2020 and Morris 2018) provided data on incidence of clinical malaria 1–3 months post-MDA in low-very low transmission settings (RR 0.58, 95% CI 0.12-2.73; Figure 6). Low certainty evidence suggests that MDA may not reduce clinical malaria incidence in areas with low/very low transmission 1–3 months post MDA.

Two cRCTs (von Seidlein 2019, 2 sites: Myanmar & Cambodia) provided data on incidence of clinical malaria 4–12 months post-MDA in low-very low transmission settings; MDA resulted in a non-significant reduction (rate ratio 0.47, 95% CI 0.21-1.03) (Figure 6). MDA may reduce clinical malaria incidence in areas of low/very low transmission 4–12 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

One cRCT (Morris 2018) provided data on incidence of clinical malaria 12–24 months post-MDA in low-very low transmission settings; MDA resulted in no difference in clinical malaria incidence at 12–24 months post MDA (rate ratio 0.77, 95% CI 0.20-3.03) (Figure 6). MDA probably results in no difference in clinical malaria incidence in areas with low/very low transmission 12–24 months post MDA.

Figure 7. Incidence of Clinical Pf Malaria, cRCTs, Low/ Very Low Transmission

Footnotes

- (1) All ages; January-May 2015 and 2016; denominator assumed to be average of 2015 and 2016 mid-year HFCA population
- (2) All ages; May-August 2016
- (3) All ages; May 2013 to January 2014; *Plasmodium falciparum* or mixed infections
- (4) All ages; July 2015 - June 2016; *Plasmodium falciparum* or mixed infections
- (5) All ages; May 2016 - August 2017

When data from the low/ very low and moderate high transmission strata are combined, there is no heterogeneity ($I^2 = 0\%$), and the overall rate ratio is 0.52 (95% CI 0.14-1.91), highlighting that MDA may not reduce the incidence of *Pf* clinical malaria 1–3 months post MDA regardless of transmission strata (Figure 7).

Figure 8. Incidence of Clinical *Pf* Malaria, 1–3 Months post MDA, cRCTs, All transmission strata

Footnotes

(1) All ages; January-May 2015 and 2016; denominator assumed to be average of 2015 and 2016 mid-year HFCA population

(2) All ages; May-August 2016

(3) All ages; January-May 2015 and 2016; denominator assumed to be average of 2015 and 2016 mid-year HFCA population

P. falciparum prevalence

An overall analysis of Pf prevalence at 1–3 months post MDA had a high degree of heterogeneity ($I^2 = 90\%$; $p = 0.002$) that could be explained in part by transmission intensity (**Figure 9**), thus, all Pf analyses were stratified by transmission strata. Though it should be noted that by the 4–12 month time point, heterogeneity was very low across transmission strata ($I^2 = 41\%$; non-significant test for sub-group differences, $p = 0.32$).

Figure 9. *P. falciparum*: Parasitemia prevalence 1–3 months post MDA, cRCTs

Test for subgroup differences: $\text{Chi}^2 = 9.97$, $\text{df} = 1$ ($P = 0.002$), $I^2 = 90.0\%$

Footnotes

- (1) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 14 (MDA events), 674 (MDA total), 21 (Control events), 336 (Control total)
- (2) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 1 (MDA events), 552 (MDA total), 24 (Control events), 812 (Control total)
- (3) Children ≤ 5 years; RDT; raw data: 3 (MDA events), 392 (MDA total), 5 (Control events), 365 (Control total)
- (4) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; ICC = 0
- (5) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; ICC = 0
- (6) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 0 (MDA events), 745 (MDA total), 90 (Control events), 722 (Control total)
- (7) All ages; qPCR; raw data: 67 (MDA events), 4896 (MDA total), 53 (Control events), 4905 (Control total)
- (8) Children ≤ 5 years; RDT; raw data: 28 (MDA events), 348 (MDA total), 22 (Control events), 438 (Control total)

P. falciparum: Moderate High Transmission Settings

P. falciparum: Parasitemia prevalence 0–1 months post MDA

There were no data for moderate high transmission settings 0–1 months post MDA.

P. falciparum: Parasitemia prevalence 1–3 months post MDA

One cRCT (Eisele 2020) contributed data at the 1–3 month time point. No significant effect was detected (risk ratio 1.76, 95% CI 0.58-5.36). One non-randomized trial (Schneider 1961) was conducted in areas of moderate to high transmission; this demonstrated a small possible effect of MDA (risk ratio 0.85, 95% CI 0.78-0.93) (**Figure 10**). Overall, the available evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at

approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may result in little to no difference in areas with moderate/high transmission 1–3 months post MDA.

***P. falciparum*: Parasitemia prevalence 4–12 months post MDA**

One cRCT (von Seidlein 2003) contributed parasitemia prevalence data at 4–12 months in an area of moderate-high transmission (**Figure 10**). There was no significant effect 4–12 months post MDA (RR 1.18, 95% CI 0.89, 5.36). There was a single non-randomized trial (Molineaux 1980) which looked at parasitemia prevalence 4–12 months post MDA in an area of moderate-high transmission intensity which suggested that MDA may reduce parasitemia prevalence (RR 0.60, 95% CI 0.55-0.67; **Figure 11**). Overall, there is low certainty evidence that suggests little to no benefit of MDA at 4–12 months in areas of moderate to high transmission.

***P. falciparum*: Parasitemia prevalence 12–24 months post MDA**

There were no cRCTs providing data on Pf parasitemia prevalence 12–24 months post MDA. One non-randomized trial (Molineaux 1980) provided data from a moderate-high transmission setting (RR 0.77, 95% CI 0.70-0.84; **Figure 11**). A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may reduce parasitemia prevalence in areas with moderate high transmission 12–24 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

Figure 10. *P. falciparum*: Parasitemia prevalence, cRCTs, Moderate High Transmission

Footnotes

- (1) Children ≤ 5 years; RDT; raw data: 28 (MDA events), 348 (MDA total), 22 (Control events), 438 (Control total)
- (2) Children < 11 years; microscopy; raw data: 530 (MDA events), 808 (MDA total), 333 (Control events), 606 (Control total)

Figure 11. *P. falciparum*: Parasitemia prevalence, Nonrandomized Trials, Moderate High Transmission

Footnotes

- (1) Molineaux 1980 NGA: MDA (SP every 2 weeks during the wet season and 10 weeks during the dry season) + IRS vs. no intervention
- (2) Molineaux 1980 NGA: MDA (SP every 2 weeks during the wet season and 10 weeks during the dry season) + IRS vs. no intervention

P. falciparum: Low/ Very Low Transmission Settings

Within the first month post-MDA, two cRCTs (McLean 2021 and Shekalaghe 2011) conducted demonstrate an effect of MDA on Pf parasitemia prevalence in low-very low transmission areas (RR 0.12, 95% CI 0.03-0.52; **Figure 12**). The evidence suggests that there is probably a large reduction in parasite prevalence in areas with low/very low transmission 0–1 months post MDA.

P. falciparum: Parasitemia prevalence 1–3 months post MDA

Five studies contributed data at the 1–3 month time point (including four sites from von Seidlein 2019). Overall, the five low transmission studies demonstrated a large effect of MDA at 1–3 months post MDA (Risk ratio 0.25, 95% CI 0.15-0.41; **Figure 12**). Overall, the available evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area probably results in large reduction in parasitemia prevalence in areas with low/very low transmission 1–3 months post MDA.

P. falciparum: Parasitemia prevalence 4–12 months post MDA

Three studies (McLean 2021, Shekalaghe 2011, von Seidlein 2019- four sites) contributed parasitemia prevalence data at 4–12 months in areas of low-very low transmission (**Figure 12**). Overall, there is low certainty evidence that MDA results in little to no difference in parasitemia prevalence in areas with low/very low transmission 4–12 months post MDA.

P. falciparum: Parasitemia prevalence 12–24 months post MDA, cRCTs

One cRCT conducted in a low-very low transmission setting provided data on Pf parasitemia prevalence 12–24 months post MDA (**Figure 12**). A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may reduce parasitemia prevalence in areas with low/very low transmission 12–24 Months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

Figure 12. *P. falciparum*: Parasitemia prevalence, RCTs, Low/ Very low Transmission

Test for subgroup differences: Chi² = 17.88, df = 3 (P = 0.0005), I² = 83.2%

Footnotes

- (1) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 12 (MDA events), 746 (MDA total), 56 (Control events), 485 (Control total)
- (2) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 14 (MDA events), 674 (MDA total), 21 (Control events), 336 (Control total)
- (3) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 1 (MDA events), 552 (MDA total), 24 (Control events), 812 (Control total)
- (4) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; ICC = 0
- (5) Children ≤ 5 years; RDT; raw data: 3 (MDA events), 392 (MDA total), 5 (Control events), 365 (Control total)
- (6) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; ICC = 0
- (7) All ages; qPCR; raw data: 67 (MDA events), 4896 (MDA total), 53 (Control events), 4905 (Control total)
- (8) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 0 (MDA events), 745 (MDA total), 90 (Control events), 722 (Control total)
- (9) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 34 (MDA events), 1012 (MDA total), 33 (Control events), 515 (Control total)
- (10) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; ICC = 0
- (11) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; ICC = 0
- (12) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 6 (MDA events), 808 (MDA total), 80 (Control events), 689 (Control total)
- (13) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 14 (MDA events), 924 (MDA total), 15 (Control events), 466 (Control total)

P. falciparum: Parasitemia incidence

P. falciparum: Parasitemia incidence, moderate high transmission areas

There are no data on parasitemia incidence 0–1 months or 12–24 months post MDA. One cRCT (Eisele 2020) provided data on parasitemia incidence 1–3 months post MDA in moderate-high settings. There is evidence that MDA reduces parasitemia incidence (RR 0.61, 95% CI 0.40-0.92) at 1–3 months post MDA in moderate-high transmission (**Figure 13**).

One cRCT (von Seidlein 2003) provided data on parasitemia incidence 4–12 months post MDA in moderate-high settings, demonstrating no effect of parasite incidence (RR 0.91, 95% CI 0.55-1.50) (**Figure 13**). A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may have no effect on parasite incidence in areas with moderate/high transmission 4–12 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

Figure 13. Pf Parasitemia Incidence, cRCTs, Moderate High Transmission

Footnotes

(1) Persons ≥ 3 months; RDT

(2) Malaria events defined as a temperature ≥ 37.5 °C and parasitaemia > 5000/uL in children < 11 years followed weekly

P. falciparum: Parasitemia incidence, low/ very low transmission areas

There are no data on parasitemia incidence in low/ very low transmission settings 0–1 months post MDA, 4–12 months post MDA, or 12–24 months post MDA. One cRCT (Eisele 2020) provided data on parasitemia incidence 1–3 months post MDA in low/ very low settings (RR = 0.37, 95% CI 0.21-0.66; **Figure 14**). There is evidence that MDA reduces parasitemia incidence at 1–3 months in low/ very low transmission strata.

Figure 14. Pf Parasitemia Incidence, cRCTs, Moderate High Transmission

Overall, there is limited heterogeneity by transmission strata ($I^2 = 48.1\%$, $p=0.17$). There is evidence that MDA reduces parasitemia incidence in both transmission strata, but the relative effect is greater in low-very low transmission strata (RR 0.37, 95% CI 0.21-0.66 in low-very low vs. RR 0.61, 95% CI 0.40-0.92 in moderate-high transmission) (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Pf Parasitemia Incidence 1–3 Months, cRCTs

P. vivax

Pv Incidence of Clinical Malaria

Pv Incidence of Clinical Malaria 0–1 months post MDA

Two observational studies (Caceres Garcia 2008 and Simeons 1938) provided data on confirmed clinical malaria with *P. vivax* at 0–1 months post MDA, demonstrating a reduced risk (rate ratio 0.23, 95% CI 0.21-0.31; **Figure 17**). There were no contributing cRCTs. Very low certainty evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area result in a reduction in confirmed clinical malaria with *P. vivax* at 0–1 months.

Pv Incidence of Clinical Malaria 1–3 months post MDA

Two observational studies (Caceres Garcia 2008 and Simeons 1938) provided data on confirmed clinical malaria with *P. vivax* at 1–3 months post MDA, demonstrating a reduced risk (rate ratio 0.29, 95% CI 0.26-0.31; **Figure 17**).

Footnotes

(1) All ages; July 2015 - June 2016; *Plasmodium vivax*

(2) All ages; May 2013 to January 2014; *Plasmodium vivax*

). There was high heterogeneity ($I^2 = 97\%$, $p < 0.001$), with Caceres-Garcia 2008 (Venezuela; single round CQ+PQ) demonstrating no significant benefit and Simeons 1938 (India; single round of atebirin IM + plasmochin simplex; oiling for larval control) demonstrating a marked reduction. There were no contributing cRCTs. Very low certainty evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may result in a reduction in confirmed clinical malaria with *P. vivax* at 1–3 months.

Pv Incidence of Clinical Malaria 4–12 months post MDA

One cRCT (von Seidlein 2019, two sites- Cambodia and Myanmar) provided data on confirmed clinical malaria with *P. vivax* at 4–12 months post MDA, demonstrating a non-significant increased risk (rate ratio 1.38, 95% CI 0.97-1.95;

Figure 16). There was moderate, but non-significant heterogeneity ($I^2 = 52\%$, $p=0.15$), with no effect in Cambodia and a slight increase in risk in Myanmar. There was one contributing observational study which demonstrated a slight reduction in clinical malaria, with very low certainty evidence (**Figure 17**). A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication, without primaquine radical cure, given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may increase or decrease clinical Pv malaria incidence 4–12 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

Pv Incidence of Clinical Malaria 12–24 months post MDA

One observational study (Simeons 1938) provided data on Pv clinical malaria incidence (**Figure 17**). There were no contributing cRCTs. There was a large reduction in clinical malaria (RR 0.04, 95% CI 0.02-0.07), with low certainty evidence. A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication, without primaquine radical cure, given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may decrease the incidence of Pv clinical malaria 12–24 months post MDA.

Figure 16. Pv Incidence of Clinical Malaria, cRCTs

Test for subgroup differences: Not applicable

Footnotes

(1) All ages; July 2015 - June 2016; *Plasmodium vivax*

(2) All ages; May 2013 to January 2014; *Plasmodium vivax*

Figure 17. Pv Incidence of Clinical Malaria, Nonrandomized trials

Pv Parasitemia Prevalence

Pv Parasitemia Prevalence 0–1 months post MDA

One cRCT (McLean 2021) provided data on *P. vivax* parasitemia prevalence 0–1 months post MDA (DP+PQ), demonstrating reduced parasitemia prevalence (risk ratio 0.18, 95% CI 0.08-0.40) (Figure 17). Data from 1 observational trials (Paik 1974A) provide further support for this conclusion (risk ratio 0.32, 95% CI 0.12-0.87) (Figure 18). There is moderate certainty of evidence that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area results in large reduction in parasitemia prevalence - 0–1 months post MDA.

Pv Parasitemia Prevalence 1–3 Months post MDA

Two cRCTs (McLean 2021 and von Seidlein 2019, 4 sites) provided data on Pv parasitemia prevalence at 1–3 months, demonstrating a reduced risk (risk ratio 0.15, 95% CI 0.10-0.24; Figure 18). In addition, two observational studies provided further support that MDA reduces parasitemia prevalence at 1–3 months (risk ratio 0.18, 95% CI 0.10-0.33) (Figure 20). The evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area probably results in a large reduction in parasitemia prevalence 1–3 months post MDA.

Pv Parasitemia Prevalence 4–12 Months post MDA

Two cRCTs (McLean 2021 and von Seidlein 2019, 4 sites) provided data on Pv parasitemia prevalence at 4–12 months, demonstrating no effect (risk ratio 1.01, 95% CI 0.87-1.18; Figure 18), one observational study (Paik 1974A) provided additional data that MDA reduces parasitemia prevalence at 4–12 months (risk ratio 0.34, 95% CI 0.15-0.78; Figure 19). While four of the five cRCT sites included single low dose primaquine in conjunction with DP (von Seidlein 2019 Cambodia used DP alone), Paik 1974A used 75 mg of primaquine (~1.25 mg/kg) in combination with CQ. The higher dose of primaquine may help explain the greater effect seen. A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication, in absence of radical cure, given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area probably results in little to no difference in parasitemia prevalence in low transmission settings 4–12 months post MDA; evidence from non-randomized trials suggests that there may be a reduction in parasitemia prevalence 4–12 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

Pv Parasitemia Prevalence 12–24 Months post MDA

One cRCT (McLean 2021) provided data on Pv parasitemia prevalence at 12–24 months, demonstrating little to no effect (risk ratio 0.81, 95% CI 0.44-1.48; Figure 18). There were no NRTs contributing data at this time point. Low certainty evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area probably results in little to no difference in parasitemia prevalence in low transmission settings 12–24 months post MDA.

Figure 18. Pv Parasitemia Prevalence, cRCTs

Test for subgroup differences: Chi² = 80.93, df = 3 (P < 0.00001), I² = 96.3%

Footnotes

- (1) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 36 (MDA events), 746 (MDA total), 131 (Control events), 485 (Control total)
- (2) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 82 (MDA events), 674 (MDA total), 54 (Control events), 336 (Control total)
- (3) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 5 (MDA events), 552 (MDA total), 144 (Control events), 812 (Control total)
- (4) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 14 (MDA events), 1061 (MDA total), 68 (Control events), 827 (Control total)
- (5) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 3 (MDA events), 470 (MDA total), 64 (Control events), 696 (Control total)
- (6) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 0 (MDA events), 745 (MDA total), 84 (Control events), 722 (Control total)
- (7) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 154 (MDA events), 1012 (MDA total), 88 (Control events), 515 (Control total)
- (8) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; ICC = 0
- (9) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 24 (MDA events), 512 (MDA total), 71 (Control events), 1090 (Control total)
- (10) All ages ≥ 6 months; uPCR; raw data: 3 (MDA events), 808 (MDA total), 33 (Control events), 689 (Control total)
- (11) Ages 18-55 years; uPCR; raw data: 148 (MDA events), 1029 (MDA total), 87 (Control events), 508 (Control total)

Figure 19. Pv Parasitemia Prevalence, Nonrandomized trials

Test for subgroup differences: Chi² = 1.82, df = 2 (P = 0.40), I² = 0%

Footnotes

(1) Jones 1954 KEN: MDA (Pyr every 6 months for 3 rounds) vs. baseline data

Pv Parasitemia Incidence

There were no cRCTs providing data on Pv parasitemia incidence.

Pv Parasitemia Incidence 0–1 months post MDA

Two observational studies (Gabaldon 1959 and Paik 1974B) provided data on Pv parasitemia incidence at 0–1 months, demonstrating a reduced risk (rate ratio 0.15, 95% CI 0.12-0.19; **Figure 20**). Low certainty evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may result in a large reduction in parasitemia incidence 0–1 months post MDA.

Pv Parasitemia Incidence 1–3 months post MDA

Two observational studies (Gabaldon 1959 and Paik 1974B) provided data on Pv parasitemia incidence at 1–3 months, demonstrating a reduced risk (rate ratio 0.37, 95% CI 0.32-0.43; **Figure 20**). Very low certainty evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may result in a reduction in Parasitemia Incidence 1–3 Months post MDA.

Pv Parasitemia Incidence 4–12 months post MDA

One observational study (Gabaldon 1959) provided data on Pv parasitemia incidence at 4–12 months, demonstrating a reduced risk (rate ratio 0.15, 95% CI 0.07-0.34; **Figure 20**). Very low certainty evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may result in a reduction in parasitemia incidence 4–12 months post MDA.

Pv Parasitemia Incidence 12–24 months post MDA

There are no data on Pv Parasitemia Incidence 12–24 months post MDA.

Figure 20. Pv Parasitemia Incidence, Nonrandomized trials

Anemia

Only two studies provided information on anemia or hemoglobin following MDA. Shekalaghe 2011 assessed the hemolytic effect of SP plus AS plus a single dose of primaquine (PQ; 0.75 mg/kg of body weight) in children aged 1 to 12 years. Children were randomized to receive SP+AS+PQ or placebo; those with a hemoglobin (Hb) level < 8 g/dl were excluded from receiving PQ and received SP+AS. At day 7 following treatment, Hb was significantly reduced among those in the SP+AS+PQ group (n=564) but not in the placebo (n= 116) or SP+AS groups (n=23) (**Figure 21**; SP+AS group not included given the small n, and the non-randomized allocation to SP+AS).

von Seidlein 2003 compared hemoglobin levels among children < 11 years of age five months post MDA with SP+AS versus placebo. In the MDA arm, 44.5% were anemic, while in the placebo arm, 53.3% were anemic (p = 0.22). At baseline, 65.4% of children < 5 years were anemic in the MDA arm, versus 61.2% in the placebo arm. Specific denominators for the MDA and control areas were not available to allow calculation of a risk ratio, however, there was no significant difference in anemia between arms as per the publication.

Figure 21. Difference in hemoglobin following SP+AS+PQ vs placebo

All-Cause Mortality

Only two studies (von Seidlein 2003 and Sterk 2020), both from moderate-high transmission settings, reported mortality data. A total of 3,404 were treated (with either placebo or MDA with SP+AS) in 18 surveillance villages (9 MDA, 9 placebo) by von Seidlein 2003. “In the 9 villages treated with SP+AS, 6 children aged < 11 years died during the 5 months of surveillance. Verbal autopsies suggested that 5 had died of malaria. In the placebo-treated villages, 6 children died during the surveillance period; 3 of these deaths were likely to have been due to malaria (P = 0.64).” Specific denominators for the MDA and control areas were not available to allow calculation of a risk ratio, however, there was no significant difference in deaths between arms as per the publication.

Sterk 2020 collected mortality data among children and adults following MDA with ASAQ for 2 rounds followed by one round of pyronaridine tetraphosphate and artesunate (Pyramax) and reported all-cause mortality in both children under 5 and all ages. A reduction in all-cause mortality was seen in the month post MDA both among children under 5 and all ages, but the effect was no longer present by 1–3 months post-MDA, and, among all ages, there was a higher risk of mortality among MDA recipients during the later time point.

Figure 22. All-Cause Mortality <1 month post-MDA

Figure 23. All-Cause Mortality 1–3 months post-MDA

Adverse events and serious adverse events

Adverse events: *P. falciparum*

Six studies in areas with *P. falciparum* transmission reported adverse event (AE) data (McLean_2021, Morris_2018, Shekalaghe_2011, von Seidlein_2003, von Seidlein_2019, and Eisele_2020; Eisele_2020 reported serious adverse events (SAEs) and AEs arising from both MDA and focal MDA arms together). Among cRCTs, Eisele_2020 and von Seidlein_2019 Cambodia used DP alone, while McLean_2021, Morris_2018, and von Seidlein_2019 (Vietnam, Laos, Myanmar) used DP plus single low dose PQ; two studies used SP+AS, either alone (von Seidlein_2003) or in combination with single low dose PQ (0.75 mg/kg; Shekalaghe_2011).

Only von Seidlein 2019 provided SAE data from both the MDA and control arms (no data were recorded from the control arms in Cambodia and Laos). In the first three months post MDA there were six SAEs in the MDA arm (2 unexplained deaths, 2 life threatening illnesses, and 2 hospitalizations due to pneumonia) and one SAE in the control arm (life threatening illness). It was reported that none of the SAEs were related to the intervention. Within 12 months of the MDA, there were a total of 28 SAEs among 4135 people in MDA villages and 10 among 2596 people in control villages. Thus, there was a non-significant increase in the odds of an SAE (OR 3.61, 95% CI 0.43-30.03 for 0-3 months post MDA and OR 1.47, 95% CI 0.68-3.20 for 4–12 months post MDA; **Figure 24**).

Among the other four studies (Eisele_2020, McLean_2021, Morris_2018, Shekalaghe_2011), there were a total of 12 reported SAEs out of a total of 353,143 doses of MDA, or SAEs at a rate of 0.03 per 1000 doses. Morris_2018 reported no SAEs, Shekalaghe_2011 reported two SAEs- a serious skin reaction and severe anemia, Eisele_2020 reported four SAEs, of which 3 were deemed unrelated to drug ingestion, and McLean_2021 reported 6 SAEs (3 deaths (all deemed unrelated to drug), one stillbirth, one miscarriage, and one episode of severe dehydration secondary to vomiting and diarrhea).

Only von Seidlein 2003 reported numbers of AEs in both MDA and placebo arms. This was derived from active surveillance among a small subset of the total population. A total of 25 of 75 individuals (33%) who took SP + AS remembered one or more complaints within 2 days of taking the drug, as compared to 2 of 15 individuals (13%) who had received placebo (OR 3.25, 95% CI 0.68-15.53; **Figure 25**). Among those who received MDA, complaints included dizziness (13/75; 17%), fever (6/75; 8%), diarrhea (5/75; 7%), vomiting (5/75; 7%) and itching (4/75; 5%).

Among the other four studies which reported AEs in the MDA arm only (Morris_2018, von Seidlein_2019, Eisele_2020, McLean_2021), there were a total of 1734 reported AEs out of a total of 376,807 doses of MDA, or AEs occurring at a rate of 4.6 per 1000 doses. Morris_2018 used both active and passive detection of AEs; 298 individuals reported a total of 414 events out of 2411 doses of DP + single low dose primaquine; the most commonly reported AEs were nausea and vomiting (33.1% of all reports), dizziness, headache, and fatigue (23.5%), and stomach pain and diarrhea (18.9%). von Seidlein_2019 reported that “1,535 of 8,112 (19%) MDA participants recalled 2,577 AEs, of which 911 (35%) were considered related to the antimalarials; 592 (23%) of the 2,577 AEs were dizziness, 199 (8%) nausea, 96 (4%) vomiting, and 39 (2%) itching, and 1,653 (64%) participants reported a range of other minor complaints. There were no cases of severe haemolysis.” Among 336,821 courses of DP, Eisele_2020 reported 687 AEs. The most common AE reported was gastrointestinal disturbances (diarrhea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and nausea) at 48.6%; dizziness 19.8%; headache 16.0%, and general body weakness at 11.4%. McLean_2021 reported 151 AEs out of a total of 10677 doses, corresponding to 3.6% (151 of 4173) of treated people. The majority of these (n=120) were mild and dizziness (n=109) and rash or itching (n=20) were most commonly reported. Only 18 AEs were assessed as probably related to the medication. Most adverse events occurred in the first treatment round (n=84), with fewer in round 2 (n=48) and round 3 (n=19).

Among one placebo controlled cRCT (Shekalaghe_2011), tolerability (vomiting following MDA with SP+AS with or without PQ) was not significantly different in the intervention vs placebo arm (OR 0.54, 95% CI 0.19- 1.54; **Figure 26**).

Adverse events: P. vivax

Three studies reported adverse event data from areas with *P. vivax* transmission (Comer_1971, McLean_2021, and von Seidlein_2019). Two used DP plus single low dose PQ (McLean_2021, von Seidlein_2019 (Myanmar, Vietnam, Laos; Cambodia used DP alone); Comer_1971 used pyrimethamine plus PQ 40 mg. Both McLean_2021 and von Seidlein_2019 reported SAEs; von Seidlein_2019 determined these to be unrelated to the intervention. Overall, among McLean_2021 and von Seidlein_2019, there were 749 AEs and 12 SAEs among 37575 courses of MDA, or 19.9 AEs per 1000 courses and 0.32 SAEs per 1000 courses. Comer_1971 noted “individual complaints of nausea and headache without observing any severe secondary effects” but no exact number was provided; none of those who complained about an AE refused subsequent rounds.

Adverse events summary

Among people who received MDA, MDA may have little to no effect on SAEs/ AEs, but the evidence is very uncertain.

Figure 24. Serious Adverse Events (Pf and Pv)

Figure 25. All Adverse Events, SP+AS vs placebo (Pf)

Figure 26. Tolerability: Vomiting, SP+AS with or without PQ vs Placebo (Pf)

Antimalarial resistance

Both von Seidlein 2019 et al. and McLean 2021 assessed polymorphisms in the *PfKelch13* gene as well as copy number for the *Pfplasmepsin2/3* gene. At baseline, von Seidlein 2019 identified 269 patients with *P. falciparum*, of whom 221 completed at least one round of MDA and had parasites sequenced for *PfKelch13* at baseline and 1 month post-MDA. At baseline, 10/221 were positive for *PfKelch13* C580Y and multiple copies of the *Pfplasmepsin2/3* gene (4.5%; *PfPailin* genotype); one-month post MDA, there was only 1 infection out of 14 (7%) remaining *Pf* infections that showed the *PfKelch13* + *Pfplasmepsin2/3* genotype.

At baseline, from among 621 individuals sampled in the MDA arm and 412 in the control arm, McLean et al. identified *PfKelch13* mutations in 28 (54%) of 52 positive *P. falciparum* samples and 27 (64%) of 42 positive *P. falciparum* samples in the MDA arm and control arm, respectively. Thus, at baseline, 5% of individuals in the MDA and 7% in the control arm had parasites harboring a *PfKelch13* mutation (**Figure 27**). At month 3 following MDA, 6/12 (50%) of 747 individuals sampled in the MDA arm, and 31/51 (61%) of 485 sampled individuals harbored parasites with the *PfKelch13* mutation (**Figure 28**). Of the 12 people in the MDA group who had *P. falciparum* infections detected at month 3, eight had not received MDA. At month 21, 7 (64%) and 10 (71%) of samples in the MDA and control arms, respectively, had the *PfKelch13* mutation, and by month 27 this was 14 (70%) and 11 (85%). All individuals with asymptomatic *P. falciparum* (n=57) or *P. vivax* (n=93) infections at baseline who received a third round of MDA were negative on retesting. No samples with multi-copy *pfplasmepsin2-3* were found in the entire study. Thus, McLean et al. concluded that there was no evidence that MDA had selected either artemisinin-resistant or piperaquine-resistant parasites.

Figure 27. Proportion of samples with the *PfKelch13* mutation among all samples*

*Data on actual number of samples collected was only available for the pre-MDA and 3 month post MDA time point, for the 4–12 and 12–24 month time points, we used the total number surveyed as the denominator. Numbers from the 5 and 10 month surveys were combined for the 4–12 month period, and numbers from the 15 and 21 month surveys were combined for the 12–24 month period.

Figure 28. Proportion of samples with the *PfKelch13* mutation among *Pf* positive samples

Other outcomes

None of the studies systematically collected data on hospitalizations, severe malaria, nor blood transfusions, beyond what was reported as severe adverse events.

Contextual factors

While no studies directly assessed values with respect to MDA, all studies that surveyed participants found that respondents valued reducing malaria cases, but that different groups valued different aspects of MDA administration. The studies that assessed financial considerations produced a wide range of costs per patient but suggested that cost-effectiveness may be improved by taking advantage of synergies between programs,

and cost-effectiveness may vary in settings based on transmission intensity. No studies highlighted direct health equity concerns. However, unequal distributions of effects and factors that impact participant acceptability and program feasibility has the potential to present a major concern. Participant acceptability was the most widely surveyed factor, appearing in 11 of the 31 studies. Perceived adverse events were the biggest cause of non-participation. Increasing awareness of the intervention and education about malaria was the biggest improvement to participation and adherence. Involving local authorities was essential, but a range of authority figures, and not a single individual or single type of official needed to be involved. Studies that surveyed feasibility factors found that physical distance and mobility, especially seasonal mobility, were major drivers of non-adherence among populations that were otherwise willing to participate. The taste, size, and number of pills provided also contributed to on-the-spot refusal or non-adherence, especially among children.

Values and Preferences

One study that surveyed participants values found that the most common explanation was the desire to protect one's family or community from future malaria infections⁴⁵ and another found that participants who found the concept of healthy people taking antimalarials to be novel found it favorable when they learned it could eliminate or reduce malaria.^{45,46} Reasons for non-participation or non-adherence differ between those who did not intend to take part (detailed under "Acceptability") and those who were unable to take part (detailed under "Feasibility"). Adult participants expressed preferences for interventions that did not cause adverse events or did not disrupt economic activity.⁴⁵⁻⁵⁴ Policymakers and authority figures based their preferences on perceived effectiveness of MDA. One noted that policymakers were unsupportive since they felt that MDA was not sufficiently supported by scientific evidence, while another found that MDA was widely supported by policymakers because they hoped it would increase the impact of vector control interventions.^{55,56} The conflicting values between participants and policymakers was noted in one study in which community members stated a preference for MDA during the dry season since it might impact farming in the wet season, whereas scientific and policy figures favored MDA during the wet season since farmers were more likely to travel away from home during the dry season.⁴⁹ Children's preferences were more difficult to document as they were enrolled by parents, but two studies noted that children's preferences were based on medication taste and size.^{34,57}

Acceptability

The major barrier to acceptability was fears of perceived adverse events.^{45-54,58} One study highlighted an interview with a respondent who refused to participate due to the perception that AE's would be worse than malaria.⁵² Two studies found that the concerns about AE's were not only related to health, but were economic concerns as well.^{47,49} In both studies, participants cited the proximity in time between harvest season and MDA administration as a reason why AE's could have an undue economic effect. However, respondents in a different study perceived that cases of malaria were more likely to limit economic activity during harvest season than AE's.⁵⁶ Concerns of economic impact extended to urban populations as well. One study noted that "participating in the campaign requires closing up the shop for nine mornings to come to the healthcare centre" in addition to existing concerns about the lack of personal benefit.⁵⁰ In contrast, one study noted that participants interpreted mild AE's as evidence of the intervention drug's effectiveness.⁴⁷ In the study by MacLean et al., while overall acceptability was high (~86%), one ethnic cluster had a lower acceptance (75%) due to a preference for tradition medicines over Western medicines.⁴²

Several studies also found that participants were concerned about blood draws for testing, citing fears that the blood would be sold⁴⁹ or that an unhealthy amount of blood was being taken.⁵⁰ In addition to education, providing healthcare helped reduce concerns about AEs in one study,⁴⁶ but another found that the presence of expatriate physicians, an ambulance, and the unfamiliar informed consent process elevated rather than reduced concerns.⁵⁴ Prior experience with MDA reinforced the initial perceptions of MDA. Individuals who had been part of previous MDA trials shared stories among the communities, and if those experiences were poor, community

members had negative impressions of MDA,⁵⁵ and a community that had experienced a prior MDA "with mixed results" were concerned about AE's.⁵⁰ Areas with prior non-MDA interventions that had effectively targeted malaria viewed MDA for malaria more positively,⁵⁹ and one study found that reported acceptability of MDA increased from 62% before MDA to 98% after, although the proportion of respondents who answered that MDA could cause side effects decreased from 30% to 20% in the same timeframe.⁴⁵

Common themes among analyses of drivers of acceptance were sensitization or education about the intervention, support from a range of local authority figures, and additional health support. Two studies assessed how participants preferred to learn about MDA and both determined that village meetings were the preferred method, with radio or television messaging and direct messages from HCW's following.^{58,60} Adhikari 2017 reported that "Respondents who felt that they have received enough information... were more likely to participate in all rounds of MDA," a theme that was repeated by five others.^{49,50,52,61-63} Participants' education was also reported as a driver linking exposure to health institutions and experience with malaria treatment to increase acceptance of MDA).⁵⁸ However, misinformation, rumors, or previous poor experience with MDA decreased participation, including previous non-malaria MDA efforts.^{47,55} Multiple studies noted that including a range of authority figures, both official and non-official, increased acceptance.^{50,52,59} This included figures from different domains (e.g., governmental figures, religious leaders, and health authorities) as well as ensuring that authority figures did not exclude groups. Ensuring support of armed groups was sometimes necessary, as was ensuring that conflicting groups did not perceive MDA as favoring one side over another.⁵⁹ Three studies noted that AE's caused greater demand for local healthcare.^{46,53,54} Two of those provided free healthcare as part of the intervention noted that this drove engagement and was cited as a reason to participate.^{46,58} One study found that lack of engagement with local healthcare providers limited adherence due to conflicting messages about MDA efficacy.⁵¹

Efforts to reduce the perception of the intervention staff as outsiders were also necessary in some settings. One study noted that areas that had experienced prolonged violence were more likely to demand support from local figures.⁶⁴ Several studies noted accidental cultural conflicts, such as suspicion of a culturally inappropriate informed consent process, or the inadvertent exclusion of certain groups of women through the requirement of pregnancy testing. In a study in Myanmar, "a small group of villagers said they would refuse to participate should any of the staff be Muslim," reflecting national tensions.⁵⁹

Health Equity, Equality, and Non-Discrimination

As noted in the section above, links between education about malaria and MDA acceptability were common. Two studies noted that malaria knowledge was linked to access to formal education which varied within their population, potentially biasing the effects of the intervention.^{50,59} Literacy, formal education, and mobility were found to be linked to MDA participation as well.⁶⁵ Occupation and ethnic minority status were found to be linked in some studies, but not linked in others.^{62,65} Only one study raised concerns about gender-based disparities, noting that women were at higher risk of influence from authority figures who did not favor MDA, and the same study noted that some women avoided participation due to concerns about stigma from study-associated pregnancy testing.⁴⁷ One study noted that ethnic minorities were potentially underrepresented due to geographic distribution rather than direct discrimination, and also found that some portions of the population relied on traditional medicine because of affordability more so than any other reason, which led to less familiarity with MDA and thus to lower participation.^{58,59} Exposure to and access to health facilities was positively associated with MDA adherence, and studies that provided access to primary care noted that this improved adherence, especially in populations that had previously lacked access to healthcare.^{46,59,64}

Financial and Economic Factors

The cost of MDA varied from ~\$1.04- \$19.40 per person per round; one study estimated that drugs accounted for 70% of the cost of MDA.⁶⁶ Gabaldon estimated a cost of \$0.11-\$0.21 per person per visit, depending on

distance between houses, (approximately \$1.04-\$1.99 in current \$US).³³ Cirera et al. reported substantially higher costs with an average yearly cost of \$20.7 per targeted person- \$26 for rounds 1 and 2 to \$13 for rounds 3 and 4 per person treated per round.⁶⁷ Galactinova et al. estimated an initial cost of \$2.35 per person treated per round in the first year, dropping to \$2.19 per person per round if implemented annually for five years.⁶⁶ Although the cost per patient treated was lower for MDA than for rapid reporting, reactive case detection, or IRS, the per capita cost of MDA was several times the estimated costs of these other interventions.⁶⁶ This same study also noted that aspects like sensitization may overlap between programs and provide overall improvements in cost-effectiveness.⁶⁶

Yukich et al. estimated that the costs of MDA and focal MDA per person targeted and reached are similar, with a cost of approximately \$4.71 per person reached per round, but that "MDA was superior in all cost-effectiveness measures, including cost per infection averted, cost per case averted, cost per death averted, and cost per disability-adjusted life year averted."⁶⁸ Further, the cost of MDA per person reached was substantially lower (US\$2.90) in an operational setting. It was also noted that "[MDA] showed superior cost-effectiveness in terms of infections averted and appeared to improve when used in relatively higher infection incidence settings."⁶⁸

Feasibility and Health Systems Challenges

Ten studies mentioned difficulties related to absent participants due to distance or to mobility.^{50,52,61,64,69-74} Of these, three studies noted that absenteeism was one of or the major driving force behind non-adherence (and one felt that determining participants' mobility and seasonal locations prior to MDA contributed to the success of the campaign.^{50,61,64,71} Three studies noted problems related to timing other than seasonal weather and agricultural patterns: overlaps with religious events, especially including Ramadan,⁴⁸ unpredictable policy changes at the national level,⁵⁵ and the school year.⁷³ Feasibility concerns related to participant religion were further noted in northern Nigeria by Archibald, who attempted to implement a program in which healthcare workers observed MDA drugs being taken but found that some women were unwilling to remove face coverings in front of strangers.⁵⁷ This was resolved by creating sequestered administration sites staffed by accepted local staff. Additionally, one study commented that survey respondents may have felt that non-adherence due to travel was more socially acceptable than non-adherence due to institutional mistrust, and this may have altered survey results.⁵⁰

Another common pattern among refusal or non-adherence among otherwise willing participants was the taste, size, and number of pills. Four studies noted participant comments complaining that the tablets they were given were too bitter (especially chloroquine), were too large to swallow, or were too numerous to manage.^{34,49,75} Of these, two drew explicit contrasts between large and bitter chloroquine pills and smaller tasteless pyrimethamine pills, both noting that the difference was especially pronounced in children, observing that "children vomit or reject chloroquine and other bitter antimalarial drugs, but will accept the tasteless pyrimethamine readily."^{34,57}

Mathematical Modelling

Timing, number, and/or spacing of rounds and number of years of the intervention

Consistent with trial data, models predicted that a single round of MDA would lead to an initial decrease in infections, but that the duration of effect would be short lived. Application of additional rounds is predicted to substantially improve the impact and duration of effect. Gerardin et al. found that three rounds had a greater impact on parasite prevalence than two. With DP, "At 70% coverage, prevalence one month post-campaign is more than twice as high for a 2-round campaign as a 3-round campaign..."⁷⁶ Walker et al. found that with 90%

coverage at every round, each additional round of MDA increased the proportion of the population in whom preelimination was achievable (74.9% (95% CI 72.3–81.3) with one round of treatment per year, 81.6% (81.3–88.4) after two rounds per year, and 91.4% (85.2–93.2) with three rounds per year).⁷⁷ Brady et al. noted that the effects of three vs two rounds were primarily a result of reaching additional individuals in the third round who had not received treatment in prior rounds.⁷⁸ Silal et al. found that six consecutive two-monthly rounds of MDA substantially decreased infections, and that it took approximately two years to recover to pre-MDA levels following the end of MDA.⁷⁹ Even in areas with low-very low malaria prevalence at baseline, it is estimated that elimination will require multiple rounds per year for a number of years.^{80,81}

Gerardin et al, 2018 noted MDA is most successful when distributed outside the traveling season and during the low transmission season; correct timing with respect to travel was more critical than transmission season.⁸² On the other hand, Silal et al. noted that application in peak season resulted in the greatest decline.⁷⁹ Maude et al. reported that the maximal impact of MDA was noted if the final round of MDA was completed before the nadir; three rounds of ACT MDA over three months was found to be optimal.⁸³ The second round of MDA should be given as soon as possible after the first, i.e. within one to two months of commencing the first round.⁸⁴ No substantial difference was noted between rounds spaced four vs six weeks apart.⁷⁸

Coverage

In order to be effective, coverage of MDA must be high;^{78,83} the most important operational factor determining effect is the proportion of the population who do not receive any treatment in any round.⁷⁸ MDA efficacy is non-linearly related to population coverage; while high coverage is required, the relative increase in efficacy decreases with increasing coverage.⁸⁴ Brady et al. reported that median percentage reduction in PfPR measured by PCR quadrupled from 15% to 61% when effective coverage increased from 30% to 70%.⁷⁸

Maude et al. suggests that if treatment with an ACT were “continued for long enough at high coverage, this alone [would] be sufficient” for elimination.⁸³ However, Pemberton-Ross suggests that MDA is unlikely to achieve elimination in areas with a large population (>1000) or high reproductive number under control (>1.2).⁸⁵ Specifically, this model suggests that “Elimination on operationally relevant timelines (<10 years) at 90% MDA coverage is not expected in populations > 200 unless $R_c \ll 1.1$,”⁸⁵ suggesting that MDA is most efficient as a strategy in areas of very low transmission.

Modelling the combination of strategies that would maximize impact and minimize cost to achieve a national prevalence of 1% in mainland Tanzania, Runge et al. suggests that in MDA coverage of 80% in most areas, in conjunction with other interventions (insecticide treated nets, indoor residual spraying, and improved case management), is needed.⁸⁶

Dosage and dosage schedule

While Gerardin et al. noted a difference in efficacy with DP vs AL, Stuckey et al. found no effect on parasite prevalence of changing drugs from DP to AL.^{76,80} Additionally, Stuckey et al. found no impact of the addition of single low dose PQ or ivermectin to DP.⁸⁰ In contrast, other models by Slater et al. found that addition of ivermectin would result in a greater reduction in RDT-positivity and more sustained period of reduced RDT-positivity than MDA alone,⁸⁷ while Maude et al. found a beneficial effect of adding PQ.⁸³ Robinson et al. noted that addition of an 8-aminoquinoline to a blood stage drug is required for a sustained reduction in *P. vivax* prevalence; tafenoquine is estimated to be more effective than PQ.⁸⁸ As compared to the use of ACTs, resistance to atovaquone proguanil (AP) develops quickly, with predicted loss of AP efficacy as a treatment within four years, and is not recommended for treatment of acute infection nor MDA.⁸⁴

Travel/human mobility

MDA is predicted to be most successful when conducted during seasons when people are not travelling, and least successful when people are travelling, particularly if this occurs at the same time as peak season in high risk areas.⁸²

Discussion

Summary of main results

- ***P. falciparum*, moderate-high transmission settings:** A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area results in little to no effect on clinical malaria illness or parasite prevalence (low certainty evidence) due to *P. falciparum*. MDA reduces all-cause mortality within the first month post MDA, with a larger effect in children under 5 than in all ages, but there is little to no effect by 1–3 months post MDA. There may be some reduction in *P. falciparum* incidence in areas with moderate/high transmission 1–3 months post MDA (moderate certainty evidence). There may be little to no effect of MDA on *P. falciparum* prevalence from 4–12 and 12–24 months (low certainty evidence). We are uncertain whether MDA has any effect on *P. falciparum* incidence or *P. falciparum* clinical malaria incidence from 4–12 or 12–24 months as the certainty of evidence was very low or no studies were identified.
- ***P. falciparum*, low-very low transmission settings** A full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area probably results in large reduction in *P. falciparum* prevalence and in a large reduction in *P. falciparum* incidence (moderate certainty evidence) but may have little to no effect on *P. falciparum* clinical malaria incidence (low certainty evidence) in areas with low/very low transmission 1–3 months post MDA. We are uncertain whether MDA reduces any *P. falciparum* outcome from 4–12 or 12–24 months post-MDA as the certainty of the evidence has been assessed as low or very low and no effect estimate was statistically significant for those time periods. There was no significant impact of MDA on anemia.
- ***P. vivax*:** The evidence suggests that a full therapeutic course of an antimalarial medication given at approximately the same time to adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area may result in a large reduction in *P. vivax* prevalence (low certainty evidence) at 1–3 months post-MDA, but we are uncertain whether MDA reduces *P. vivax* incidence or the incidence of clinical malaria due to *P. vivax* at 1–3 months post-MDA due to very low certainty evidence. We are uncertain whether MDA has any impact on *P. vivax* outcomes from 4–12 and 12–24 months as the certainty of evidence was assessed as very low or the evidence was assessed as low certainty and the effect estimate was not statistically significant.
- **Adverse events:** Adverse events (AEs) after MDA were rare. Among people who received MDA, MDA may have little to no effect on the frequency of serious AEs (SAEs)/ AEs, but the evidence is very uncertain.

- **Drug resistance:** Data on whether MDA increases drug resistance is limited, but based on one study in which drug resistance markers were collected, there does not appear to be an increase in drug resistance markers following MDA.
- **Contextual Factors:**
 - Values and preferences
 - Policymakers and scientists value effective interventions
 - Participants value reducing/eliminating malaria. Adult participants value low rates of adverse events. Children prefer tasteless/easy-to-swallow medications.
 - Acceptability
 - Previous MDAs influenced acceptability
 - Adverse events, economic impact (including time required to administer drugs or AE's during agricultural season), and mistrust of MDA staff lowered acceptability.
 - Sensitization, education, and inclusion of local staff were very important to improve acceptability
 - Health Equity, Equality, and Non-Discrimination
 - No *direct* impacts, but acceptability drivers are unequally distributed; uptake and acceptability tend to be lower in high-risk communities. Ethnic minority communities may suffer from geographic isolation; specific efforts may be needed to reach them.
 - Financial and Economic Considerations
 - Estimated costs per patient varied from USD ~3 to ~20, with better cost-effectiveness in high transmission settings.
 - Feasibility and Challenges
 - Multiple studies noted participant distance or mobility as a major limitation. Mobility was primarily seasonal mobility related to agriculture. Religious mobility was also noted.

Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

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Appendix 1. Characteristics of studies

Characteristics of included studies

Comer 1971 Panama

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 1965-1968</p> <p>Location of study: Panama</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): 17.4% in all ages [Moderate]</p> <p>Transmission season: Rainy season late May to late December</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P. falciparum</i>, <i>P. vivax</i></p> <p>Vector species: Not specified</p> <p>Study design: Uncontrolled before-and-after study</p> <p>Evaluation design: Cross-sectional surveys</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: Ages > 6 months</p> <p>Sample size</p> <p>Intervention group 1 mean (range): 1709 (1548 - 1908)</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention group 1 (Valle del Rio Sambu): MDA to all persons aged > 6 months with pyrimethamine 50 mg (cycles 1-25)/ 75 mg (cycles 26-49) and primaquine 40 mg given every 2 weeks for 2 years from August 1966 to April 1968. Coverage 61-87%. No co-interventions.</p>
Outcomes	<p>Parasitaemia prevalence</p> <p>No adverse event surveillance conducted.</p> <p>Adverse events reported: The acceptance of drugs by the population was excellent. Complaints of nausea and headache were reported, but no other serious side effects were described. None of the people who complained of headaches or nausea refused to take the medicine in subsequent cycles. The number of people who refused to take the medicine was < 1% of the population covered by the programme.</p>
Notes	<p>No post-intervention data</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	High risk	MDA was intended to be given to to all persons aged > 6 months, however, coverage was as low as 61%. There was no comparison group.
Domain 2.	Low risk	Coupon system used to track patients; all persons included in the surveys.

Domain 3.Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Coupon system used to track patients; all persons included in the surveys.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Parasite prevalence was measured in surveys, all persons included.
Domain 5.	High risk	Uncontrolled before-after study.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	High risk	

Cáceres Garcia 2008 Venezuela

Methods	Dates of study: 2002-2007 Location of study: Venezuela Malaria endemicity (incidence): 22/1000 monthly incidence in all ages Transmission season: November Malaria species: <i>P. vivax</i> Vector species: Not specified Study design: Uncontrolled before-and-after study Evaluation design: Passive surveillance
Participants	Age groups included: Ages > 6 months; non-pregnant Sample size Intervention group 1: 25,722
Interventions	Intervention group 1 (6 municipalities in Estado Sucre): MDA to all non-pregnant persons aged >6 months with chloroquine 25 mg/kg administered over 3 days and primaquine 3.5 mg/kg administered over 7 days in November 2002. Coverage 77% (of census)/ 86% (of included). No co-intervention specified.
Outcomes	Clinical malaria incidence No adverse event surveillance conducted No adverse events reported
Notes	MDA done in setting of an outbreak

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	MDA was given to all non-pregnant persons aged >6 months; relatively high coverage (77% of census; 86% of included).
Domain 2.	Low risk	Exposure was defined temporally.

Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	High risk	Passive surveillance of large municipalities after one round of treatment; participants were aware of the intervention which may have affected care seeking
Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	High risk	Passive surveillance system used; participants and health facility personnel were aware of the intervention which may have affected care seeking and testing
Domain 5.	High risk	Uncontrolled before-and-after study
OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	High risk	

Eisele 2020 Zambia A

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2014-2017 Location of study: Zambia</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): Clusters stratified by $\leq 10\%$ and $> 10\%$ parasite prevalence prior to randomisation. This study includes the <u>low</u> transmission strata [Low].</p> <p>Transmission season: January to May</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i></p> <p>Vector species: <i>Anopheles funestus</i> and <i>An. gambiae</i></p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: Widespread resistance to chloroquine and sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine, but no evidence of resistance to artemisinin.</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial (3 arms: MDA, fMDA, and a no fMDA or MDA control; only MDA and control arms included in this review)</p> <p>Statistical power: 80% power ($\alpha = 0.05$) to detect a 50% reduction in parasite prevalence accounting for clustering and 80% power ($\alpha = 0.05$) to detect a 50% reduction in parasite incidence accounting for clustering</p> <p><u>For cRCTs</u></p> <p>Unit of randomisation: Health facility catchment area (HFCA)</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using the study-provided ICC to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Random intercept for HFCA</p> <p>ICC (estimated at the HFCA level in the low transmission strata): 0.06517 (in 2014); 0.01753 (in 2015); 0.01515 (in 2016); 0.04184 (in 2017)</p>
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	<p>Number of clusters randomized: 20</p> <p>Number of clusters analyzed: 20</p> <p>Number of people: 82,866 (low), 184,928 (total)</p> <p>Average cluster size: 9,246</p> <p>Features: Stratified by low vs high (below and above 10%) transmission strata and HFCA population size prior to randomization of clusters</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All ages above 3 months. Children < 3 months and pregnant women in first trimester excluded from MDA with dihydroartemisinin piperazine, but offered appropriate dose of antimalarial treatment in accordance with national policy if found to be RDT positive (note: testing was performed in fMDA and MDA arms, but all eligible persons were treated in the MDA arm, irrespective of RDT result).</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p> <p>Intervention: 37,694</p> <p>Comparison: 45,172</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug/dose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ages ≥ 14 years (> 45 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine (120 mg/960 mg as 3 tablets) given for three days • Ages 8-13 years (25 to 40 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine (80 mg/640 mg as 2 tablets) given for three days • Ages 1-7 years (10 to 23 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine (40 mg/320 mg as 1 tablet) given for three days • Ages 3 months to 1 year (8 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine (20 mg/160 mg as ½ tablet) given for three day <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 4 (December 2014 at the end of the dry season, February-March 2015 at the start of the rainy season, September-October 2015 during dry season, and February-March 2016 at start of the rainy season)</p> <p>Interval: Variable</p> <p>Duration implemented: 15 months</p> <p>Coverage (%): 79% in round 1, 63% in round 2, 76% in round 3, and 66% in round 4</p> <p>Co-interventions: Baseline IRS household coverage in the preceding 12 months was 6.9%; Baseline household LLIN coverage of at least 1 net was 70.3%; Enhanced standard of care was scaled up in the study area, which consisted of RDT or microscopic confirmation of all suspected cases presenting to health facility and treating positives with artemether-lumefantrine and reactive case detection in areas with manageable case counts.</p>

	<p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: No MDA and no placebo</p> <p>Co-interventions: Baseline IRS household coverage in the preceding 12 months was 16.9%; Baseline household LLIN coverage of at least 1 net was 75.3%; Enhanced standard of care was scaled up in the study area, which consisted of RDT or microscopic confirmation of all suspected cases presenting to health facility and treating positives with artemether-lumefantrine and reactive case detection in areas with manageable case counts.</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys of <i>P falciparum</i> prevalence by RDT in children ≥ 3 months and < 6 years</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (April-May 2014), During MDA (April-May 2015), and Post-MDA 1–3 months (April-May 2016)</p> <p>Sample size (range): 372-545 (intervention); 361-453 (comparison)</p> <p><u>Parasitaemia incidence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Prospective cohort of persons ≥ 3 months of age to capture <i>P falciparum</i> incidence by RDT</p> <p>Time points: Followed through 2 months post-MDA (January 2015 - May 2016)</p> <p>Sample size: 260 (intervention); 271 (comparison)</p> <p><u>Clinical malaria illness incidence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Passive surveillance as measured by outpatient department clinical malaria cases (by microscopy or RDT) reported through routine health management information systems data</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (January-May 2013 combined with January-May 2014) and Post-MDA 1–3 months (January 2015 -May 2016)</p> <p><u>Adverse effects (AEs)</u> (reported in both MDA and fMDA arms)</p> <p>A total of 687 AEs (0.13% of participants and 0.24% of treatments) were reported and four were serious AEs; of these, three were deemed unrelated. The most common AEs reported were gastrointestinal symptoms (diarrhea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and nausea) at 48.6%; dizziness 19.8%; headache 16.0%, and general body weakness at 11.4%.</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT02329301</p> <p>Outcomes stratified by low and high transmission strata as specified <i>a priori</i> by study design (defined as above and below 10% parasite prevalence)</p>

	<p>Two out of ten low transmission strata clusters received two additional rounds of programmatic MDA (for a total of six rounds) at 10 and 12 months following the fourth round of trial MDA, however no outcomes were analyzed following the first round of programmatic MDA.</p> <p><u>Abbreviations:</u></p> <p>ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, fMDA = focal mass drug administration, IRS = indoor residual spraying, LLIN = long-lasting insecticide-treated bednet, MDA = mass drug administration, RDT = rapid diagnostic test</p>
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Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	Following stratification by transmission setting and health facility catchment area population size, clusters were randomly allocated to study arms using random allocation rule.
Domain 1b.	Low risk	Following stratification by transmission setting and health facility catchment area population size, clusters were randomly allocated to study arms using random allocation rule. Allocation was conducted by an institution.
Domain 2.	Low risk	No significant deviations from protocol
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Simple random sample of children at baseline and follow-up.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	"No statistically significant differences in primary outcomes or covariates between individuals" included in analysis and those lost to follow-up
Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	Based on routine data from health management information system with established reporting from January 2011 onwards.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Simple random sample of children at baseline and follow-up.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	Prospective cohort of persons 3 months of age and over to capture <i>P falciparum</i> incidence by RDT. While less sensitive than molecular testing, would not expect differential measurement by arms

Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Based on routine data from health management information system with established reporting from January 2011 onwards. Participants were not blinded to allocation, which may have impacted careseeking.
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-stated outcomes of interest were reported.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	
OVERALL: Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	
OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Participants were not blinded to allocation, which may have impacted careseeking.

Eisele 2020 Zambia B

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2014 to 2017</p> <p>Location of study: Zambia</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): Clusters stratified by $\leq 10\%$ and $> 10\%$ parasite prevalence prior to randomization. This study includes the high transmission strata [High].</p> <p>Transmission season: January to May</p> <p>Malaria species: Plasmodium falciparum</p> <p>Vector species: An funestus and An gambiae</p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: Widespread resistance to chloroquine and sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine, but no evidence of resistance to artemisinin.</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial (3 arms: MDA, fMDA, and a no fMDA or MDA control; only MDA and control arms included in this review)</p> <p>Statistical power: 80% power ($\alpha = 0.05$) to detect a 50% reduction in parasite prevalence accounting for clustering, and 80% power ($\alpha = 0.05$) to detect a 50% reduction in parasite incidence accounting for clustering</p> <p>For cRCTs</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Health facility catchment area (HFCA)</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using the study-provided ICC to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Random intercept for HFCA</p> <p>ICC (estimated at the HFCA level for the high transmission strata): 0.16142 (in 2014); 0.11301 (in 2015); 0.08066 (in 2016); 0.13479 (in 2017)</p> <p>Number of clusters randomized: 20</p> <p>Number of clusters analysed: 20</p> <p>Number of people: 102,062 (high), 184,928 (total)</p> <p>Average cluster size: 9246</p> <p>Features: Stratified by low vs high (below and above 10%) transmission strata and HFCA</p>
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	<p>population size prior to randomization of clusters</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All ages above 3 months. Children < 3 months and pregnant women in first trimester excluded from MDA with dihydroartemisinin piperazine, but offered appropriate dose of antimalarial treatment in accordance with national policy if found to be RDT positive (note: testing was performed in fMDA and MDA arms, but all eligible persons were treated in the MDA arm, irrespective of RDT result). Population targeted Intervention: 45,442 Comparison: 56,620</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention: Drug/dose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ages M 14 years (> 45 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine (120 mg/960 mg as 3 tablets) given for three days • Ages 8-13 years (25 to 40 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine (80 mg/640 mg as 2 tablets) given for three days • Ages 1-7 years (10 to 23 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine (40 mg/320 mg as 1 tablet) given for three days • Ages 3 months to 1 year (8 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine (20 mg/160 mg as ½ tablet) given for three days <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 4 (December 2014 at the end of the dry season, February to March 2015 at the start of the rainy season, September to October 2015 during dry season, and February to March 2016 at start of the rainy season) Interval: Variable Duration implemented: 15 months Coverage (%): 79% in round 1, 63% in round 2, 76% in round 3, and 66% in round 4 Co-interventions: Baseline IRS household coverage in the preceding 12 months was 6.9%; Baseline household LLIN coverage of at least 1 net was 70.3%; Enhanced standard of care was scaled up in the study area, which consisted of RDT or microscopic confirmation of all suspected cases presenting to health facility and treating positives with artemether-lumefantrine and reactive case detection in areas with manageable case counts. Comparison: Type: No MDA and no placebo Co-interventions: Baseline IRS household coverage in the preceding 12 months was 16.9%; Baseline household LLIN coverage of at least 1 net was 75.3%; Enhanced standard of care was scaled up in the study area, which consisted of RDT or microscopic confirmation of all suspected cases presenting to health facility and treating positives with artemether-lumefantrine and reactive case detection in areas with manageable case counts.</p>

<p>Outcomes</p>	<p>Parasitaemia prevalence Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys of P falciparum prevalence by RDT in children M 3 months and < 6 years Time points: Pre-MDA (April to May 2014), During MDA (April to May 2015), and Post-MDA 1 to 3 months (April to May 2016) Sample size (range): 348 to 490 (intervention); 332 to 505 (comparison)</p> <p>Parasitaemia incidence Measurement: Prospective cohort of persons M 3 months of age to capture P falciparum incidence by RDT Time points: Followed through 2 months post-MDA (January 2015 to May 2016) Sample size: 339 (intervention); 337 (comparison)</p> <p>Clinical malaria illness incidence Measurement: Passive surveillance as measured by outpatient department clinical malaria cases (by microscopy or RDT) reported through routine health management information systems data Time points: Pre-MDA (January to May 2013 combined with January to May 2014) and Post-MDA 1 to 3 months (January to May 2015) Adverse effects (AEs) (reported in both MDA and fMDA arms)</p> <p>A total of 687 AEs (0.13% of participants and 0.24% of treatments) were reported and four were serious AEs; of these, three were deemed unrelated. The most common AEs reported were gastrointestinal symptoms (diarrhea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and nausea) at 48.6%; dizziness 19.8%; headache 16.0%, and general body weakness at 11.4%.</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT02329301 Outcomes stratified by low and high transmission strata as specified a priori by study design (defined as above and below 10% parasite prevalence) Abbreviations: ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, fMDA = focal mass drug administration, IRS = indoor residual spraying, LLIN = long-lasting insecticide-treated bed net, MDA = mass drug administration, RDT = rapid diagnostic test</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	Following stratification by transmission setting and health facility catchment area population size, clusters were randomly allocated to study arms using random allocation rule.
Domain 1b.	Low risk	Recruitment occurred after randomization, but no apparent deviations occurred as a result of trial context. Households within a 3 km buffer around HFCA borders were excluded from the sampling frame for parasite prevalence and incidence, reducing risk of contamination.

Domain 2.	Low risk	
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Simple random sample of children at baseline and follow-up.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	"No statistically significant differences in primary outcomes or covariates between individuals" included in analysis and those lost to follow-up
Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	Based on routine data from health management information system with established reporting from January 2011 onwards.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Simple random sample of children at baseline and follow-up
Domain 4: Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	Prospective cohort of persons 3 months of age and over to capture <i>P falciparum</i> incidence by RDT. While less sensitive than molecular testing, would not expect differential measurement by arms
Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Based on routine data from health management information system with established reporting from January 2011 onwards. Participants were not blinded to allocation, which may have impacted care-seeking.
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-stated outcomes of interest were reported.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	
OVERALL: Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	
OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Participants were not blinded to allocation, which may have impacted care-seeking.

Gabaldon 1959 Venezuela

Methods	Dates of study: 1956-1957 Location of study: Venezuela Malaria endemicity (incidence): 0.4/1000 baseline monthly incidence Transmission season: May to November
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	<p>Malaria species: <i>P. vivax</i></p> <p>Vector species: <i>A. aquasalis</i>, <i>A. nuneztovari</i></p> <p>Study design: Uncontrolled before-and-after study</p> <p>Evaluation design: Active and passive surveillance</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: Ages > 1 month</p> <p>Sample size</p> <p>Intervention group 1 (mean): 111,995</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention group 1: Eastern Venezuela (174 localities, 3084 houses, 16,416 persons) and Western Venezuela (735 localities, 17,638 houses, 95,579 persons): MDA to all persons aged > 1 month with pyrimethamine 50 mg per week for 24 weeks from July 1957 to December 1957. Coverage not specified.</p> <p>Co-intervention with IRS.</p>
Outcomes	<p>Parasitaemia incidence</p> <p>No adverse event surveillance conducted</p> <p>No adverse events reported</p>
Notes	<p>MDA added to IRS program</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Unclear risk	MDA to all persons aged > 1 month; coverage not specified.
Domain 2.	Unclear risk	Most persons received more than 19 treatments; however, the actual figures are not reported due to "lack of mechanical tabulation of the data". The number of persons with relapses who had less than 19 treatments demonstrated similar trends to those who received 19 or more treatments.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	All houses numbered. Envelope system for drug dispensers and slide collectors. Cooperation of the people was excellent. Active search for all infections and passive search at all medical dispensaries in the area.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	Active search for all infections and passive search at all medical dispensaries in the area.
Domain 5.	High risk	Uncontrolled before-and-after study
OVERALL: Parasitemia Incidence	High risk	

Jones 1954 Kenya

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 1952-1953</p> <p>Location of study: Kenya</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): 34.8% (baseline survey in a random sample of adults and infants); 32.6% (baseline survey in school children) [Moderate]</p> <p>Transmission season: January to March, May to August</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P. falciparum</i>, <i>P. malariae</i></p> <p>Vector species: <i>A. gambiae</i>, <i>A. funestus</i></p> <p>Study design: Uncontrolled before-and-after study</p> <p>Evaluation design: Cross-sectional surveys</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All ages</p> <p>Sample size</p> <p>Intervention group 1 (mean): 3721 (including 297 school children)</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention group 1: MDA administered to all persons in Makueni with pyrimethamine 100 mg once for three rounds in September 1952, March 1953 and September 1953. Coverage not specified. No co-interventions.</p>
Outcomes	<p>Parasitaemia prevalence</p> <p>No adverse event surveillance conducted</p> <p>No adverse events reported</p>
Notes	<p>Following the first MDA round, blood smears were taken from random samples of the adult and infant (< 5 years) population and from all school children for a year. Due to the high degree of resistance that developed following two MDA rounds, parasitaemia prevalence results in the meta-analysis reflect only first round MDA results for infants and adults.</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Unclear risk	MDA administered to all persons in Makueni. Coverage not specified.
Domain 2.	Low risk	
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Measured through microscopy; blood smears collected during cross-sectional surveys. Individual data kept of all school children and of all subjects with malaria attending the dispensary.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Blood smears collected from random samples of adults and infants and of all school children monthly for a year following the first MDA round.

Domain 5.	High risk	Uncontrolled before-and-after study
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	High risk	

McLean 2021 Myanmar

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2014 to 2017</p> <p>Location of study: Myanmar</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): P falciparum < 20 cases per 1000 population per year and P falciparum/ P vivax 2.7% at baseline by rapid diagnostic test (RDT) [Low]</p> <p>Transmission season: June to August</p> <p>Malaria species: P falciparum, P vivax, P ovale, P malariae</p> <p>Vector species: Not described</p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: Artemisinin resistance reported; Kelch 13 in 57% (54/94) of samples at baseline.</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial</p> <p>Statistical power: Not statistically powered for outcomes</p> <p>For cRCTs</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Village</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: No; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using the study-provided ICC to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Not applicable</p> <p>ICC: 0.056</p> <p>Number of clusters randomized: 16</p> <p>Number of clusters analysed: 16</p> <p>Number of people: 8721</p> <p>Average cluster size: 554</p> <p>Features: Intervention and control clusters were pair-matched based on P falciparum prevalence (+/- 8%), geographical proximity and distance to main road</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All ages M 1 year and pregnant women in first trimester excluded. No primaquine administered to pregnant women in other trimesters.</p> <p>Population targeted: Intervention: 5481; Comparison: 3240</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention area:</p> <p>Drug/dose: Dihydroartemisinin (7 mg/kg) plus piperaquine (55 mg/kg) administered once a day for three days with a single dose of primaquine (0.25 mg/kg)</p> <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 3 (March, April, May 2015, during dry season)</p> <p>Interval: Every 1 month</p> <p>Duration implemented: 3 months</p> <p>Coverage (%): 90% completed at least one round; Round 1: 86%, Round 2: 86%, Round 3:</p>

	<p>88%</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs distributed at the start of study; routine malaria control by village health workers, PLUS for each case, contact tracing in the 50 km around the house for individuals testing positive for malaria.</p> <p>Comparison area: Type: No MDA and no placebo Co-interventions: LLITNs distributed at the start of study; routine malaria control by village health workers.</p>
Outcomes	<p>Parasitaemia prevalence (P falciparum and P vivax)</p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys of P falciparum and P vivax prevalence by ultrasensitive PCR in adults 18 to 55 years; up to 2 participants sampled from randomly selected households at baseline and the same participants were sampled at follow-up surveys.</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (January 2015) and at < 1 (3-8 June 2015), 3 (24-29 August 2015), 8 (15-26 January 2016), 13 (7-14 June 2016), 19 (2-19 December 2016), 25 (13-18 June 2017), and 31 (1-13 December 2017) months post-MDA</p> <p>Sample size (range): 620 to 1106 (intervention); 412 to 543 (comparison)</p> <p>Adverse effects (AEs) A total of 151 (1.4% of all doses, 3.6% of treated individuals) adverse effects reported: 12 (7.9%) not related to drug, 40 (26.5%) unlikely related to drug, 81 (53.6%) possibly related to drug, and 18 (11.9%) probably related to drug. 6 serious AEs: 1 possibly related, 5 unrelated</p>
Notes	<p>Prior to randomization, villages selected based on baseline PCR prevalence survey conducted in 58 villages in study area. Selected villages: (1) had a population between 75 to 1200 people (excluded 15 villages), and (2) were a hotspot village defined as > 30% parasite prevalence (all types) or > 10% P falciparum prevalence by PCR (excluded 27 non-hotspot villages)</p> <p>Abbreviations: ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, LLITN = long-lasting insecticide-treated bed net, MDA = mass drug administration, PCR = polymerase chain reaction</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	Allocation done by coin toss where paired villages were assigned 1:1 to control:intervention.
Domain 1b.	Low risk	Recruitment occurred after randomization but no evidence that this adversely affected arm allocation

Domain 2.	Unclear risk	In addition to MDA, there was contact tracing of all identified cases in the 50km around the case in the MDA arm only
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	High risk	The population evaluated at different time points should have remained consistent, and did not. Outcome data was assessed only in participants aged 18 to 55 years. Up to 2 participants from randomly selected households at baseline were surveyed at each time point and alternative participants (similarly matched by gender, age, and occupation) were surveyed if selected participants were unavailable during follow-up. Substantial variation in denominators suggesting different participants sampled (non-randomly) during each survey.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Laboratory staff performing PCR were unaware of the study arm allocation of samples. Use of ultrasensitive PCR provides excellent detection of even low density infections.
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-specified outcomes were reported
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	High risk	

Molineaux 1980 Nigeria

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 1970–1976 (included data from 1970–1973 in this review)</p> <p>Location of study: Nigeria</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): 46% in all ages [High]</p> <p>Transmission season: April to October</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>, <i>P. malariae</i>, <i>P. ovale</i></p> <p>Vector species: <i>Anopheles gambiae</i>, <i>A. funestus</i></p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: Not described</p> <p>Study design: Controlled before-and-after study (4 arms: no intervention, IRS only, low frequency MDA+IRS, and high frequency MDA+IRS; IRS only, low frequency+IRS, and high frequency+IRS arms included in this review)</p> <p>Statistical power: Consideration of statistical power was mentioned, but the parameters were not described.</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All ages, but infants not included in MDA until their first malaria episode.</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p>

	<p>Intervention (low frequency MDA+IRS): 14,129</p> <p>Intervention (high frequency MDA+IRS): 1,810</p> <p>Comparison (IRS only): 32,828</p>
<p>Interventions</p>	<p>Drug/dose (<i>for all intervention arms receiving MDA</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ages ≥10 years: Sulfalene-pyrimethamine (500 mg/25 mg as 1 tablet) as a single dose • Ages 5-9 years: Sulfalene-pyrimethamine (250 mg/12.5 mg as ½ tablet) as a single dose • Ages 1-4 years: Sulfalene-pyrimethamine (230 mg/12.0 mg as 30 drops syrup) as a single dose • Ages 6-11 months: Sulfalene-pyrimethamine (150 mg/7.5 mg as 20 drops syrup) as a single dose • Ages < 6 months: Sulfalene-pyrimethamine (90 mg/4.5 mg as 12 drops syrup) as a single dose <p><u>Intervention</u> (Low frequency MDA+IRS group):</p> <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 9 (April 1972 - October 1973)</p> <p>Interval: Every 10 weeks</p> <p>Duration implemented: 18 months</p> <p>Coverage (%): 73% to 92%</p> <p>Co-interventions: IRS using propoxur 3-4 rounds per year</p> <p><u>Intervention</u> (High frequency MDA+IRS group):</p> <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 23 (April 1972 - October 1973)</p> <p>Interval: Every two weeks during the wet season (May-October 1972 and May-October 1973) and every 10 weeks during the dry season (December 1972, March 1973, and October-November 1973)</p> <p>Duration implemented: 18 months</p> <p>Coverage (%): 72% to 91%</p> <p>Co-interventions: IRS using propoxur 3-4 rounds per year</p> <p><u>Comparison</u> (IRS only)</p> <p>Type: No MDA and no placebo</p> <p>Co-interventions: IRS using propoxur 3-4 rounds per year</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence</u></p>

	<p>Measurement: Cross- sectional surveys in selected village clusters (all ages) (microscopy)</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (8 surveys), During MDA (8 surveys)</p> <p>Sample size (range): 1,257-2,099 (intervention: low frequency MDA+IRS); 1,486-1,679 (intervention: high frequency MDA+IRS); 1,104-1,171 (comparison: IRS only)</p>
Notes	<p><u>Abbreviations:</u></p> <p>IRS = indoor residual spraying, MDA = mass drug administration</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	MDA administered to all ages, except for infants who have not had their first malaria episode; coverage 85%.
Domain 2.	Low risk	Contiguous areas allocated to the same treatment with similarly treated buffer zones around the evaluation villages to reduce the effect of migrations.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Operation aimed for total coverage
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Both cross-sectional surveys and active surveillance were carried out to detect cases.
Domain 5.	Unclear risk	Non-randomized controlled study
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Unclear risk	Non-randomized controlled study

Morris 2018 Zanzibar

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2016-2017</p> <p>Location of study: Zanzibar (three districts in Unguja, Central, South, and West districts)</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): 2.5% (range between clusters 0.7-4.5%) in control group at baseline by quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) [Very low - estimated <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> slide prevalence 0.2%]</p> <p>Transmission season: April to August</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P falciparum</i> (predominant), <i>P malaria</i>, <i>P ovale</i>, and <i>P vivax</i> (rare)</p> <p>Vector species: <i>Anopheles gambiae s.l.</i>, <i>An. arabiensis</i>, <i>An. merus</i> and <i>An. funestus</i>.</p>
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	<p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: No evidence of resistance to first line treatment artesunate-amodiaquine, with 100% efficacy in clinical trial conducted in 2017.</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial (allocation of Shehias within the trial arms conducted using computerized block randomisation based on shehia population size)</p> <p>Statistical power: Assuming a coefficient of variation of 0.35 and baseline malaria incidence of 12 per 1,000, there was 80% power ($\alpha=0.05$) to detect a 50% reduction in clinical malaria illness incidence in the intervention group. Study was not powered for parasitaemia prevalence.</p> <p><u>For cRCTs</u></p> <p>Unit of randomisation: Shehia (hotspot <i>Shehia</i>, defined as a Shehia with an with an annual parasite index of greater than 8 confirmed malaria cases per 1000 population)</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using an estimated ICC to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Generalized estimating equations</p> <p>ICC: Not determined</p> <p>Number of clusters randomized: 16</p> <p>Number of clusters analyzed: 16</p> <p>Number of people: 23,251</p> <p>Average cluster size: 1,453</p>
<p>Participants</p>	<p>Age groups included: All ages > 6 months. Pregnant women in their first trimester and anyone on concurrent antimalarial treatment at the time of MDA were excluded from MDA with dihydroartemisinin piperaquine. Pregnant women (all trimesters) or women breast feeding infants < 6 months were excluded from receiving low dose primaquine.</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p> <p>Intervention: 10,944</p> <p>Comparison: 12,307</p>
<p>Interventions</p>	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug/dose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ages ≥ 14 years (> 40 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperaquine (120 mg/960 mg as 3 tablets) given for three days with a single dose of primaquine (15 mg as 2 tablets) • Ages 8-13 years (21 to 40 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperaquine (80 mg/640 mg as 2 tablets) given for three days with a single dose of primaquine (7.5 mg as 1 tablet)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ages 2-7 years (10 to 20 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperaquine (40 mg/320 mg as 1 tablet) given for three days with a single dose of primaquine (4 mg as 4 cc solution) • Ages 6 months to 1 year (5 to 9.9 kg): Dihydroartemisinin plus piperaquine (20 mg/160 mg as ½ tablet) given for three days with a single dose of primaquine (2 mg as 2 cc solution) <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 2 (April 30 - May 7, 2016 at the start of high transmission season and May 28 - June 4, 2016 during the peak of high transmission season) Interval: Every 4 weeks</p> <p>Duration implemented: 6 weeks</p> <p>Coverage (%): 91% in round 1 and 88% in round 2 (DHAp); 86% in round 1 and 80% in round 2 (low dose primaquine).</p> <p>Co-interventions: IRS (single round in March 2016 with pirimiphos methyl; 85% of households sprayed at baseline) and ITNs (universal distribution campaign in 2015-2016; self-reported ITN use among all ages 75% at baseline).</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: No MDA and no placebo</p> <p>Co-interventions: IRS (single round in March 2016 with pirimiphos methyl; 85% of households sprayed at baseline)</p> <p>and ITNs (universal distribution campaign in 2015-2016; self-reported ITN use among all ages 71% at baseline).</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys of <i>P falciparum</i> (and <i>Plasmodium</i>) prevalence by two-step pooled 18s-quantitative PCR (qPCR) with first step screening by cytochrome b (Cytb) qPCR and 18s-qPCR in participants of all ages from households randomly selected (50% of households randomly selected at each time point).</p> <p>Time points: During MDA (April 30 - May 17, 2016) and 3 months post-MDA (August 30 - September 9, 2016)</p> <p>Sample size (range): 4,402-4,896 (intervention); 3,875-4,905 (comparison)</p> <p><u>Clinical malaria illness incidence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Passive case detection at health facilities via malaria case notification system which captures clinical malaria infections in real time.</p>

	<p>Time points: Pre-MDA (May - November 2015) and at 2 (May-August 2016), 5 (May-November 2016), 10 (May 2016 - April 2017), and 14 (May 2016 - August 2017) months post-MDA</p> <p><u>Adverse effects (AEs)</u></p> <p>Among participants receiving MDA, 11.6% and 3.2% reported at least one AE after the first and second round, respectively. An additional 85 and 29 AE reports were passively identified at health facilities after rounds 1 and 2, respectively. The most commonly reported AEs were: nausea and vomiting (33.1%), stomach pain and diarrhoea (18.9%), and dizziness, headache, and fatigue (23.5%). Across all AEs, 44.1% were considered mild, 52.0% as moderate, and 0.5% as severe. There were no MDA-associated deaths or other serious AEs.</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT02721186</p> <p>The timing of the first parasitaemia survey coincided with the first round of MDA and continued for 10 days following the end of the first MDA distribution; therefore, the first parasitaemia survey was considered as "during MDA".</p> <p>"Self-reported adherence to the 3-day treatment regimen was 82.0% (range between shehias 71.9–88.6%) and 93.7% (83.7–99.3%) for rounds 1 and 2, respectively. The main reason for not completing the treatment was experiencing side effects (50.1% of non-completed treatments). The self-reported adherence corresponded with day 7 piperazine concentrations at the group level."</p> <p><u>Abbreviations:</u></p> <p>ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, IRS = indoor residual spraying, ITN = insecticide-treated bednet, MDA = mass drug administration, PCR = polymerase chain reaction</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Unclear risk	Random allocation of shehias to trial arms was conducted using computerized block randomization based on shehia population size. Allocation concealment was not described. Baseline malaria prevalence was higher in control (2.5%) compared to intervention (0.8%) shehias. Baseline vector control interventions and demographic characteristics were balanced across arms.
Domain 1b.	Low risk	Baseline malaria prevalence was higher in control (2.5%) compared to intervention (0.8%) shehias. Baseline vector control interventions and demographic characteristics were balanced across arms. Distance between hotspot shehias was not described and there was no mention of buffer zones.

Domain 2.	Low risk	
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Outcomes were assessed in participants of all ages residing in randomly sampled households. 50% of households randomly selected at each survey
Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	Malaria cases reported in real time at health facilities through the malaria case notification system (MCN).
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	
Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Passive case detection at health facilities via malaria case notification system which captures clinical malaria infections in real time. Knowledge of allocation arm could have influenced care seeking
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-specified outcomes were reported.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Unclear risk	Baseline imbalance in malaria prevalence
OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Passive detection among participants with knowledge of intervention assignment.

Sterk 2020 Dem. Rep. Congo

Methods

Dates of study: September 2020- March 2021
Location of study: Democratic Republic of Congo (Angumu Health zone, Ituri province)
Malaria endemicity: High transmission
Transmission season: Three distinct seasonal peaks: April to May, July to August, and October to November.
Malaria species: *P falciparum*
Vector species: *Anopheles gambiae* and *An funestus*
Antimalarial drug resistance context: No evidence of resistance to first line treatment artesunate-amodiaquine.
Study design: Non-randomized controlled before and after study
Statistical power: The sample size was calculated to detect a 50% drop in the under 5 mortality rate (U5MR) “after” the MDA (shortest recall period, 152 days), taking into consideration the various stratifications, a U5MR of 3/10,000 children/day before the MDA based on the latest

	<p>population-based survey conducted in the HZ, expected accuracy of 1.1 before and 0.8 after the MDA, and $\alpha=0.04$.</p> <p>Unit of non-randomized group allocation: Village and IDP sites</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Generalized estimating equations</p> <p>ICC: NA</p> <p>Numbers of clusters selected: 31 clusters</p> <p>Numbers of clusters analysed: 31 clusters</p> <p>Number of people: 13645 (5439 intervention; 8215 comparator)</p> <p>Average cluster size:</p> <p>143 in the villages (26 households of 5.5 persons on average)</p> <p>365 in the IDP sites (average of 73 households [min= 10/ max=101] of 5 persons on average)</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All people ages > 2 months. Pregnant women in their first trimester as well as people with severe malaria, jaundice, or other severe disease, people with an allergy to the drug being used for MDA, and people recently treated for malaria were excluded from MDA.</p> <p>The survey included 3034 households; in each household, all people who were part of the household during the recall period (even though they have left or have died before the survey date) were included.</p> <p>Intervention:</p> <p>786 households in villages where MDA was conducted</p> <p>731 households in IDP sites where MDA was conducted</p> <p>Comparator:</p> <p>786 households in villages where MDA was NOT conducted</p> <p>731 households in IDP sites where MDA was NOT conducted</p>
Interventions	<p>Drug/ dose:</p> <p>Rounds 1 & 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ages ≥ 14 years: Artesunate Amodiaquine (100mg/270mg), 2 tablets given for three days - Ages 6-13 years: Artesunate Amodiaquine (100mg/270mg), 1 tablet given for three days - Ages 1-5 years: Artesunate Amodiaquine (50mg/135mg), 1 tablet given for 3 days - Ages 2-11 months: Artesunate Amodiaquine (25mg/67.5mg), 1 tablet given for 3 days <p>Round 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ages ≥ 15 years: Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (180mg/60mg), 3 tablets given for three days - Ages 11-14 years: Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (180mg/60mg), 2 tablets given for three days - Ages 4-10 years: Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (180mg/60mg), 1 tablets given for three days - Ages 12-48 months: Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (60mg/20mg), 2 sachet/day given for three days - Ages 2-11 months: Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (60mg/20mg), 1 sachet/day given for three days

Number of rounds (timing/ dates): 3; 2 with artesunate-amodiaquine (ASAQ) and 1 with pyronaridine-artesunate (ASAQ1 from 24 September to 13 October 2020, ASAQ2 from 9 to 27 November 2020, pyronaridine-artesunate from 17 December 2020 to 8 January 2021).

Interval: Goal was to space the rounds 28 days apart, but in practice rounds occurred as much as 7 weeks apart.

Duration implemented: Approximately 3 months.

Coverage (%): 90.5% [89-92] in villages and 96.6% [95-98] in IDP sites in round 1 and 90.9% [89-92] in villages and 96.7% [95-98] in IDP sites in round 2 (artesunate-amodiaquine) and 92.7% [91-94] in villages and 97.1% [96-98] in IDP sites in round 3 (pyronaridine-artesunate) (Based on survey results)

Co-interventions: ITNs were distributed in villages and IDP sites; ownership of at least one ITN per household in villages was 91.9% and in IDP camps 66.3% (not available by arm)

Comparison:

Type: No MDA and no placebo

Co-interventions: ITNs were distributed in villages and IDP sites; ownership of at least one ITN per household in villages was 91.9% and in IDP camps 66.3% (not available by arm)

Outcomes

Clinical malaria incidence

Surveys collected data on self-reported malaria illness in the 2 weeks preceding the surveys.

Mortality

Surveys collected data on self-reported data on mortality.

Adverse effects (AEs)

Adverse events were very rarely reported among those who received MDA, with 0.91% and 0.57% reporting adverse events after rounds 1 and 2 (artesunate-amodiaquine) and 0.3% reporting adverse events after round 3 (pyronaridine-artesunate). Overall, only 6 severe adverse events were reported. There were no MDA-associated deaths or serious AEs.

Notes

Data reported as "Feasibility of large scale Mass Drug Administration for malaria in Angumu Health zone, DRC, Sterk E et al"., MSF scientific days 2021.

Adverse events were monitored after each MDA round.

- After 1st round, over 74874 persons treated, 682 adverse events were reported (0.91%) from which 3 were severe (patients referred to the reference hospital). After investigation, none of the severe AE were associated with MDA.

- After 2nd round, over 74545 persons treated, 428 adverse events were reported (0.57%) from which 3 were severe (diarrhea, vomiting and asthenia). After investigation, none of the severe AE were associated with MDA.

- After 3rd round, over 78227 persons treated, 220 adverse events were reported (0.3%), with no severe adverse events reported.

No data on adverse events was recorded in the comparator.

Reported AEs were mainly headache and diarrhea, both for ASAQ and Pyramax.

Abbreviations: IDP= Internally displaced people (IDP), ITN= insecticide-treated bed net, MDA = mass drug administration, ASAQ = artesunate-amodiaquine

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	All people ages > 2 months except pregnant women in first trimester, people with severe malaria, jaundice, or other severe disease, people with an allergy to the drug being used for MDA, and people recently treated for malaria. Coverage > 90% in all rounds.
Domain 1b.	NA	
Domain 2.	Unclear risk	Possibility of in/out migration between areas.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence		
Domain 3. Parasitemia Incidence		
Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	Data came from a large cross sectional survey.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence		
Domain 4: Parasitemia Incidence		
Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	High risk	Survey collected self reported malaria illness; no malaria testing was conducted.
Domain 5.	Unclear risk	Non-randomized controlled study
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence		
OVERALL: Parasitemia Incidence		
OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	High risk	Excluded from this outcome as the parasitemia was self-reported and not confirmed by the study

Paik 1974 Solomon Islands A

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 1972</p> <p>Location of study: Solomon Islands (known as British Solomon Islands at the time of the study's publication)</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): 27.8% all ages (May 1972 survey) [Moderate]</p> <p>Transmission season: Rainy season December to April</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P. falciparum</i>, <i>P. vivax</i></p> <p>Vector species: <i>A. farauti</i></p> <p>Study design: Uncontrolled before-and-after study</p>
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	Evaluation design: Cross-sectional surveys, passive surveillance and active surveillance
Participants	Age groups included: All ages Sample size Intervention group 1 (mean): Not specified
Interventions	Intervention group 1 (Nggela archipelago): MDA administered to all persons with chloroquine 600 mg and pyrimethamine 50 mg monthly for four months from July to October 1972. Coverage 90%. Co-intervention with IRS.
Outcomes	Parasitaemia prevalence (includes both passive and active case detection for the period during and after the intervention) Parasitaemia incidence (population size not given) No adverse event surveillance conducted No adverse events reported
Notes	Baseline surveillance did not include active case detection

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	MDA administered to all persons; coverage 90%.
Domain 2.	Low risk	
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Unclear risk	Insufficient reporting of attrition/exclusions to permit judgement
Domain 3. Parasitemia Incidence	Unclear risk	Insufficient reporting of attrition/exclusions to permit judgement
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Cross-sectional surveys.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	Included both passive and active case detection for the period during and after the intervention.
Domain 5.	High risk	Uncontrolled before-after study
OVERALL: Parasitemia Incidence	High risk	

Paik 1974 Solomon Islands B

Methods	Dates of study: 1972-1973 Location of study: Solomon Islands (known as British Solomon Islands at the time of the study's publication) Malaria endemicity (incidence): 15/1000 baseline monthly incidence Transmission season: Rainy season December to April Malaria species: <i>P. vivax</i> , <i>P. malariae</i> Vector species: <i>A. farauti</i> Study design: Uncontrolled before-and-after study Evaluation design: Passive surveillance
Participants	Age groups included: All ages Sample size Intervention group 1 (mean): 1200
Interventions	Intervention group 1 (Wagina and Shortland): MDA administered to all persons with chloroquine 1500 mg and primaquine 75 mg over five days every three months for three rounds from October 1972 to March 1973. Coverage 90%. No co-interventions.
Outcomes	Parasitaemia incidence No adverse event surveillance conducted No adverse events reported
Notes	

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	MDA administered to all persons. Coverage 90%.
Domain 2.	Low risk	MDA administered to all persons. Coverage 90%.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Incidence	Unclear risk	Insufficient information to permit judgement
Domain 4: Parasitemia Incidence	High risk	Passive surveillance
Domain 5.	High risk	Uncontrolled before-and-after study
OVERALL: Parasitemia Incidence	High risk	

Schneider 1961 Burkina Faso

Methods	Dates of study: 1960–10–1961 Location of study: Burkina Faso Malaria endemicity (prevalence): Comparison group 1 (baseline survey): 59.4% in children 2-9 years [High]
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	<p>Transmission season: August to September</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P. falciparum</i>, <i>P. vivax</i></p> <p>Vector species: Not described</p> <p>Study design: Non-randomized controlled study (no pre-intervention measurements)</p> <p>Evaluation design: Cross-sectional surveys</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All ages</p> <p>Sample size</p> <p>Intervention group 1 (mean): 2500</p> <p>Intervention group 2 (mean): 3535</p> <p>Comparison group 1 (mean): Not specified</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention group 1: MDA administered to all persons with a combination of 600 mg base chloroquine or amodiaquine and 15 mg base primaquine every 14 days in June to December 1960 for 15 rounds. No co-intervention. Coverage 90%.</p> <p>Intervention group 2: MDA administered to all persons with 600 mg base amodiaquine and 15 mg base primaquine every 14 days in June to December 1960 for eight rounds. Coverage not specified. Co-intervention with IRS using DDT once a year in May 1960.</p> <p>Comparison group 1: Control zone free of any intervention (house spraying or treatment). Coverage not specified.</p>
Outcomes	<p>Parasitaemia prevalence</p> <p>No adverse event surveillance conducted</p> <p>No adverse events reported</p>
Notes	<p>Data on children 0-9 years were reported; however, data could only be abstracted for 2-9 years to draw appropriate comparisons. In addition, data for during MDA for the intervention groups were estimated using only October 1960 survey data; during MDA data for the comparison group was only provided for October 1960.</p> <p>Intervention sample size is based on the 2500 inhabitants of the three villages surveyed; half were randomized to receive amodiaquine and primaquine while the other half received chloroquine and primaquine.</p> <p>A third intervention group was treated with a combination of 600 mg base chloroquine or amodiaquine and 15 mg base primaquine every 14 days in June to December 1960; however, due to lack of detailed data presented, this group was not included in the meta-analysis.</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Unclear risk	Intervention group 1: MDA administered to all persons; Coverage 90%.

		Intervention group 2: MDA administered to all persons; Coverage not specified. Co-intervention with IRS using DDT once a year. Comparison group 1: Control zone free of any intervention (house spraying or treatment). Coverage not specified.
Domain 2.	Low risk	Cross sectional surveys to measure effect of intervention
Domain 3.Parasitemia Prevalence	High risk	Adults were treated during MDA, but were not included in the evaluation.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Unclear risk	Cross-sectional surveys
Domain 5.	Unclear risk	Non-randomized controlled study
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	High risk	

Shekalaghe 2011 Tanzania

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2008</p> <p>Location of study: Tanzania</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): 0% in all ages at baseline by microscopy [Very low]</p> <p>Transmission season: March to May, October to November</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i></p> <p>Vector species: Not described</p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: Not described</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial</p> <p>Statistical power: 80% power (alpha = 0.05) to detect a 10-fold lower malaria incidence in the intervention arm vs control (assuming 0.5 episodes per child) accounting for repeated measures and clustering.</p> <p><u>For cRCTs</u></p> <p>Unit of randomisation: Geographical clusters of households</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using an estimated ICC to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Generalized estimating equations</p> <p>ICC: Not described</p>
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	<p>Number of clusters randomized: 16</p> <p>Number of clusters analyzed: 16</p> <p>Number of people: 3,457</p> <p>Average cluster size: 216</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: Ages > 1 year, but individuals who had received a full dose of artemisinin-based combination therapy in the two weeks before the intervention were excluded. Pregnant women and individuals who were anaemic did not receive primaquine.</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p> <p>Intervention: 1,110</p> <p>Comparison: 2,347</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug/dose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ages ≥ 1 year: Sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (25 mg + 1.25 mg/kg as a single dose on the first day) plus artesunate (4 mg/kg/day for three days) with primaquine (0.75 mg/kg as a single dose on the third day) • Anaemic individuals: No primaquine. Sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine plus artesunate as described above. • Pregnant women: No primaquine. Sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine as described above plus amodiaquine (10 mg/kg once daily for three days) instead of artesunate. <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 1 (February-March 2008)</p> <p>Interval: Not applicable</p> <p>Duration implemented: 16 days</p> <p>Coverage (%): 94.6% received at least one dose and 93% received a complete dose of an efficacious anti-malarial drug prior to the transmission season or immediately upon arrival to the area</p> <p>Co-interventions: Reported ITN use 36.1% (2007) and a single treatment campaign for trachoma with azithromycin was undertaken by a non-governmental organisation.</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Placebo administered to all persons in eight clusters once daily over three days.</p> <p>Co-interventions: Reported ITN use 36.1% (2007) and a single treatment campaign for trachoma with azithromycin was undertaken by a non-governmental organisation.</p> <p><i>If Placebo:</i></p>

	<p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 1 (February-March 2008) Interval: Not applicable Duration implemented: 16 days Coverage (%): Not described</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys of <i>P falciparum</i> prevalence by microscopy and QT-NASBA in 50 randomly selected individuals per cluster</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (January-February 2008) and at <1 (April 2008), 2 (May 2008), 3 (June 2008), and 4 (July 2008) months post-MDA</p> <p>Sample size (range): 261–399 (intervention); 212-395 (comparison)</p> <p><u>Clinical malaria illness incidence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Active case surveillance of 150 randomly selected children (ages 1-10 years) from each arm, visited every 2 weeks to monitor symptoms and test by RDT if febrile. Passive surveillance in entire population.</p> <p>Time points: Followed every 2 weeks for 6 months (February-July 2008)</p> <p><u>Gametocyaemia prevalence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys of gametocyaemia prevalence by microscopy and QT-NASBA in 50 randomly selected individuals per cluster</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (January-February 2008) and at <1 (April 2008), 2 (May 2008), 3 (June 2008), and 4 (July 2008) months post-MDA</p> <p>Sample size (range): 261–399 (intervention); 212-395 (comparison)</p> <p><u>Adverse effects</u></p> <p>One individual was diagnosed with possibly-drug related severe skin reaction in the week following MDA.</p> <p>A second individual presented with non-drug related skin hyperpigmentation on the face. Both individuals were treated with steroids and monitored until symptoms disappeared. In those given primaquine, moderate anaemia (Hb level of <8 g/dL) was observed in 40% (6/15 individuals) of the G6PD A-, 11.1% (3/27 individuals) of the G6PD A, and 4.5% (18/399 individuals) of the G6PD B individuals; one case of severe anaemia (hemoglobin level of <5 g/dL) was observed.</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT00509015</p> <p>Due to the following reasons, we excluded this study from quantitative synthesis in this Review: outcome evaluation by 18S QT-NASBA ended prematurely during the follow-up period, we were unable to classify events in microscopy outcomes by post-MDA time point</p>

	<p>(reported in aggregate in the publication), and the baseline before MDA number of events for multiple outcomes was zero.</p> <p><u>Abbreviations:</u></p> <p>ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, ITN = insecticide-treated bednet, MDA = mass drug administration, QT-NASBA = real-time quantitative nucleic acid sequence based amplification, RDT = rapid diagnostic test</p>
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Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	Placebo controlled cluster-randomized trial
Domain 1b.	Low risk	Placebo controlled cluster-randomized trial
Domain 2.	Low risk	Placebo controlled cluster-randomized trial; "Households that were located between clusters (i.e. within 1 km distance from the boundary of intervention and/or control clusters) were considered as buffer zones. Members of these households received the intervention in order to minimize contamination."
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Random sample of individuals surveyed at baseline and follow-up.
Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	Active case surveillance of 150 randomly-selected children (ages 1 to 10 years) from each arm, visited every 2 weeks to monitor symptoms and test by RDT if febrile. Passive surveillance in entire population.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Cross-sectional surveys of P falciparum prevalence by microscopy and QT-NASBA in 50 randomly-selected individuals per cluster
Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	Active case surveillance of 150 randomly-selected children (ages 1 to 10 years) from each arm, visited every 2 weeks to monitor symptoms and test by RDT if febrile. Passive surveillance in entire population.
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-specified outcomes reported.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	

OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	
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Simeons 1938 India

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 1935</p> <p>Location of study: India</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (incidence): 156 cases/1000 baseline monthly incidence in all age groups</p> <p>Transmission season: March to August</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P. vivax</i></p> <p>Vector species: <i>A. culicifacies</i></p> <p>Study design: Uncontrolled before-and-after study</p> <p>Evaluation design: Passive surveillance</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All ages</p> <p>Sample size</p> <p>Intervention group 1 (mean): 5650</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention group 1 (Mill Area): MDA administered to all persons with atebirin intramuscular 300 mg daily for 2 days and plasmochin simplex 60 mg daily for three days once in May to June 1935. Coverage 100%. Co-intervention with oiling for larval control after MDA.</p>
Outcomes	<p>Clinical malaria incidence</p> <p>Passive event surveillance conducted</p> <p>Adverse events reported: Haemoglobinuria occurred in 4 cases (2 severe and died; 2 mild); three of the cases were from the same household and all were taking treatment for syphilis. Fatal cases known to have syphilis and unlikely to be associated with atebirin; although potentially associated with plasmochin. Abscesses reported in 49 small children and weak adults. "Giddiness" reported with atebirin.</p>
Notes	<p>Baseline monthly incidence was estimated using survey data from May 1934 to April 1935 prior to MDA. Data used in the meta-analysis was extrapolated from graphs presented in the text.</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
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Domain 1a.	Low risk	MDA administered to all persons; Coverage 100%.
Domain 2.	Low risk	Coverage 100%.
Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	High risk	Passive surveillance; unclear how care-seeking was affected by knowledge of having received MDA
Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	High risk	Passive surveillance; unclear how care-seeking or testing was affected by knowledge of having received MDA
Domain 5.	High risk	Uncontrolled before-and-after study
OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	High risk	

von Seidlein 2003 Gambia

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 1999 Location of study: The Gambia</p> <p>Malaria endemicity: 42.9% in children \leq 5 years in control at baseline [High]</p> <p>Transmission season: June to December</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i></p> <p>Vector species: Not described</p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: Not described</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial</p> <p>Statistical power: 90% power ($\alpha = 0.05$) to detect a 40% reduction in malaria incidence among children <11 years assuming coefficient of variation between pair-matched villages of 0.25, 20% loss to follow-up, and mean incidence of malaria of 1 attack per child per week during the 20 week transmission season.</p> <p><u>For cRCTs</u></p> <p>Unit of randomisation: Villages</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using an estimated ICC to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Poisson regression model adjusting for population size</p> <p>ICC: Not described</p> <p>Number of clusters randomized: 18</p> <p>Number of clusters analyzed: 18</p>
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	<p>Number of people: 3,655</p> <p>Average cluster size: 203</p> <p>Feature: Matched villages by population size, spleen rate in children <5 years, and distance from the river</p>
Participants	<p>Age groups included: All persons ≥ 6 months old; pregnant women excluded.</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p> <p><i>A total of 16,442 people, of which 14,017 people (85%) were treated (placebo or MDA) including the buffer zone. In the 18 surveillance villages, 3,404 were treated (placebo or MDA) out of 3,829</i></p> <p>Intervention: 12,331</p> <p>Control: 1,686</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug/dose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adults: Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (1500 mg/75 mg as 3 tablets) plus artesunate (200 mg as 4 tablets) given in a single day • Children (<10 kg): Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (250 mg/37.5 mg as ½ tablet) plus artesunate (4 mg/kg) given in a single day. Additional quarter tablet of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine given for every 5 kg increment in weight <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 1 (June 1999)</p> <p>Interval: Not applicable</p> <p>Duration implemented: 1 month</p> <p>Coverage (%): 89% in total population, 90.8% in evaluated group</p> <p>Co-interventions: None</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Placebo</p> <p>Co-interventions: None</p> <p><i>If placebo:</i></p> <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 1 (June 1999)</p> <p>Interval: Not applicable</p> <p>Duration implemented: 1 month</p> <p>Coverage (%): 89% in total population, 90.8% in evaluated group</p>

<p>Outcomes</p>	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys of <i>P falciparum</i> prevalence by microscopy in children and weekly surveillance in all ages</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (children ≤ 5 years, May 1999) and at 6 months post-MDA (children <11 years, November 1999)</p> <p>Sample size (range): 808-985 (intervention); 605 or 606 (comparison)</p> <p><u>Parasitaemia incidence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Weekly surveillance in children aged <11 years for cases with temperature ≥ 37.5°C and <i>P falciparum</i> parasitaemia > 5000 parasites per uL by microscopy</p> <p>Time points: at 5 months post-MDA (20 July 1999 to 2 December 1999)</p> <p>Sample size: 769 (intervention); 607 (comparison)</p> <p><u>Gametocytaemia prevalence</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys of gametocytaemia prevalence by microscopy in children</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (children ≤ 5 years) and at 6 months post-MDA (children <11 years)</p> <p>Sample size (range): 808-985 (intervention); 605 or 606 (comparison)</p> <p><u>Malaria-specific mortality</u></p> <p>Measurement: Verbal autopsy confirmed by 3 physicians in children <11 years</p> <p><u>Adverse effects (AEs)</u></p> <p>Monitored through passive and active surveillance. Active surveillance consisted of asking 90 randomly selected individuals across all 42 study area villages about AEs one month following MDA.</p> <p>AEs reported (passive surveillance system): 1 episode of pruritus in intervention group.</p> <p>AEs reported (active surveillance system): 25 of 75 individuals in intervention group remembered one or more complaints within 2 days of taking the drug including dizziness (13), fever (6), diarrhoea (5), vomiting (5) and itching (4). In the comparison group, 2 of 15 individuals (13%) who had received placebo remembered complaints</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p><u>Abbreviations:</u></p> <p>ICC = intraclass correlation coefficient, MDA = mass drug administration</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	Placebo-controlled randomized trial
Domain 1b.	Low risk	Placebo-controlled randomized trial
Domain 2.	Low risk	Placebo-controlled randomized trial
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	All children < 11 years in the surveillance villages were surveyed.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Incidence	High risk	78-92% of children were examined weekly by field workers and 87% of planned visits took place. However, malaria cases were defined as a temperature greater than or equal to 37.5 °C and parasitaemia > 5000/uL, which may have precluded asymptomatic or lower density infections and resulted in an underestimate of parasitaemia incidence.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Study personnel and participants were blinded to the intervention status.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Incidence	Low risk	Study personnel and participants were blinded to the intervention status.
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-specified outcomes reported.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	
OVERALL: Parasitemia Incidence	High risk	

von Seidlein 2019 Cambodia

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2014-2016</p> <p>Location of study: Battambang province, Cambodia</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> prevalence 0.9% in MDA villages and 2.4% in control villages at baseline by ultrasensitive polymerase chain reaction (uPCR);</p>
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	<p><i>P vivax</i> prevalence 10.7% in MDA villages and 8.8% in control villages at baseline by uPCR [Very low - estimated <i>P falciparum</i> slide prevalence 0.5%]</p> <p>Transmission season: May to October</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i></p> <p>Vector species: Not described</p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: Reduced susceptibility to artemisinins and ACT partner drug resistance</p> <p>Study design: Pair-matched cluster-randomized trial</p> <p>Statistical power: For the multi-country trial (von Seidlein 2019 Myanmar; von Seidlein 2019 Cambodia; von Seidlein 2019 Laos; von Seidlein 2019 VNM), 80% power (alpha = 0.05) to detect a 95% reduction in parasite prevalence from a baseline prevalence of 10%</p> <p><u>For cRCTs</u></p> <p>Unit of randomisation: Village</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using ICC values estimated from the study data to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Generalized estimating equations</p> <p>ICC: 0.004175 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at baseline before MDA), 0 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at post-MDA 1–3, 4-6, and 7-12 months); 0.02167 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at baseline before MDA), 0.01637 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 1–3 months), 0.02229 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 4-6 months), 0.002531 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 7-12 months)</p> <p>Number of clusters randomized: 4</p> <p>Number of clusters analyzed: 4</p> <p>Number of people: 2,770</p> <p>Average cluster size: 693</p> <p>Features: Two village pairs (4 villages) were established by geographical proximity, population size, and parasite prevalence. Within each pair, one village was randomly selected to receive early MDA, while the other village received deferred MDA</p>
<p>Participants</p>	<p>Age groups included: All ages ≥ 6 months. All pregnant women were excluded from MDA.</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p> <p>Intervention: 858</p> <p>Comparison: 1,912</p>

<p>Interventions</p>	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug/dose: Dihydroartemisinin (7 mg/kg) plus piperaquine tetraphosphate (55 mg/kg) administered once a day for 3 days. Visitors or returning residents were offered a single course of piperaquine tetraphosphate.</p> <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 3 (July, August, September 2015)</p> <p>Interval: Every 1 month</p> <p>Duration implemented: 3 months</p> <p>Coverage (%): 74% in round 1, 60% in round 2, and 71% in round 3</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs, uninterrupted access to diagnosis and treatment in study villages</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Deferred MDA administered in control villages in July, August, and September 2016</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs, uninterrupted access to diagnosis and treatment in study villages</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence (<i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i>)</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys in all ages every 3 months by uPCR; all individuals present at the time of the survey in the study villages were sampled.</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (July 2015) and at 1 (Oct 2015), 4 (Jan 2016), 7 (April 2016), and 10* (July 2016) months post-MDA</p> <p>Sample size (range): 470-543 (intervention) and 583-1,090 (control)</p> <p><u>Confirmed malaria illness incidence (<i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i>)</u></p> <p>Measurement: Passive case detection at malaria posts for measured or self-reported fever ($\geq 37.5C$) and confirmed <i>P falciparum</i> or <i>P vivax</i> infection by RDT or microscopy.</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (July 2014 - June 2015) and at 9 (July 2015 to June 2016) months post-MDA</p> <p><u>Adverse effects (AEs)</u></p> <p>AEs were assessed through active surveillance on days 1, 2, 3, and 7 following MDA rounds. AEs were reported by 46% (n=909) participants and a majority (96%) were mild; 4% (n=40) required medical attention and there were 3 non-study-related deaths. No serious AEs were reported. The most common AEs reported were dizziness (22%), headache (18%), fever (10%), and nausea (8%).</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>One of four sites from a multi-country trial in Southeast Asia (ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT01872702)</p>

	<p>Abbreviations:</p> <p>ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, LLITN = long-lasting insecticide-treated bednet, MDA = mass drug administration, uPCR = ultrasensitive polymerase chain reaction</p> <p>* Data from this survey was analyzed as post-MDA 7-12 month time point</p>
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Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Unclear risk	The randomisation was based on computer-generated random numbers provided by the trial statistician. Baseline prevalence of P falciparum substantially higher in control compared to intervention villages baseline. Small number of clusters (4 villages) randomized.
Domain 1b.	Low risk	No recruitment following randomization.
Domain 2.	Low risk	No evidence of failures in implementation.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Parasitaemia surveys were performed in all individuals aged six months or older residing in the study villages.
Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	Data collected at malaria health posts with dedicated study staff.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Parasitaemia surveys were performed in all individuals aged six months or older residing in the study villages. Laboratory staff performing PCR were unaware of the study arm allocation of samples.
Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Participants were not blinded, which may have impacted care-seeking; unclear if the health facility staff performing malaria testing were aware of which study arm participants were assigned to.
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-specified outcomes reported.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Unclear risk	Small number of clusters, baseline imbalances
OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Knowledge of allocation may have impacted care-seeking or testing by health workers.

von Seidlein 2019 Laos

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2016-2017</p> <p>Location of study: Savannakhet Province, Laos</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> prevalence 4.8% in MDA villages and 17.5% in control villages at baseline by ultrasensitive polymerase chain reaction (uPCR); <i>P vivax</i> prevalence 2.3% in MDA villages and 14.7% in control villages at baseline by uPCR [Low - estimated <i>P falciparum</i> slide prevalence 5.3%]</p> <p>Transmission season: May to October</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i></p> <p>Vector species: Not described</p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: Not described</p> <p>Statistical power: For the multi-country trial (von Seidlein 2019 Myanmar; von Seidlein 2019 Cambodia; von Seidlein 2019 Laos; von Seidlein 2019 VNM), 80% power (alpha = 0.05) to detect a 95% reduction in parasite prevalence from a baseline prevalence of 10%</p> <p>For cRCTs</p> <p>Unit of randomisation: Village</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using ICC values estimated from the study data to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Generalized estimating equations</p> <p>ICC: 0.1416 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at baseline before MDA), 0.0944 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at post-MDA 1–3 months), 0.05406 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at post-MDA 4-6 months), 0.04319 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at post-MDA 7-12 months); 0.1438 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at baseline before MDA), 0.0913 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 1–3 months), 0.02963 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 4-6 months), 0.01452 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 7-12 months)</p> <p>Number of clusters randomized: 4</p> <p>Number of clusters analyzed: 4</p> <p>Number of people: 1,889</p> <p>Average cluster size: 472</p> <p>Features: Two village pairs (4 villages) were established by geographical proximity, population size and parasite prevalence. Within each pair, one village was randomly selected to receive early MDA, while the other village received deferred MDA</p>
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Participants	<p>Age groups included: All ages \geq 6 months. All pregnant women were excluded from MDA.</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p> <p>Intervention: 1,006</p> <p>Comparison: 883</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug/dose: Dihydroartemisinin (7 mg/kg) plus piperaquine (55 mg/kg) administered once a day for 3 days with a single dose of primaquine (0.25 mg/kg).</p> <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 3 (April, June, and July 2016)</p> <p>Interval: Every 1 month</p> <p>Duration implemented: 3 months</p> <p>Coverage (%): 81% in round 1, 80% in round 2, and 82% in round 3</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs, uninterrupted access to diagnosis and treatment in study villages</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Deferred MDA administered in control villages in April, June, and July 2017</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs, uninterrupted access to diagnosis and treatment in study villages</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence (<i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i>)</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys in all ages every 3 months by uPCR; all individuals present at the time of the survey in the study villages were sampled.</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (April 2016, just prior to first MDA round) and at 1 (August 2016), 4 (late October 2016), 7 (January 2017), and 10* (April 2017) months post-MDA</p> <p>Sample size (range): 745-859 (intervention) and 618-802 (control)</p> <p><u>Adverse effects (AEs)</u></p> <p>AEs were assessed by home visits from village volunteers and clinicians following a report of an AE. Following MDA rounds, 282 individuals reported 295 AEs: 291 (99%) were mild, 3 (1%) were moderate, and 1 (<1%) was severe (case of pneumonia requiring hospitalization). The most common AEs were common cold (17%), gastritis (8%), diarrhoea (8%), vomiting (7%), dizziness (6%), pruritus (6%), watery stool (4%), nausea (3%), and headache (3%).</p>
Notes	<p>One of four sites from a multi-country trial in Southeast Asia (ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT01872702)</p>

	<p>Abbreviations:</p> <p>ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, LLITN = long-lasting insecticide-treated bednet, MDA = mass drug administration, uPCR = ultrasensitive polymerase chain reaction</p> <p>* Data from this survey was analyzed as post-MDA 7-12 month time point</p>
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Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Unclear risk	Randomisation was based on computer-generated random numbers provided by the trial statistician; Baseline prevalence of both <i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i> substantially higher in control compared to intervention villages. Small number of clusters (4 villages) randomized.
Domain 1b.	Low risk	No recruitment following randomization.
Domain 2.	Low risk	No evidence of non-adherence
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Parasitaemia surveys were performed in all individuals aged six months or older residing in the study villages.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Parasitaemia surveys were performed in all individuals aged six months or older residing in the study villages. Laboratory staff performing PCR were unaware of the study arm allocation of samples.
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-specified outcomes reported.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Unclear risk	Small number of clusters, baseline imbalance

von Seidlein 2019 Myanmar

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2013-2015</p> <p>Location of study: Kayin (Karen) state, Myanmar</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> prevalence 11.0% in MDA villages and 5.4% in control villages at baseline by ultrasensitive polymerase chain reaction (uPCR); <i>P vivax</i> prevalence 18.9% in MDA villages and 17.5% in control villages at baseline by uPCR [Low - estimated <i>P falciparum</i> slide prevalence 1.2%]</p> <p>Transmission season: June to October</p> <p>Malaria species: <i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i></p>
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	<p>Vector species: <i>Anopheles minimus s.l.</i>, <i>An. maculatus s.l.</i>, and <i>An. dirus s.l.</i></p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: “Area where artemisinin resistance is firmly established”</p> <p>Statistical power: For the multi-country trial (von Seidlein 2019 Myanmar; von Seidlein 2019 Cambodia; von Seidlein 2019 Laos; von Seidlein 2019 VNM), 80% power (alpha = 0.05) to detect a 95% reduction in parasite prevalence from a baseline prevalence of 10%</p> <p>For cRCTs</p> <p>Unit of randomisation: Village</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using ICC values estimated from the study data to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Generalized estimating equations</p> <p>ICC: 0.03512 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at baseline before MDA), 0 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at post-MDA 1–3, 4-6, and 7-12 months); 0 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at baseline before MDA, post-MDA 4-6 and 7-12 months), 0.000798 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 1–3 months)</p> <p>Number of clusters randomized: 4</p> <p>Number of clusters analyzed: 4</p> <p>Number of people: 3,238</p> <p>Average cluster size: 810</p> <p>Features: Two village pairs (4 villages) were established by geographical proximity, population size, and parasite prevalence. Within each pair, one village was randomly selected to receive early MDA, while the other village received deferred MDA</p>
<p>Participants</p>	<p>Age groups included: All ages \geq 6 months. All pregnant women their first trimester were excluded from MDA and pregnant women in any trimester were excluded from primaquine.</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p> <p>Intervention: 1,434</p> <p>Comparison: 1,804</p>
<p>Interventions</p>	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug/dose: Dihydroartemisinin (7 mg/kg) plus piperazine (55 mg/kg) administered once a day for 3 days with a single dose of primaquine (0.25 mg/kg)</p> <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 3 (May, June, July 2013 or June, July, August 2013)</p>

	<p>Interval: Every 1 month</p> <p>Duration implemented: 3 months</p> <p>Coverage (%): 66% in round 1, 56% in round 2, and 65% in round 3</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs, uninterrupted access to diagnosis and treatment in study villages</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Deferred MDA administered in control villages in January, February, and March 2014</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs, uninterrupted access to diagnosis and treatment in study villages</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence (<i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i>)</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys in all ages every 3 months by uPCR; all individuals present at the time of the survey in the study villages were sampled.</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (May 2013) and at 1 (Aug 2013), 4 (Nov 2013), and 7 (Jan 2014) months post-MDA</p> <p>Sample size (range): 419-689 (intervention) and 750-848 (control)</p> <p><u>Confirmed malaria illness incidence (<i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i>)</u></p> <p>Measurement: Passive case detection at malaria posts for measured or self-reported fever ($\geq 37.5C$) and confirmed <i>P falciparum</i> or <i>P vivax</i> infection by RDT or microscopy.</p> <p>Time points: 7 (May 2013 to January 2014) months post-MDA</p> <p><u>Adverse effects (AEs)</u></p> <p>AEs monitored by active surveillance through structured interviews on the second, third, and seventh day of MDA treatment course and by passive surveillance via reporting to medical assistants in mobile clinics located in study villages during MDA rounds. From interviews, no serious AEs were reported. The most common AEs were dizziness (n=192) and pruritus (n=17). There were three reports of black urine, from G6PD-deficient (report prior to PQ), G6PD-normal (48 hours after PQ), and G6PD-heterozygous individuals. Among patients reporting passively to mobile clinics, there were 23 serious AEs and 15 deaths that were not drug-related, 9 moderate AEs of which 4 were possibly related to the study drug, and 191 mild AEs of which 1 was highly likely related and 7 were possibly related to the study drug.</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>One of four sites from a multi-country trial in Southeast Asia (ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT01872702)</p> <p><u>Abbreviations:</u></p> <p>ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, LLITN = long-lasting insecticide-treated bednet, MDA = mass drug administration, uPCR = ultrasensitive polymerase chain reaction</p>

Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Unclear risk	Randomisation was based on computer-generated random numbers provided by the trial statistician; only 4 total sites, randomized by 2 pairs, some variability in Pf prevalence at baseline
Domain 1b.	Low risk	Village level randomization; No recruitment following randomization.
Domain 2.	Low risk	No evidence of failure to implement
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Parasitaemia surveys were performed in all individuals aged six months or older residing in the study villages.
Domain 3. Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Low risk	Data collected at malaria health posts with dedicated study staff.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Laboratory staff performing PCR were unaware of the study arm allocation of samples.
Domain 4: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Unclear if the health facility staff performing malaria testing were aware of which study arm participants were assigned to; participants were aware of intervention which could have impacted care seeking.
Domain 5.	Low risk	Reported all pre-specified outcomes.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Unclear risk	Small numbers of clusters
OVERALL: Incidence of Confirmed Malaria Illness	Unclear risk	Small numbers of clusters and possibility that knowledge of arm allocation could influence care-seeking

von Seidlein 2019 Viet Nam

Methods	<p>Dates of study: 2013-2015</p> <p>Location of study: Binh Phuoc and Ninh Thuan province, Vietnam</p> <p>Malaria endemicity (prevalence): <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> prevalence 3.9% in MDA villages and 4.1% in control villages at baseline by ultrasensitive polymerase chain reaction (uPCR); <i>P vivax</i> prevalence 6.3% in MDA villages and 7.3% in control villages at baseline by uPCR [Very low - estimated <i>P falciparum</i> slide prevalence 0.9%]</p> <p>Transmission season: May to November</p>
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	<p>Malaria species: <i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i></p> <p>Vector species: Not described</p> <p>Antimalarial drug resistance context: At the start of the study, no evidence of resistance to piperaquine and cure rates following dihydroartemisinin piperaquine (DHAp) were satisfactory. In 2016, multidrug resistance was first detected and treatment failures with DHAp have increased since then.</p> <p>Statistical power: For the multi-country trial (Landier 2017 MMRa; Tripura 2018 KHM; Pongvongsa 2018 LAO; von Seidlein 2019 Viet Nam), 80% power (alpha = 0.05) to detect a 95% reduction in parasite prevalence from a baseline prevalence of 10%</p> <p>For cRCTs</p> <p>Unit of randomisation: Village</p> <p>Adjusted analyses for clustering: Yes; however, in this review, we performed cluster adjustment of the raw data using ICC values estimated from the study data to calculate effective sample sizes</p> <p>Adjustment method: Generalized estimating equations</p> <p>ICC: 0.002464 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at baseline before MDA), 0 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at post-MDA 1–3 months), 0.003616 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at post-MDA 4-6 months), 0.006523 (<i>P falciparum</i> outcomes at post-MDA 7-12 months); 0.001502 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at baseline before MDA), 0.002539 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 1–3 months), 0 (<i>P vivax</i> outcomes at post-MDA 4-6 and 7-12 months)</p> <p>Number of clusters randomized: 4</p> <p>Number of clusters analyzed: 4</p> <p>Number of people: 2,846</p> <p>Average cluster size: 712</p> <p>Features: Two village pairs (4 villages) were established by geographical proximity, population size and parasite prevalence. Within each pair, one village was randomly selected to receive early MDA, while the other village received deferred MDA</p>
<p>Participants</p>	<p>Age groups included: All ages ≥ 6 months. All pregnant women in their first trimester were excluded from MDA and pregnant women in any trimester were excluded from primaquine.</p> <p><u>Population targeted</u></p> <p>Intervention: 1,439</p>

	Comparison: 1,407
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug/dose: Dihydroartemisinin (7 mg/kg) plus piperazine (55 mg/kg) administered once a day for 3 days with a single dose of primaquine (0.25 mg/kg).</p> <p>Number of rounds (timing/dates): 3 (November 2013, January and February 2014)</p> <p>Interval: Every 1 month</p> <p>Duration implemented: 3 months</p> <p>Coverage (%): 83% in round 1, 98% in round 2, and 99% in round 3</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs, uninterrupted access to diagnosis and treatment in study villages</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Deferred MDA administered in control villages in December 2014, January 2015, and February 2015</p> <p>Co-interventions: LLITNs, uninterrupted access to diagnosis and treatment in study villages</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Parasitaemia prevalence (<i>P falciparum</i> and <i>P vivax</i>)</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional surveys in all ages every 3 months by uPCR; all individuals present at the time of the survey in the study villages were sampled.</p> <p>Time points: Pre-MDA (November 2013, just prior to first MDA round) and at 1 (March 2014), 4 (June 2014), 7 (September 2014), and 10* (December 2014) months post-MDA</p> <p>Sample size (range): 745-859 (intervention) and 618-802 (control)</p> <p><u>Adverse effects (AEs)</u></p> <p>Twenty-two AEs were reported which included vomiting, nausea, diarrhea, labyrinth disorder, leg fracture and urticaria. Seven serious AEs were reported within the first year of the study including death from suicide, sudden death, drowning, decline due to aging, and gastric cancer.</p>
Notes	<p>One of four sites from a multi-country trial in Southeast Asia (ClinicalTrials.gov: NCT01872702)</p> <p><u>Abbreviations:</u></p>

	<p>ICC = intracluster correlation coefficient, LLITN = long-lasting insecticide-treated bednet, MDA = mass drug administration, uPCR = ultrasensitive polymerase chain reaction</p> <p>* Data from this survey was analyzed as post-MDA 7-12 month time point</p>
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Risk of bias table

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Domain 1a.	Low risk	Randomized controlled trial; intervention deferred in control villages. The randomisation was based on computer-generated random numbers provided by the trial statistician. Small number of clusters (4 villages) randomized, but baseline malaria prevalence balanced across arms.
Domain 1b.	Low risk	No recruitment following randomization.
Domain 2.	Unclear risk	Intervention and control clusters were pair-matched by geographical proximity, which likely led to a high risk of contamination due to population movement.
Domain 3. Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Cross-sectional surveys in all ages every 3 months by uPCR; all individuals present at the time of the survey in the study villages were sampled.
Domain 4: Parasitemia Prevalence	Low risk	Cross-sectional surveys in all ages every 3 months by uPCR; all individuals present at the time of the survey in the study villages were sampled. Laboratory staff performing PCR were unaware of the study arm allocation of samples.
Domain 5.	Low risk	All pre-specified outcomes reported.
OVERALL: Parasitemia Prevalence	Unclear risk	Possibility for contamination

Characteristic of excluded studies

The following studies were excluded from the quantitative synthesis. In order to ensure that each population was captured only once, when there were multiple publications from a single study, only one paper was included, however, the relevant data from excluded papers was still captured. This is indicated below as cross reference with outcomes. Studies which contributed to the contextual factor and modelling synthesis are highlighted in blue and yellow, respectively.

Key

Contextual factors

Modeling studies

Main study	Study	#	Title	Citation	REASON FOR EXCLUSION
Eisele 2020 ³² (#732)	Anonymous 2017	128	Erratum: Short-term impact of mass drug administration with dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine on malaria in southern province zambia: A cluster-randomized controlled trial (J Inf Dis (2016) 214:12 (1831-1839) DOI: 10.1093/infdis/jiw	2017. J Inf Dis;216(8):1048	No outcomes reported; linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)
	Bennett 2016	61	A longitudinal cohort to monitor malaria infection incidence in the context of a community randomized trial of mass drug administration in Southern Province, Zambia	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():489	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract - duplicate of #722; Linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)
	Bennett 2020	722	A Longitudinal Cohort to Monitor Malaria Infection Incidence during Mass Drug Administration in Southern Province, Zambia	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):54-65	Cross reference with outcomes; Linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)
	Bever 2016	67	Epidemiological and operational lessons learned from a malaria elimination campaign in zambia's lake kariba region	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():490	Contextual Factors; ASTMH abstract; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Chalwe 2016	57	Adverse event reporting from malaria mass drug administration rounds conducted in southern Zambia	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():487	Cross reference with outcomes; ASTMH abstract; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Chishimba 2020	728	Prevalence of Plasmodium falciparum and Non-falciparum Infections by Photo-Induced Electron Transfer-PCR in a Longitudinal Cohort of Individuals Enrolled in a Mass Drug Administration Trial in Southern Province, Zambia	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):82-89	No outcomes reported; Linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)
	Chiyende 2016	79	Targeted community sensitization to reduce anticipated refusals in malaria mass drug administration trial: Lessons learned from Southern Zambia	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():485	Cross reference with outcomes; ASTMH abstract; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Conner 2017	112	Programmatic mass drug administration in southern province, Zambia: An evaluation of impact and possible spill-over effects using dhis2 malaria case incidence data	2017. AJTMH;97 (5 Supplement 1)():501	No outcomes reported; ASTMH abstract; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Daniels 2020	729	Evidence for Reduced Malaria Parasite Population after Application of Population-Level Antimalarial Drug Strategies in Southern Province, Zambia	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):66-73	No outcomes reported; Linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)
	Dieye 2017	111	Malaria elimination: Engaging communities through nationwide campaigns	2017. AJTMH;97 (5 Supplement 1)():592	Contextual Factors; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)

Eisele 2015	448	Assessing the effectiveness of household-level focal mass drug administration and community-wide mass drug administration for reducing malaria parasite infection prevalence and incidence in Southern Province, Zambia: study protocol for a community randomized controlled trial	2015. Trials;16():347	Cross reference with additional details; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Eisele 2015	40	The impact of targeted mass drug administration using dihydroartemisinin-piperazine in southern province Zambia: Initial findings	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement)():83	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract - duplicate of #488; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Eisele 2016	488	Short-term Impact of Mass Drug Administration With Dihydroartemisinin Plus Piperazine on Malaria in Southern Province Zambia: A Cluster-Randomized Controlled Trial	2016. J Inf Dis;214(12):1831-1839	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Eisele 2017	108	The long-term durability of mass drug administration using dihydroartemisinin-piperazine as part of a comprehensive malaria elimination strategy in Southern province Zambia	2017. AJTMH;97 (5 Supplement 1)():309	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract, linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Finn 2016	60	Treatment adherence to dihydroartemisinin-piperazine during mass drug administration for malaria in Southern Province, Zambia	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():284	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract; Linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)
Finn 2020	727	Treatment Coverage Estimation for Mass Drug Administration for Malaria with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperazine in Southern Province, Zambia	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):19-27	Cross reference with additional details; Linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)
Finn 2020	731	Adherence to Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperazine and Plasmodium falciparum Clearance in Southern Province, Zambia	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):37-45	Cross reference with additional details; Linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)
Galactionova 2019	179	From pilots to an elimination program: How much do malaria interventions cost	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():512-513	Duplicate; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Galactionova 2020	713	Costing malaria interventions from pilots to elimination programmes	2020. Malaria journal;19(1):332	Provides Contextual Factors; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Miller 2020	730	Moving from Malaria Burden Reduction toward Elimination: An Evaluation of Mass Drug Administration in Southern Province, Zambia	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):44261	No outcomes reported; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Nct 2014	275	Mass Drug Administration With Dihydroartemisinin + Piperazine for Reducing Malaria in Southern Zambia	2014. https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT02329301 ();	Cross reference with additional details; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Porter 2016	87	Assessing associations between recent travel and malaria parasite prevalence during a mass drug administration campaign in southern Zambia	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():282	Duplicate;
Porter 2020	726	Recent Travel History and Plasmodium falciparum Malaria Infection in a Region of Heterogenous Transmission in Southern Province, Zambia	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):74-81	Contextual Factors; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
Scott 2015	36	Evaluating the costs of implementing a package of interventions and surveillance systems to support malaria elimination in southern province, Zambia: A micro-costing analysis	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement)():268	ASTMH abstract - duplicate of #725; Linked to Eisele 2020 (#723)

	Silumbe 2016	81	Transitioning an evidence-based malaria mass drug administration (MDA) research strategy to program/routine mode: Factors for consideration	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():487	Contextual Factors; ASTMH abstract; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Silumbe 2019	173	Reductions in malaria burden through the use of a scalable intervention package (SIP) in accordance with the Zambia national malaria elimination strategic plan 2017-2021: The case of Mulobezi district in Western Province	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():524	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract- data duplicated in #723; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Silumbe 2020	720	Assessment of the Acceptability of Testing and Treatment during a Mass Drug Administration Trial for Malaria in Zambia Using Mixed Methods	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):28-36	Provides contextual Factors only; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Steketee 2020	724	Implications of the MDA Trial in Southern Province, Zambia, for Malaria Control and Elimination	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):98-101	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Stuckey 2014	418	Investigating operational strategies for antimalarial drug administration in Zambia's Southern province: A simulation study	2014. AJTMH;1()():461	Duplicate;
	Stuckey 2016	467	Operational strategies of anti-malarial drug campaigns for malaria elimination in Zambia's southern province: a simulation study	2016. Malaria journal;15()():148	Modelling data; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Suresh 2018	139	Stratification of malaria transmission dynamics and optimal intervention packages in Zambia and Mozambique	2018. AJTMH;99 (4 Supplement)():357-358	No outcomes reported; ASTMH abstract; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Suresh 2019	190	Choosing the right tool for the job: Estimating effect sizes for multiple overlapping interventions in Southern Province, Zambia	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():416	No outcomes reported; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Wenger 2013	384	Modeling for malaria control and elimination scenario planning: Application of the epidemiological modeling (EMOD) malaria disease transmission kernel to community-based intervention delivery in Southern Zambia	2013. AJTMH;1()():396	No outcomes reported; ASTMH abstract ; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Wenger 2014	401	Spatial dynamics of malaria transmission in the EMOD model for campaigns targeting sustained regional elimination in Southern Zambia	2014. AJTMH;1()():14	No outcomes reported; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
	Yukich 2016	76	Cost-effectiveness of focal mass drug administration and mass drug administration with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for malaria prevention in Southern Province, Zambia: Results of a community randomized control trial	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():8	Duplicate;
	Yukich 2020	725	Cost-Effectiveness of Focal Mass Drug Administration and Mass Drug Administration with Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine for Malaria Prevention in Southern Province, Zambia: Results of a Community-Randomized Controlled Trial	2020. AJTMH;103(2_Suppl):46-53	Contextual Factors; linked to Eisele 2020 (723)
von Seidlein 2019 ⁴¹ (#596)	Adhikari 2017	526	Elements of effective community engagement: lessons from a targeted malaria elimination study in Lao PDR (Laos)	2017. Global health action;10(1):1366136	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Adhikari 2017	530	Factors associated with population coverage of targeted malaria elimination (TME) in southern Savannakhet Province, Lao PDR	2017. Malaria journal;16(1):424	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Adhikari 2018	538	Why do people participate in mass anti-malarial administration? Findings from a qualitative study in Nong District, Savannakhet Province, Lao PDR (Laos)	2018. Malaria journal;17(1):15	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Adhikari 2018	593	Perceptions of asymptomatic malaria infection and their implications for malaria control and elimination in Laos	2018. PloS one;13(12):e0208912	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)

Bertozi-Villa 2017	120	Impact of human migration patterns on malaria elimination feasibility in the greater Mekong subregion	2017. AJTMH;97 (5 Supplement 1)():522-523	Modelling data: ABSTRACT ONLY
Chaumeau 2019	616	Contribution of Asymptomatic Plasmodium Infections to the Transmission of Malaria in Kayin State, Myanmar	2019. J Inf Dis;219(9):1499-1509	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Imwong 2020	199	Molecular epidemiology of resistance to antimalarial drugs in the Greater Mekong subregion: an observational study	2020. The Lancet Infectious Diseases.;():	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Kajeechiwa 2016	482	The acceptability of mass administrations of anti-malarial drugs as part of targeted malaria elimination in villages along the Thai-Myanmar border	2016. Malaria journal;15(1):494	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Kajeechiwa 2017	661	Community engagement for the rapid elimination of malaria: the case of Kayin State, Myanmar	2017. Wellcome open research;2():59	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Landier 2016	72	Relative contribution of generalized early diagnosis and treatment and of targeted mass treatment to elimination of Plasmodium falciparum malaria in Eastern Myanmar	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():382	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Landier 2017	662	Safety and effectiveness of mass drug administration to accelerate elimination of artemisinin-resistant falciparum malaria: A pilot trial in four villages of Eastern Myanmar	2017. Wellcome open research;2():81	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Landier 2018	607	Effect of generalised access to early diagnosis and treatment and targeted mass drug administration on Plasmodium falciparum malaria in Eastern Myanmar: an observational study of a regional elimination programme	2018. Lancet (London, England);391(10133):1916-1926	Design: control group criteria not met
Li 2019	186	Spatial analysis of parasite population genomics during malaria elimination efforts in Eastern Myanmar	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():597	No outcomes reported; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Nct 2013	278	Targeted Chemo-elimination (TCE) of Malaria	2013. https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT01872702 ;():	Cross reference with additional details; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Nguyen 2017	497	Community perceptions of targeted anti-malarial mass drug administrations in two provinces in Vietnam: a quantitative survey	2017. Malaria journal;16(1):17	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Parker 2019	598	Potential herd protection against Plasmodium falciparum infections conferred by mass antimalarial drug administrations	2019. eLife;8():	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Pell 2017	511	Mass anti-malarial administration in western Cambodia: a qualitative study of factors affecting coverage	2017. Malaria journal;16(1):206	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Pell 2019	597	Community engagement, social context and coverage of mass anti-malarial administration: Comparative findings from multi-site research in the Greater Mekong sub-Region	2019. PloS one;14(3):e0214280	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)

	Peto 2018	537	Reflections on a Community Engagement Strategy for Mass Antimalarial Drug Administration in Cambodia	2018. AJTMH;98(1):100–104	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Peto 2018	539	Community participation during two mass anti-malarial administrations in Cambodia: lessons from a joint workshop	2018. Malaria journal;17(1):53	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Peto 2018	588	The feasibility and acceptability of mass drug administration for malaria in Cambodia: a mixed-methods study	2018. Trans Royal Soc Trop Med Hyg;112(6):264-271	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Phommason e 2020	624	Mass drug administrations with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine and single low dose primaquine to eliminate Plasmodium falciparum have only a transient impact on Plasmodium vivax: Findings from randomised controlled trials	2020. PloS one;15(2):e0228190	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Pongvongsa 2018	559	The dynamic of asymptomatic Plasmodium falciparum infections following mass drug administrations with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine plus a single low dose of primaquine in Savannakhet Province, Laos	2018. Malaria journal;17(1):405	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Sahan 2017	500	Community engagement and the social context of targeted malaria treatment: a qualitative study in Kayin (Karen) State, Myanmar	2017. Malaria journal;16(1):75	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Tangseefa 2018	705	"Nine Dimensions": A multidisciplinary approach for community engagement in a complex postwar border region as part of the targeted malaria elimination in Karen/Kayin State, Myanmar	2018. Wellcome open research;3():116	Contextual Factors; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Tripura 2018	1	A Controlled Trial of Mass Drug Administration to Interrupt Transmission of Multidrug-Resistant Falciparum Malaria in Cambodian Villages	2018. Clin Inf Dis;67(6):817-826	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	Tun 2017	533	Towards malaria elimination in Savannakhet, Lao PDR: mathematical modelling driven strategy design	2017. Malaria journal;16(1):483	No outcomes reported; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
	vonSeidlein 2019	619	The probability of a sequential Plasmodium vivax infection following asymptomatic Plasmodium falciparum and P. vivax infections in Myanmar, Vietnam, Cambodia, and Laos	2019. Malaria journal;18(1):449	No outcomes reported; linked to vonSeidlein 2019 (596)
Caceres 2008 ³⁰	Caceres 2004	893	Eficacia de la cura radical masiva en la incidencia malĂrrica del Municipio Marino, Estado Sucre	2004. Bol. malariol. salud ambient;():45-49	Cross reference with additional details; linked to Caceres 2005, 2008 (included)
	Caceres 2005	891	Impacto de la Cura Radical Masiva sobre la incidencia malĂrrica del estado Sucre, Venezuela	2005. Bol. Malariol. Salud Amb;45():27-36	Cross reference with additional details; linked to Caceres 2008 (included)
	Garcia 2004	884	Estado Sucre: El exito antimalajrico de Venezuela en el ano 2003	2004. Buletin de Malariologia y Salud Ambiental;44(1):51-5	Cross reference with outcomes; no control, only 1 pre-intervention time point
Jones 1958 ³⁴	Jones 1954	878	Resistance of P. falciparum and P. malariae to Pyrimethamine (Daraprim) following Mass Treatment with this Drug. A Preliminary Note	1954. East African medical journal;31(2):47-9	Cross reference with outcomes; Linked to Jones 1958 (included)
Morris 2018 ³⁶	Nct 2016	274	Effectiveness of Mass Drug Administration for Reducing Seasonal Malaria Transmission in Zanzibar	2016. https://clinicaltrials .	Registration for Morris 2018 (562) which was included

				gov/show/NCT02721186;():	
Simeons 1936 ⁴⁰	Simeons 1938	865	Follow-Up of a Mass Treatment with Injectable Atebrin	1938. Ind Med Gaz;73(12):713-715	Cross reference with outcomes; Simeons 1936 (included)
Fraser 2020	Fraser 2020	739	Evaluating the impact of programmatic mass drug administration for malaria in Zambia using routine incidence data	2020. J Inf Dis;():	Design: ITS analysis of programmatic rounds of MDA, however, IRS partially implemented at the same time as MDA, so insufficient data points to evaluate MDA alone
	Mancuso 2019	189	Ongoing assessment of plasmodium falciparum parasite prevalence in southern province Zambia: Results from a 2019 parasite survey three years after a mass drug administration trial	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():216	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to only #739 (Fraser 2020); ASTMH abstract
Mwesigwa 2019	Dial 2014	671	A qualitative study to assess community barriers to malaria mass drug administration trials in The Gambia	2014. Malaria journal;13():47	Contextual Factors; linked to 631-Mwesigwa 2019 (631)
	Dierickx 2015	47	Community barriers for the implementation of a mass drugs administration for malaria in the Gambia	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement)():197	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract - full publication is #464; linked Mwesigwa 2019 (#631)
	Dierickx 2016	464	Factors Associated with Non-Participation and Non-Adherence in Directly Observed Mass Drug Administration for Malaria in The Gambia	2016. PloS one;11(2):e0148627	Contextual Factors; linked to Mwesigwa 2019 (#631)
	Mwesigwa 2016	74	Impact of mass drug administration with dihydroartemisinin-piperazine on malaria transmission in a highly seasonal transmission setting in the Gambia	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():382	Cross reference with outcomes; ASTMH abstract - full publication is #631
	Mwesigwa 2017	103	Impact of two annual cycles of mass drug administration on temporal trends of clinical malaria	2017. AJTMH;97 (5 Supplement 1)():411	Cross reference with outcomes; ASTMH abstract - full publication is Mwesigwa 2019 (#631)
	Mwesigwa 2018	152	Impact of mass treatment with dihydroartemisinin piperazine on malaria transmission dynamics in the Gambia: A prospective study	2018. AJTMH;99 (4 Supplement)():126	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract - full publication is Mwesigwa 2019 (#631)
	Mwesigwa 2019	631	Mass Drug Administration With Dihydroartemisinin-piperazine and Malaria Transmission Dynamics in The Gambia: A Prospective Cohort Study	2019. Clin Inf Dis;69(2):278-286	Design: control group criteria not met; not designed as ITS; no control group and outcomes are Pf
	Mwesigwa 2019	609	Field performance of the malaria highly sensitive rapid diagnostic test in a setting of varying malaria transmission	2019. Malaria journal;18(1):288	No outcomes reported; full publication is Mwesigwa 2019 (#631)
	Siling 2016	73	Ignoring people 'who are not there' may mitigate success of mass drug administration for malaria: Findings from a mixed-method study in the Gambia	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():7	Contextual Factors; ASTMH abstract; linked to Mwesigwa 2019 (631)
	Wu 2018	136	Validating novel serological markers of malaria exposure: Evaluating the effect of mass drug administration (MDA) and seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) on transmission in rural Gambia based on population-level antibody responses	2018. AJTMH;99 (4 Supplement)():321-322	No outcomes reported; ASTMH abstract

Chang 2019	Chang 2019	192	Results of a pilot of targeted mass drug administration with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine and primaquine as a component of a malaria elimination package in Haiti	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():417	Design: control group criteria not met
	Chang 2019	182	Accounting for human mobility in malaria elimination programs with heterogeneous travel data	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():189	No outcomes reported
	Andrinopoulos 2016	78	Designing malaria elimination strategies to achieve high community uptake: Findings from a formative research study in the department of Grand Anse, Haiti	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():485	Contextual Factors; Linked to Chang 2019 (192); control group criteria not met
	Druetz 2019	171	Reduction in malaria prevalence in sentinel populations following introduction of a package of interventions for malaria elimination: Results from easy access group surveys in 2017 and 2018, Grande-Anse (Haiti)	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():523	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to Chang 2019
Gomez Mendoza 1960	GomezMendoza 1960	830	Observations on the programme for the employment of antimalarial drugs in the malaria eradication campaign in Venezuela.	1960. CNEP Boletin;4(2):74-81	No outcomes reported
	GomezMendoza 1960	858	Observations on the Programme for the Employment of Antimalarial Drugs in the Malaria Eradication Campaign in Venezuela [Informe del viaje efectuado para observar el programa de utilizaci3n de drogas antipal3dicas en la campa3a de erradicaci3n del paludismo en la Rep3blica de Venezuela.]	1960. CNEP Boletin;4():74-81	Duplicate; 830
Archibald 1960	Archibald 1960	895	Field trials of mass administration of antimalarial drugs in Northern Nigeria	1960. ;262():44207	Design: control group criteria not met
	Archibald 1960	894	A preliminary report on the effect of diamino-diphenyl sulphone on malaria in northern Nigeria	1960. J Trop Med Hyg;63():25-7	Intervention: not MDA
	Archibald 1960	896	The appearance of P. falciparum resistant to pyrimethamine in a northern Nigerian village	1960. West Afr Med J;9():21-5	Cross reference with outcomes; Linked to #895 (Design: control group criteria not met)
Bloch 1982	Bloch 1982	786	Teachings of the Antimalarial Campaign in El Salvador, Central America	1982. R.I.I.M.;11(2):119-124	Intervention: Insufficient information on drug administration;
	Mason 1973	765	A study of the epidemiology of malaria in a high-incidence coastal area of El Salvador, C. A	1973. Revista del Instituto de Investigaciones medicas;2(1):51-54, 55-57	Intervention: Insufficient information on drug administration; linked ot Bloch 1982
	Mason 1977	766	Malaria field studies in a high-incidence coastal area of El Salvador, C.A	1977. Bulletin of the Pan American Health Organization;11(1): 17-30	Intervention: No data on drug dose available: linked to Bloch 1982 (786)
	NaveRebollo 1973	763	Malaria in El Salvador. Control and eradication campaign analysis	1973. Revista del Instituto de Investigaciones medicas;2(1):31-39, 3-30	Intervention: not enough data in main article for ITS, no control group; Insufficient information on drug administration Linked to Bloch 1982 (786)
Galatas 2020	Brew 2017	115	The economic and educational impacts of a malaria elimination campaign in Mozambique	2017. AJTMH;97 (5 Supplement 1)():501	Duplicate; ABSTRACT; linked to Galatas 2020 (635)

	Cirera 2020	634	Moving towards malaria elimination in southern Mozambique: Cost and cost-effectiveness of mass drug administration combined with intensified malaria control	2020. PLoS one;15(7):e0235631	Contextual Factors; linked to 635, Galatas 2020
	Galatas 2019	193	The magude project: Drastic reduction of malaria burden and sustained gains after a malaria elimination project in Southern Mozambique	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():417	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract of publication #635 Galatas 2020
	Galatas 2020	635	A multiphase program for malaria elimination in southern Mozambique (the Magude project): A before-after study	2020. PLoS medicine;17(8):e1003227	Design: imbalance of interventions (blanket IRS started at the same time as phase 1)
	Gupta 2020	716	Effect of mass dihydroartemisinin-piperazine administration in southern Mozambique on the carriage of molecular markers of antimalarial resistance	2020. PLoS one;15(10):e0240174	Design: imbalance of interventions
Kaneko 2014	Kaneko 1994	876	Island malaria control in eastern Melanesia: 1) Malaria eliminated from a small island by 9-week mass drug administration and impregnated bednets	1994. J Japan. J. Parasitol.;43():358-370	Duplicate; linked to Kaneko 2000
	Kaneko 2000	748	Malaria eradication on islands	2000. Lancet;356(9241):1560-4	Imbalance of background interventions
	Kaneko 2010	823	A community-directed strategy for sustainable malaria elimination on islands: short-term MDA integrated with ITNs and robust surveillance	2010. Acta Trop;114(3):177-83	Contextual Factors; linked to Kaneko 2000
	Kaneko 2014	407	Sustainable malaria elimination on Aneityum Island, Vanuatu, 1991-2014	2014. AJTMH;1()():197	Duplicate; linked to Kaneko 2000
	Kaneko 2014	399	Community-directed malaria freedom on Aneityum Island, Vanuatu, 1991-2014	2014. Malaria Journal;1()():S25	Cross reference with outcomes; Kaneko 2000
	Canet 1949	Canet 1949	781	First Trials in Southern Indo-China of Mass Prophylaxis of Malaria with Nivaquine B (Resoquine) and with Paludrine	1949. Bulletin de la Societe de Pathologie Exotique;42(44322):165-8
Canet 1949		844	First trials in southern Indo-China of mass prophylaxis of malaria with Nivaquine B (resochine) and with Paludrine.	1949. Bulletin de la Societe de Pathologie Exotique;42(44322):165-168	Duplicate; 781 Canet 1949
Celli 1914	Celli 1903	859	La malaria in Italia durante il 1902. Parte II: Profilassi della malaria. [Malaria in Italy in 1902. Part II: Prophylaxis of Malaria]	1903. Annali di Igiene Sperimentale;13():322-343	Design: control group criteria not met
	Celli 1914	843	[English title not available.]	1914. Ann. Igiene;24(2):177-243	No outcomes reported
	Snowden 2006	799	Conquest of malaria: Italy, 1900-1962.	2006. ;():	Cross reference; linked to Celli 1914 (843)
Chaves 2020	Chaves 2020	712	Malaria Elimination in Costa Rica: Changes in Treatment and Mass Drug Administration	2020. Microorganisms;8(7):	No outcomes reported; Include for qualitative synthesis. No control group, vivax only

	MarinRodriguez 2019	627	Parasite Removal for Malaria Elimination in Costa Rica	2019. Trends in parasitology;35(8):585-588	Linked to Chaves 2020
Clyde 1961	Clyde 1958	777	Single Dose Pyrimethamine Treatment of Africans during a Malaria Epidemic in Tanganyika	1958. East African Medical Journal;35(1):23-9	Intervention: exclude as targeted MDA (sent to emergency settings review)
	Clyde 1961	778	Malaria Control in Tanganyika under the German Administration. Part II. Mass Chcmoprophylaxis in Dar es Salaam	1961. East African Medical Journal;38(2):69-82	Contextual Factors;
	Clyde 1961	779	Malaria Control in Tanganyika under the German Administration. Part I	1961. East African Medical Journal;38(1):27-42	Cross reference with additional details; Linked to 778 Clyde 1961
	Clyde 1961	838	Malaria control of Tanganyika under the German Administration. II. Mass chemoprophylaxis in Dar es Salaam	1961. East Afr Med J;38():69-82	Duplicate; Linked to 778 Clyde 1961
Zuleta 1964	DeZulueta 1961	888	The results of the first year of a malaria eradication pilot project in Northern Kigezi (Uganda)	1961. East Afr Med J;38():44222	Design: control group criteria not met; Pf, no control, only 1 area
	Zulueta 1964	860	A Malaria Eradication Experiment in the Highlands of Kigezi (Uganda)	1964. East Afr Med J;41():102-20	Design: control group criteria not met; MDA given concomitantly with DDT spray rounds, no control group (Pf)
Diallo 2016	Diallo 2014	408	A cluster-randomized trial of targeted control to eliminate malaria in central Senegal: Study design and acceptability of the interventions	2014. AJTMH;1():198	Cross reference with additional details; linked to Diallo 2016
	Diallo 2015	32	A cluster-randomized trial of targeted control to eliminate malaria in central Senegal: Main results in year 2	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement)():81	Cross reference with outcomes; linked to Diallo 2016
	Diallo 2016	70	Targetting malaria hotspots in Senegal: Results of a cluster-randomized trial	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():381	Design: control group criteria not met
	Tairou 2015	33	The costs and cost-effectiveness of two spatially targeted, multi-component malaria elimination strategies: Results of a large three-arm cluster-randomized trial in rural Senegal	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement)():81	Contextual Factors; linked to Diallo 2016 (70)
	Pactr 2013	276	A trial of targeted control to eliminate malaria in Central Senegal	2013. http://www.who.int/trialsearch/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=PACTR201310000575267 ();	Cross reference with additional details; trial registration; linked to Diallo 2016 (70)
Echodu 2018	Echodu 2018	149	Mass drug administration combined with indoor residual spraying for accelerated reduction of malaria in a high transmission setting in northeastern Uganda: Preliminary results	2018. AJTMH;99 (4 Supplement)():580	Design: <2 areas/clusters per group; Excluded because each arm has a n=1
	Elliott 2018	549	Medical and entomological malarial interventions, a comparison and synergy of two control measures using a Ross/Macdonald model variant and open malaria simulation	2018. Mathematical biosciences;300():187-200	No outcomes reported; A modeling study that does not compare outcomes according to operational design considerations; linked to Echodu 2018

	Elliott 2019	571	Synergy and timing: a concurrent mass medical campaign predicted to augment indoor residual spraying for malaria	2019. Malaria journal;18(1):160	No outcomes reported; linked to Echodu 2018
	Mulebeke 2018	145	Implementing malaria mass drug administration: Experience from a high transmission setting in Northeastern Uganda	2018. AJTMH;99 (4 Supplement)():575	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract; linked to Echodu 2018
	Mulebeke 2019	582	Implementing population-based mass drug administration for malaria: experience from a high transmission setting in North Eastern Uganda	2019. Malaria journal;18(1):271	Contextual Factors; linked to Echodu 2018 (149)
	Wanzira 2018	563	Community facilitators and barriers to a successful implementation of mass drug administration and indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Uganda: a qualitative study	2018. Malaria journal;17(1):474	Contextual Factors; linked to Echodu 2018
	Wanzira 2018	131	Community facilitators and barriers to a successful implementation of mass drug administration and indoor residual spraying for malaria prevention in Uganda	2018. AJTMH;99 (4 Supplement)():349	Duplicate; ASTMH Abstract ;
Escudie 1961	Escudie 1961	750	[Results of 2 years of antimalarial chemoprophylaxis in the rural African area in the pilot zone of Bobo Dioulasso (Haute Volta)]	1961. Med Trop (Mars);21(Special)():689-728	Design: <2 areas/clusters per group; See Escudie 1962
	Escudie 1962	751	Results of mass antimalarial chemoprophylaxis with a combination of 4-aminoquinoline and 8-aminoquinoline under rural African conditions in the region of Bobo-Dioulasso (Upper Volta) 1960. Comparative study in a zone treated with DDT and outside this zone.	1962. Medecine Tropicale;22(2):268-305	Cross reference with additional details linked to Escudie 1961
Garfield 1983	Garfield 1983	883	Changes in malaria incidence after mass drug administration in Nicaragua	1983. The Lancet;322(8348):500-503	Imbalance of background interventions;
	Garfield 1986	882	Health education and community participation in mass drug administration for malaria in Nicaragua	1986. Soc Sci Med;22(8):869-77	Contextual Factors; linked to Garfield 1983 (883)
Hsiang 2013	Hsiang 2013	233	Mass drug administration for the control and elimination of Plasmodium vivax malaria: an ecological study from Jiangsu province, China	2013. Malaria journal;12()():383	Design: No pre-intervention data or control
	Zhang 2014	690	Preparation of malaria resurgence in China: case study of vivax malaria re-emergence and outbreak in Huang-Huai Plain in 2006	2014. Advances in parasitology;86()():205-30	Cross reference with outcomes; Linked Hsiang 2013 (233)
Kagaya 2019	Idris 2016	485	High and Heterogeneous Prevalence of Asymptomatic and Sub-microscopic Malaria Infections on Islands in Lake Victoria, Kenya	2016. Scientific reports;6()():36958	No outcomes reported; linked to 642 (Kagaya 2019)
	Kagaya 2017	100	The impact of mass drug administration on submicroscopic malaria infection: A pilot study on ngodhe island in lake victoria, kenya	2017. AJTMH;97 (5 Supplement 1)():101	Duplicate; ASTMH abstract - duplicate of publication #642 (Kagaya 2019)
	Kagaya 2019	642	Malaria resurgence after significant reduction by mass drug administration on Ngodhe Island, Kenya	2019. Scientific reports;9(1):19060	Design: <2 areas/clusters per group
Kuehne 2015	Kuehne 2015	439	Malaria prevalence decreased following mass drug administration of malaria chemoprevention during the Ebola outbreak, Monrovia, Liberia, 2014	2015. Trop Med Int Health;1()():43-44	Setting: emergencies/epidemics; abstract
	Kuehne 2016	480	Impact and Lessons Learned from Mass Drug Administrations of Malaria Chemoprevention during the Ebola Outbreak in Monrovia, Liberia, 2014	2016. PloS one;11(8):e0161311	Setting: emergencies/epidemics
MendezGalvan 1984	MendezGalvan 1984	764	Evaluation of alternative scheme of treatment for malaria control	1984. Salud Publica de Mexico;26(6):561-572	Intervention: can't determine when rounds occurred. 3 rounds, monthly, uncontrolled study for pv

	MendezGalvan 1984	813	Evaluation of alternative scheme of treatment for malaria control.	1984. Salud Publica de Mexico;26(6):561-572	Duplicate: 764
Ossi 1967	Ossi 1967	761	An epidemic in the life of a malaria eradication programme	1967. Bulletin of Endemic Diseases;9(44200):44334	Contextual Factors; Uncontrolled before and after for pv, but pre-intervention and post-intervention includes cases (no denominators) in different populations. Insufficient info on outcomes to include.
	Ossi 1967	806	An epidemic in the life of malaria eradication programme.	1967. Bulletin of Endemic Diseases;9():44334	Duplicate 761
Pikul 1934	Pikul 1934	760	Experiment on the Prophylactic Use of Plasmocide in Daghestan with Observations on the Mosquito Infection Rate	1934. Meditsinskaya Parazitologiya i Parazitarnye Bolezni;3(4):322-329 pp.	Intervention: not MDA- this is MTaT
	Pikul 1934	805	Experiment on the prophylactic use of plasmocide in Daghestan with observations on the mosquito infection rate.	1934. Meditsinskaya Parazitologiya i Parazitarnya Bolezni;3(4):322-329	Duplicate;
Sergent 1913	Sergent 1913	758	[English title not available]	1913. Ann. Inst. Pasteur;27(5):373-390	No outcomes reported
	Sergent 1913	801	[Etudes epidemiologiques et prophylactiques du paludisme: neuvieme et dixieme campagnes en Algerie, en 1910 et 1911]	1913. Annales de la Institut Pasteur;27(5):373-390	Duplicate 758
Silal 2014	Silal 2014	411	Towards malaria elimination in Mpumalanga, South Africa: A metapopulation modeling approach	2014. AJTMH;1():278	Duplicate 681
	Silal 2014	681	Towards malaria elimination in Mpumalanga, South Africa: a population-level mathematical modelling approach	2014. Malaria journal;13():297	Modelling data; LINKED: 411-dup681
Sok 2016	Sok 2016	71	Comparison of mass drug administration vs. mass screening and treatment high-risk, military mobile populations to support malaria elimination in Cambodia	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1):381	Intervention: not MDA
	Manning 2018	558	Cluster-randomized trial of monthly malaria prophylaxis versus focused screening and treatment: a study protocol to define malaria elimination strategies in Cambodia	2018. Trials;19(1):558	Cross reference with additional details; linked to Sok 2016
	Manning 2018	668	Cluster-randomized trial of monthly malaria prophylaxis versus focused screening and treatment: a study protocol to define malaria elimination strategies in Cambodia 11 Medical and Health Sciences 1117 Public Health and Health Services	2018. Trials;19(1) (no pagination):	Duplicate 558

	Wojnarski 2016	86	Primaquine safety in G6PD-deficient military cohort in Cambodia using the lower-dose, extended course regimen as part of mass drug administration for malaria elimination	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1):281	Cross reference with outcomes; MAIN: Sok 2016 (71)
	NCT Trial registration	18	Malaria Elimination Pilot Study in Military Forces in Cambodia	. ;():	Cross reference with additional details; Linked to Sok 2016 (71)
Song 2010	Song 2010	863	Rapid and effective malaria control in Cambodia through mass administration of artemisinin-piperazine	2010. Malar J;9():57	No outcomes reported; Reports Pv + Pm together, no data on Pv alone
	Maude 2012	215	Optimising strategies for Plasmodium falciparum malaria elimination in Cambodia: primaquine, mass drug administration and artemisinin resistance	2012. PloS one;7(5):e37166	Modelling data; linked to Song 2010 #863
	Aguas 2018	552	Infectivity of Chronic Malaria Infections and Its Consequences for Control and Elimination	2018. Clin Inf Dis;67(2):295-302	No outcomes reported
	Ali 2017	522	Artemisinin combination therapy mass drug administration in a setting of low malaria endemicity: programmatic coverage and adherence during an observational study in Zanzibar	2017. Malaria journal;16(1):332	Contextual Factors
	Aregawi 2016	481	Impact of the Mass Drug Administration for malaria in response to the Ebola outbreak in Sierra Leone	2016. Malaria journal;15():480	Setting: emergencies/epidemics
	Baukapur 1984	787	A focal outbreak of malaria in Valsad District, Gujarat State	1984. Journal of Communicable Diseases;16(4):268-272	Setting: emergencies/epidemics
	Boni 2019	174	Antimalarial drug-resistance evolution during and after mass drug administration	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement):510	No outcomes reported;
	Brady 2017	514	Role of mass drug administration in elimination of Plasmodium falciparum malaria: a consensus modelling study	2017. The Lancet. Global health;5(7):e680-e687	Modelling data;
	Bretscher 2017	523	Modelling the benefits of long-acting or transmission-blocking drugs for reducing Plasmodium falciparum transmission by case management or by mass treatment	2017. Malaria journal;16(1):341	Modelling data;
	Briet 2017	96	Modelling to support the planning of malaria elimination in southern Palawan, the Philippines	2017. Trop Med Int Health;22 (Supplement 1):55	No outcomes reported;
	Butler 1943	783	Malaria Control Program on a South Pacific Base	1943. Naval Medical Bulletin;41(6):1603-12	No outcomes reported;
	Camponovo 2019	615	Mass campaigns combining antimalarial drugs and anti-infective vaccines as seasonal interventions for malaria control, elimination and prevention of resurgence: a modelling study	2019. BMC infectious diseases;19(1):920	Modelling data;
Cavalié 1961	Cavalié 1961	890	La campagne expérimentale d'éradication du paludisme dans le Nord de la République du Cameroun	1961. ;():	Design: <2 areas/clusters per group
	Cheah 2016	478	Antimalarial mass drug administration: ethical considerations	2016. International health;8(4):235-8	Contextual Factors;
	Chen 1999	780	[A pilot study on malaria control by using a new strategy of combining strengthening infection source treatment and health education in mountainous areas of Hainan province]	1999. Chung-Kuo Chi Sheng Chung Hsueh Yu Chi Sheng	Intervention: not MDA; Tx not administered to entire population

				Chung Ping Tsa Chih Chinese Journal of Parasitology & Parasitic Diseases;17(1):4420 0	
	Chi 2017	669	Protocol of the Project of Malaria Elimination in the Plateaux Region of the Togolese Republic (Sino-Togolese Cooperation)	2017. http://www.who.int/trialsearch/Trial2.aspx?TrialID=ChiCTR-EON-17010697 ;():	Awaiting classification; This study does not yet appear to have been published.
	Citron 2019	175	Quantifying malaria acquired during travel and its role in malaria elimination on Bioko Island	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():511	No outcomes reported; Abstract only
Ciuca 1937	Ciuca 1937	840	Experimental control of malaria with synthetic drugs.	1937. Archives Roumaines de Pathologie Experimentale et de Microbiologie;10(3): 295-306	Design: control group criteria not met
	Dapeng 1996	774	A successful control programme for falciparum malaria in Xinyang, China	1996. Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg;90(2):100-2	Design: No pre-intervention data or control;
Deng 2018	Deng 2018	591	Large-scale Artemisinin-Piperaquine Mass Drug Administration With or Without Primaquine Dramatically Reduces Malaria in a Highly Endemic Region of Africa	2018. Clin Inf Dis;67(11):1670–1676	Design: control group criteria not met; not designed as ITS; no control group
	Desowitz 1987	834	Malaria in the Maprik area of the Sepik region, Papua New Guinea: 1957-1984	1987. Trans Royal Soc Trop Med Hyg;81(1):175-176	Intervention: not MDA;
	Diallo 1983	833	Clinical consequences of chloroquine prophylaxis and of its discontinuation in an hyperendemic malarial region	1983. Dakar Medical;28(1):43-65	Intervention: not MDA; Treatment not administered to entire population
	Dolenz 2013	378	Assessing cost optimized strategies for maintaining and extending the gains against malaria	2013. AJTMH;1()():262	No outcomes reported; This is an abstract, doesn't appear to be very relevant for modelling outcomes and has not been published.
	Dupoux 1937	773	Mass Prophylaxis of Malaria in Tunis	1937. Bull. Acad. Med.;118(35):368-372 pp.	No outcomes reported;
	Farinaud 1934	831	[English title not available] [Essai de prophylaxie rationelle du paludisme en milieu infantile a Tri-Cu (Tonkin)].	1934. Bulletin de la Societe de Pathologie Exotique;627(6):568-575	Intervention: not MDA
	Farinaud 1958	898	Rapport sur les conditions d'organisation d'une campagne d'eradicacion due paludisme en Tunisie	1958. ;(EM/MAL/33):	Intervention: not MDA

	Finda 2019	178	Perspectives of key stakeholders in Tanzania on alternative technologies for malaria elimination	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():124	Irrelevant, no discussion of MDA
	Gao 2020	647	Determinants of MDA impact and designing MDAs towards malaria elimination	2020. eLife;9():	Modelling data;
	Garbern 2018	134	Effect of mass artesunate-amodiaquine distribution on Ebola-related mortality in Sierra Leone	2018. AJTMH;99 (4 Supplement)():303	Setting: emergencies/epidemics: https://academic.oup.com/ofid/article/6/7/ofz250/5498323
	Gerardin 2015	245	Mass campaigns with antimalarial drugs: a modelling comparison of artemether-lumefantrine and DHA-piperaquine with and without primaquine as tools for malaria control and elimination	2015. BMC infectious diseases;15():144	Modelling data;
	Gerardin 2016	462	Optimal Population-Level Infection Detection Strategies for Malaria Control and Elimination in a Spatial Model of Malaria Transmission	2016. PLoS computational biology;12(1):e1004707	Modelling data;
	Gerardin 2018	545	Impact of mass drug administration campaigns depends on interaction with seasonal human movement	2018. International health;10(4):252-257	Modelling data;
	Gunther 1952	828	Proguanil and malaria among non-tolerant New Guinea natives.	1952. Trans Royal Soc Trop Med Hyg;46(2):185-200	Intervention: not MDA
Henderson 1934	Henderson 1934	827	Prophylaxis of malaria in the Sudan, with special reference to the use of plasmoquine	1934. Trans Royal Soc Trop Med Hyg;28(2):157-164	Intervention: not tx dose; 1 area divided into 2 parts. For 14 days all members of Group A were treated with one tablet of quinoplasmine three times daily with the object of completely sterilizing the blood of parasites. Thereafter all were given one tablet of plasmoquine simplex, i.e. 0,02 grammes daily till the end of December. No clear data on prevalence pre-Tx
Hii 1987	Hii 1987	880	The influence of permethrin-impregnated bednets and mass drug administration on the incidence of Plasmodium falciparum malaria in children in Sabah, Malaysia	1987. Med Vet Entomol;1(4):397-407	Design: control group criteria not met; MDA+ nets vs C: MDA. Does not meet design criteria but may have info on contextual factors
	Ho 1965	770	Studies on malaria in new China	1965. Chinese Medical Journal;84(8):491-497 pp.	No outcomes reported
	Houel 1945	825	Chemoprophylaxis of malaria with monthly doses of chloroquine and amodiaquine.	1945. Bulletin de la Societe de Pathologie Exotique;47(2):254-260	Intervention: not MDA

	Houel 1954	879	Treatment of Epidemic-Malaria with a Single Dose of Pyrimethamine	1954. Bulletin de la Societe de Pathologie Exotique;47(2):262-4	Intervention: not MDA
Huehne 1971	Huehne 1971	824	Experience with an insecticide-drug combination and observations on suppressive chloroquine-pyrimethamine treatment	1971. J Trop Med Hyg;74(5):110-6	Design: control group criteria not met; uncontrolled. Only 1 site. Pf
	Husson 1906	897	Etiudes Epidemiologiques & Prophylactiques Sur Le Paludisme en Tunisie	1906. ;():	Intervention: not MDA
	Kaehler 2019	589	The promise, problems and pitfalls of mass drug administration for malaria elimination: a qualitative study with scientists and policymakers	2019. International health;11(3):166-176	Contextual Factors;
	Karl 2015	440	Mathematical models for <i>P. vivax</i> elimination	2015. Trop Med Int Health;1():105	Modelling data;
	Kasereka 2014	404	Malaria case-finding and treatment strategies in an internally displaced persons (IDP) camp in the democratic republic of Congo	2014. AJTMH;1():105	Setting: emergencies/epidemics;
	Khaing 2016	75	Evaluation of targeted mass treatment of malaria in Tanintharyi region, Myanmar: Preliminary results	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():401	Awaiting classification; abstract only;
Kligler 1931	Kligler 1931	874	Periodic Intermittent Treatment with Chinoplasmine as a Measure of Malaria Control in a Hyperendemic Area	1931. Riv Malariol;10(4):	Design: control group criteria not met;
	Kobylinski 2020	652	Safety, Pharmacokinetics, and Mosquito-Lethal Effects of Ivermectin in Combination With Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine and Primaquine in Healthy Adult Thai Subjects	2020. Clinical pharmacology and therapeutics;107(5):1221-1230	Intervention: not MDA;
	Kyaw 2019	176	Costing mass drug administration with different targeting strategies	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():123	Contextual Factors; abstract only, no data at all included here
Levenson 1943	Levenson 1943	819	Experiences in the control of a malarial focus in the north (Arehangel RÅgion) by mass chemoprophylaxis and systemic treatment of malaria patients (Russian).	1943. Meditsinskaya Parazitologiya i Parazitarnya Bolezni;12():23-38	Design: No pre-intervention data or control
	Liu 1986	818	INTEGRATED APPROACH IN MALARIA CONTROL INCLUDING ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT TO REDUCE MAN-MOSQUITO CONTACT AND REDUCTION OF INFECTION SOURCE IN HUANGHUI PLAIN	1986. CHINESE JOURNAL OF PARASITOLOGY AND PARASITIC DISEASES;4(4):246-250	Intervention: not tx dose; mixed curative and prophylactic dose;
Lwin 2015	Lwin 2015	449	Elimination of Plasmodium falciparum in an area of multi-drug resistance	2015. Malaria journal;14():319	Design: control group criteria not met;
	Lysenko 1960	817	Use of quinocide in treatment and prophylaxis of vivax malaria	1960. Bull World Health Organ;22(6):641-62	No outcomes reported;
	Muhlen 1913	810	Report of a malaria expedition to Jerusalem.	1913. Zentrablatt fur Backteriologie, Parasitenkunde,	Intervention: not MDA;

				Infektionskrankheiten und Hygiene;69(44198):41-85	
	Marasinghe 2020	205	Mass radical treatment of a group of foreign workers to mitigate the risk of re-establishment of malaria in Sri Lanka	2020. Malaria Journal;19 (1) (no pagination)(346):	Intervention: not MDA;
	Maude 2014	685	The diminishing returns of atovaquone-proguanil for elimination of Plasmodium falciparum malaria: modelling mass drug administration and treatment	2014. Malaria journal;13():380	Modelling data;
	Maude 2016	65	Mathematical modelling of tafenoquine for plasmodium falciparum malaria elimination	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1)():305	No outcomes reported;
	Merle 1955	812	[English title not available] [Problemas actuales del control y erradicacion de la malaria en America Latina].	1955. Bulletin de la Societe de Pathologie Exotique;48(2):242-269	Intervention: not MDA: Treatment not administered to entire population.
	Millar 2020	733	To screen or not to screen: an interactive framework for comparing costs of mass malaria treatment interventions	2020. BMC medicine;18(1):149	No outcomes reported;
	Millat-Martinez 2018	557	Electrocardiographic Safety of Repeated Monthly Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine as a Candidate for Mass Drug Administration	2018. Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy;62(12):	Intervention: not MDA
	Mosha 2013	229	Epidemiology of subpatent Plasmodium falciparum infection: implications for detection of hotspots with imperfect diagnostics	2013. Malaria journal;12():221	Intervention: not MDA;
	Murta 2019	576	Misperceptions of patients and health workers regarding malaria elimination in the Brazilian Amazon: a qualitative study	2019. Malaria journal;18(1):223	Contextual Factors;
Najera 1973	Najera 1973	746	Mass drug administration and DDT indoor-spraying as antimalarial measures in the norther savanna of Nigeria	1973. World Health Organization;73(817):12420	Imbalance of background interventions;
	Nankabirwa 2019	185	Quantifying the potential impact of mass drug administration on the parasite reservoir in an area of declining malaria transmission in Uganda	2019. AJTMH;101 (5 Supplement)():316-317	Modelling data;
	Nct 2018	267	Mass Drug Administration of Ivermectin and Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine as an Additional Intervention for Malaria Elimination	2018. https://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT03576313 ();	Intervention: not MDA; Protocol only. MDA Ivermectin + DP, no DP alone arm: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33211022/ ;
	Nikolov 2015	447	Modeling the effectiveness of population-level malaria infection detection strategies for optimal campaign scoping	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement)():293	No outcomes reported; Abstract only
	Norman 1952	762	An Investigation of the Failure of Proguanil Prophylaxis	1952. Trans Royal Soc Trop Med Hyg;46(6):653-5	No outcomes reported;
	Nosten 2016	489	[Elimination in South-East Asia? The role of antimalarial drugs]	2016. Elimination du paludisme en	No outcomes reported; perspective piece;

				Asie du Sud-Est? Moyens medicamenteux.;20 0(3):467-6	
	Pemberton- Ross 2016	56	Reactive case detection for malaria elimination	2016. AJTMH;95 (5 Supplement 1):283	No outcomes reported; ASTMH abstract
	Pemberton- Ross 2017	528	A stochastic model for the probability of malaria extinction by mass drug administration	2017. Malaria journal;16(1):376	Modelling data;
Ricosse 1959	Ricosse 1959	870	Results of pyrimethamine chemoprophylaxis in a pilot antimalarial prevention study in Bobo Dioulasso [Resultats d'une experimentation de chimioprophylaxie par la pyrimethamine dans la zone pilote de lutte antipaludique de Bobo Dioulasso]	1959. Bulletin de la Societe de Pathologie Exotique;52():516-5 35	Design: <2 areas/clusters per group;
Roberts 1956	Roberts 1956	745	Pyrimethamine (Daraprim) in the control of epidemic malaria	1956. J Trop Med Hyg;59(9):201-8	Design: <2 areas/clusters per group;
	Robinson 2015	600	Strategies for understanding and reducing the Plasmodium vivax and Plasmodium ovale hypnozoite reservoir in Papua New Guinean children: a randomised placebo-controlled trial and mathematical model	2015. PLoS medicine;12(10):e1 001891	No outcomes reported; targeted MDA (to children)
	Roy 2013	395	The Potential Elimination of Plasmodium vivax Malaria by Relapse Treatment: Insights from a Transmission Model and Surveillance Data from NW India	2013. PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases;7 (1) (no pagination)(e1979):	Intervention: not tx dose; Included in Mass relapse prevention review
	Runge 2020	625	Simulating the council-specific impact of anti-malaria interventions: A tool to support malaria strategic planning in Tanzania	2020. PLoS one;15(2):e0228469	Modelling data;
	Saarinen 1987	804	Mass proguanil prophylaxis	1987. The Lancet;1(8539):985- 986	Intervention: not MDA;
	Selvaraj 2019	613	Reducing malaria burden and accelerating elimination with long-lasting systemic insecticides: a modelling study of three potential use cases	2019. Malaria journal;18(1):307	Intervention: not MDA;
	Silal 2015	43	Modelling mass drug administration in malaria endemic countries in the presence of imported infections	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement):289	No outcomes reported; Abstract only;
	Silal 2015	255	Predicting the impact of border control on malaria transmission: a simulated focal screen and treat campaign	2015. Malaria journal;14():268	Intervention: not MDA;
	Silal 2015	457	Hitting a Moving Target: A Model for Malaria Elimination in the Presence of Population Movement	2015. PLoS one;10(12):e014499 0	No outcomes reported;
	Silal 2017	106	Costing malaria elimination in the Asia-pacific	2017. AJTMH;97 (5 Supplement 1):332-333	Contextual Factors; abstract only;
	Singh 1953	742	Suppressive treatment with amodiaquin	1953. Indian J Malariol;7(1):27-31	Intervention: not tx dose;
	Singh 1968	800	Epidemiological study of focal outbreak of malaria in consolidation phase area and evaluation of remedial measures in Uttar Pradesh (India).	1968. Bulletin of the Indian Society for	No outcomes reported

				Malaria and Other Communicable Diseases;5():207-220	
	Slater 2014	679	The potential impact of adding ivermectin to a mass treatment intervention to reduce malaria transmission: a modelling study	2014. J Inf Dis;210(12):1972-80	Modelling data;
	Smith 2019	621	Resurgence of malaria infection after mass treatment: a simulation study	2019. Malaria journal;18(1):409	No outcomes reported; Linked to Maud 2012 (#215)
Toyb 2016	Toyb 2016	329	Le paludisme dans l'Archipel des Comores : État des lieux en 2015 après quinze années de lutte	2016. Bull Soc Pathol Exot;109(2):107-13	Design: control group criteria not met
	VanDijk 1961	862	Mass treatment of malaria with chloroquine. Results of a trial in Inanwatan	1961. Tropical geographical medicine;13(4):351-6	Intervention: not tx dose;
	Walker 2015	25	Estimating the most resource-efficient malaria intervention packages and spatial scales to achieve elimination across Africa	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement):476-477	Duplicate #475 Walker;
	Walker 2015	46	Estimated increase in malaria morbidity and mortality in EBOLA-affected countries due to decreased healthcare capacity and the potential impact of mitigation strategies	2015. AJTMH;93 (4 Supplement):292	Duplicate;
	Walker 2015	247	Malaria morbidity and mortality in Ebola-affected countries caused by decreased healthcare capacity, and the potential effect of mitigation strategies: a modelling analysis	2015. The Lancet. Infectious diseases;15(7):825-32	Setting: emergencies/epidemics;
	Walker 2016	475	Estimating the most efficient allocation of interventions to achieve reductions in Plasmodium falciparum malaria burden and transmission in Africa: a modelling study	2016. The Lancet. Global health;4(7):e474-84	Modelling data;
	Lakshmanacharyulu	767	Control of Malaria Epidemics in a River Valley project	. ;():312-322	Intervention: not MDA
	White 1937	793	Anti-gametocyte treatment combined with anti-larval malaria control. Part II.	1937. Records of the Malaria Survey of India;7(4):221-231	Intervention: not MDA; Abstract